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Deliverable Report

D11.5

WP11 - Linking HBM, health studies and registers

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2 Abbreviations

ALSPAC	Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children
AvoHILMO	Register of Primary Health Care Visits
Defra	Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs
DH-PHE	Department of Health
DHSC	Department for Health and Social Care
DIY	Do it yourself (activities)
EA	Environment Agency
EC	European Commission
EEA	European Environment Agency
EHES	European Health Examination Survey
ESB	German Environmental Specimen Bank
EU	European Union
F2F	Face to face meeting
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HBM	Human Biomonitoring
HBM4EU	European Human Biomonitoring Initiative
HES(s)	health examination survey(s)
HILMO	Care Register for Health Care
HPRU	Health Protection Research Unit
HSfE	Health Survey for England
HSL	Health and Safety Laboratory
IC	Internal Call
ICO	UK Information Commissioner's Office
ICT	information and communication technology
IOM	Institute of Occupational Medicine
KELA	Social Insurance Institution of Finland
KouBio	Biomonitoring study of school children in Kuopio
MB	Management Board
UBA	German Environment Agency
UCL	University College London
UK	United Kingdom
UL	University of Leipzig
WP	work package

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IBMT	Fraunhofer Institute for Biomedical Engineering
LIFE	Leipzig Research Centre for Civilisation Diseases
NatCen	National Centre for Social Research
NERC-BGS	Natural Environment Research Council
NIHR	National Institute for Health Research
NHS	National Health Service
NSW	National Survey for Wales
OGD	Other Government Department
PAF	Postcode Address Files
PHE	Public Health England
PSU(s)	primary sampling unit(s)
QA/QC	quality assurance and quality control
RVI	Royal Victoria Infirmary
REC	Research Ethics Committee
SHeS	Scottish Health Survey
SOP(s)	standard operating procedure(s)
SSU(s)	secondary sampling unit(s)
TC	Teleconference
THL	Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare
WHS	Welsh Health Survey

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3 Abstract

National health examination surveys (HESs), dietary surveys and disease specific health surveys are conducted in many European countries in parallel to Human Biomonitoring (HBM) studies. Both studies use similar infrastructure and data collection methods, i.e., population samples, questionnaires, and collection and analysis of biological samples. Until now, only in few countries HBM modules are included in national HESs.

Within the European Human Biomonitoring Initiative (HBM4EU), three feasibility studies were conducted to evaluate possibilities and obstacles in combining HBM and health studies. Studies were from Finland, Germany, and UK/England.

The Finnish study, KouBio-KUOPIO study, collected information on health and chemical exposures of the 5th and 6th grade students (10-12 years) from primary schools. The German study targeted adults (40-79 years) by integrating the Human Biomonitoring (HBM) module to the existing cohort of LIFE Adult study. In the UK study, an HBM module was linked to Health Survey for England (HSfE), and the target group included both adults (20-49 years) and adolescents (16-19 years). In Finland and Germany fieldwork has been concluded, whereas in England the planning phase has been completed and the fieldwork is still to be conducted.

Feasibility studies identified several opportunities for combining HBM and health studies. By combining HBM modules to HESs higher participation rates can be obtained, and additional information from HBM can be combined to other health data from HESs. Questionnaires can be more extensive when combined to HESs, and participants more motivated to answer when they are already used to HESs and furthermore can receive their health information as an incentive. Also, access to biobank samples can provide an advantage.

Obviously, some obstacles were encountered when conducting the feasibility studies. Preparatory phase was rather time consuming in all the surveys. This was often due to ethical and GDPR issues. The COVID-19 pandemic caused major challenges to the studies. It was learned that children can be a challenging group to motivate, and often motivating of participants requires a lot of effort from the research team. The HBM4EU standard questionnaires can be problematic since they are not always specific to the study region or target population. Obtaining funding is often difficult.

In the future combining HBM studies and HESs could be a feasible and cost-effective way to conduct biomonitoring studies. Strong partnership and communication between the actors are crucial for successful activities. Partnering with an established HES can offer both benefits and challenges for the data collection, timetables, and reporting. The policy value of HBM studies might be enhanced with relatively short transition time between collection, analysis and reporting of results. It should be acknowledged that thus far most of the HES/HBM studies have focused on adults; one reason for this being the strict ethical regulations regarding minors.

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4 Background

4.1 Rationale

The European Human Biomonitoring Initiative (HBM4EU) is a joint effort of 30 countries, the European Environment Agency (EEA) and the European Commission (EC), co-funded under the Horizon 2020.

The main objective of HBM4EU is to use HBM to assess human exposure to chemicals in Europe to better understand the associated health impacts and to improve chemical risk assessment. HBM4EU will generate knowledge on chemical exposure levels in the population and their health effects.

In parallel to HBM studies, national HESs, dietary surveys and disease specific health surveys are conducted in many European countries. HESs are surveys where information collected by questionnaire(s) is complemented with information obtained by physical measurements such as blood pressure and anthropometric measurements, and by analysis of biomarkers from biological samples. The European Health Examination Survey (EHES) was established in 2010 to coordinate the development of national HESs in Europe (<http://www.ehes.info/index.htm>). Between 2014 and 2021, 10 European countries have conducted a national HES and in many countries smaller, regional or disease specific surveys or dietary surveys have been carried out (http://www.ehes.info/national/national_hes_status.htm).

Since for both HBM studies and HESs, data is collected through fieldwork, which is one of the largest expenses for such studies and for which the needed infrastructures are very similar, the potential to combine these two types of studies has been considered. This could result in more cost-effective ways to conduct health and HBM studies, and in providing data to study exposure-health outcome relationships.

HBM and health studies have many similarities in terms of infrastructure and procedures required for their implementation. However, in practice, the opportunity to add an HBM module to an ongoing/planned health study (and vice versa) is rarely used. Some reasons for this were obtained through questionnaire survey organised by WP11 in 2017 and results were reported in the HBM4EU Deliverable D11.1 Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies (see D11.1 at <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/>) and discussed during the workshop organised in June 2018 in Brussels, Belgium (see Deliverable 11.2 at <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/>).

4.2 Selection of the feasibility studies

A minimum set of criteria for the feasibility studies has been described in the HBM4EU Additional Deliverable AD11.2 Criteria for feasibility studies (see AD11.2 at <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/>). These criteria were used as basis for the Internal Call (IC) published in 2018. The process for selecting feasibility studies is described in detail in the HBM4EU Additional Deliverable AD11.3 Selection of feasibility studies for linking HBM and health studies, and linking to administrative data sources (see AD11.3 at <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/>). A short summary of the process and outcomes will be provided here.

Both HBM and health studies collect data utilising fieldwork with similar infrastructures. Therefore, combining these two study types should be theoretically possible with the added value of increased information collected on chemical exposures, health outcomes, and lifestyles. Until now, a limited

number of health measures has been included in many HBM studies, however HBM modules are seldom implemented in health studies. More information about opportunities and obstacles on linking HBM and health studies is needed.

The process for the selection of the feasibility studies under IC was followed (Figure 1.)

Figure 1: Process of selecting feasibility studies through IC

The Management Board (MB) made their decision on the outcomes of the IC during their June 2018 meeting based on the external reviews, Scientific Advisory Board recommendations and detailed discussions, and recommended two studies for funding; one from Germany and one from UK/England. Since Finland (THL) had a conflict of interest as the leader of the WP11 and therefore could not apply for IC, it was already agreed in the June 2017 MB meeting that Finland may conduct a feasibility study without participating in the IC. Thus, the following three feasibility studies were

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conducted since the Governing Board approved them in their September 2018 meeting as part of Annual Work Programme 2019. The UK, however, commenced their work in April 2021.

1. Germany: the LIFE-Adult cohort study (40-79 years). Involved partners in Germany are the Fraunhofer Institute for Biomedical Engineering (IBMT) and Leipzig Research Centre for Civilisation Diseases (LIFE).
2. UK/England: a national health examination survey (HES), Health Survey for England (HSE), including both adolescents (16-19 years) and adults (20-49 years). Involved partners in UK/England are Department of Health (DH-PHE), Institute of Occupational Medicine (IOM), Natural Environment Research Council (NERC-BGS) and Health and Safety Laboratory (HSL). The study is being undertaken only by DH-PHE, however.
3. Finland: a new study combining regular health check-ups and HBM module among 5th and 6th graders (10-12 years) students. Involved partner in Finland is the Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL).

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5 Finnish feasibility study

5.1 Preparation and description of the study

5.1.1 Background

Finland has a long, over 45-years, experience on conducting HESs among adults (Borodulin et al., 2018). A lot of information about the health (health care visits, medical operations, prescription of medications, etc.) of the population can also be obtained through administrative registers. Children and adolescents are examined regularly in child-care clinics and in school health services for health and development monitoring.

In Finland, children go through regular health check-ups several times during their first year of life and thereafter annually until they are 16 years old. These health check-ups are provided in the municipal child and school health care system, covering nearly 100 % of all children. Most of these health check-ups are conducted by a nurse, but at the age of 4 months, 18 months, 4 years, 6-8 years, 10-12 years, and 12-15 years, they include also medical examinations conducted by a doctor. Younger children and their families visit child health clinics and after starting school (7+ years), school health services. Health check-ups are regulated by legislation (<https://www.finlex.fi/en/laki/kaannokset/2011/en20110338.pdf>) and there are also nationally agreed protocols to monitor the health status and growth, covering physical, social and mental health and development of the children (Mäki et al., 2017). Information collected during these health check-ups cannot directly be used in population-based health monitoring, since there is still a lot of challenges related to the lack of standardisation in the information entered to information and communication technology (ICT) systems and in the transfer of this information to a centralised database.

THL is currently developing a system, which will collect this structured information from the health check-ups into one centralised database. This will facilitate access to nationwide health information on children. The first data to be nationally extracted will cover anthropometric measurements of height and weight to monitor overweight and obesity (Jääskeläinen et al., 2020).

5.1.2 Rationale for the selection of included chemicals

Humans are exposed to different chemicals and their mixtures in their everyday life through their living environment, products they use, diet, drinking water and occupation. For example, phthalates are used in several plastic packing materials, cleaning products, air fresheners and hygiene products such as soaps and shampoos. Also, many building materials, which include plastic contain phthalates. Similarly, bisphenols can be found in different plastic containers and dishes, car parts as well as in many cashiers' receipts (see D4.9 at <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/>).

In epidemiological studies, exposure to phthalates has been associated with obesity, asthma and different levels of cognitive disorders such as ADD and ADHD. Exposure to bisphenols is associated with obesity and different functional and behavioural disorders (see upcoming D11.4 at <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/> - status on 2021-09-07).

To be able to estimate how much we are exposed to different chemicals and which are their potential health effects, HBM studies are needed. Biomonitoring means measurement of chemicals or their metabolites in human samples, for example urine, hair, saliva or blood (see D4.9 at <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/>).

Until now, there are no population based HBM programmes in Finland. Only a limited number of targeted research studies have been carried out, and most of these studies have covered only adults. Therefore, we have little information on human exposure to different chemicals and

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therefore, collecting of new, up-to-date information especially from children is important. This type of exposure information cannot be obtained from any health care registers or through questionnaires.

5.1.3 Aim and purpose of the study

KouBio-KUOPIO study aims to collect information about health and chemical exposures of the 5th and 6th grade students (10-12 years) from the selected primary schools of Kuopio area. The study aims to assess to which extent school aged children are exposed to selected chemicals (phthalates and bisphenols measured from urine samples). In addition, one of the aims is to evaluate whether the construction years of the included school buildings reflect the results obtained by the biomonitoring samples of the students.

5.1.4 Target group and sample selection

The study covered school children from the 5th (10-11 years old) and 6th (11-12 years old) grades from selected primary schools in city of Kuopio, Finland. Schools were selected based on their willingness to participate.

Given that some of the chemicals used in building materials, for example some of the phthalates, have been banned already ten years ago, it was important to select both new and old school buildings. Depending on the size of the interested schools, 4-6 schools were aimed to be included from which 2-3 schools with children at least 10 years old, and 2-3 schools with children less than 10 years old. For the logistic feasibility, schools were located relatively close to the centre of Kuopio (radius 10 km). All the students in the 5th and 6th grades in the selected schools were invited to participate.

A minimum sample size of 300 participating children was determined through the HBM4EU requirements.

5.1.5 Recruitment of study population

Permission for the study was obtained from the City of Kuopio on the 26th of March 2019 (Issue number 2563/2019). The steps of the originally planned recruitment process are presented in the Figure 2.

Figure 2: Original recruitment process

When schools were contacted, it became evident that they were not willing to provide lists of pupils for THL to prepare materials with pseudonymised identifiers for pupils. Therefore, the recruitment process had to be changed before the start of the actual study.

New protocol included additional steps for the coordination team to ensure that each pupil could be identified at the end and linked to written informed consent and possibly also to data from administrative registers. In the new protocol, the number of pupils in each school (5th and 6th grade) were estimated based on the information on the web pages of the schools and suitable number of pseudonymised material packages were prepared. The material package (Figure 3.) included an invitation and information letter, instructions for spot urine sample collection, questionnaire, and informed consent form together with sample collection materials. Identification stickers were placed on all these materials to allow linkage between the different materials.

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Figure 3: Photo of the material package

Otherwise, the protocol was as originally planned, i.e. schools contacted parents to inform about the study, THL representative visited schools and distributed materials, parents made the decision whether their child/children would participate and filled in the questionnaires, and children provided urine samples to be mailed to THL.

5.1.6 Collection of information

Basic information about students (name, address, social security number) was supposed to be available through student lists of the schools but since schools were not able to provide these lists, information was obtained through questionnaire. Further information about the health status of students, needed for evaluation of potential, also unknown, health effects of measured chemicals, was obtained through different administrative registers.

- Registers from the National Institute for Health and Welfare, THL
 - Care Register for Health Care (HILMO)
 - Register of Primary Health Care Visits (AvoHILMO)
- Registers from the Social Insurance Institution of Finland, KELA
 - Prescription of medicines
 - Entitlement to reimbursement of drug expenses

Record linkage was planned to be performed to reduce participant's reporting burden. However, this requires use of personal identifier (social security number).

Information which was not available through registers such as lifestyle information and diet were obtained through a questionnaire which was filled in at home by the parents/legal guardians. Furthermore, urine sample was taken at home according to the instructions provided (see Appendix 1).

Children and their parents/guardians were given detailed information concerning the research, voluntary participation and consent as well as guidance in collecting and posting the urine samples. Contact details for the responsible researcher were provided. Information on the use of the samples and the distribution of the data outside the EU/ETA countries were disclosed. Material was also made available through project web site at <http://thl.fi/koubio> which also included a link to the HBM4EU web site (<https://www.hbm4eu.eu/>).

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School visits and material distribution was conducted by a member of the research group. During the school visits all the children received a package including the following items:

- Information on the research letter,
- Consent form (2 pieces; one to keep and one to return in the return box),
- Instructions on urine sample collection,
- Questionnaire (paper questionnaire and instructions on how to alternatively fill in an online questionnaire), and
- Equipment for the sample collection (500 ml canister, wooden mixing stick, 2 Falcon sampling tubes, plastic bag, drying material for posting, return box for the sample and paper questionnaire).

Families had the possibility to either fill in the questionnaire online or manually in the paper form. Guardians were advised to send back the return box including the consent form, details of the sample, questionnaire (if not filled online), and the urine sample. Postal fees of the return boxes were covered by THL. Invitation letter, information letter, consent form, instructions on urine sample collection and questionnaire (in Finnish and in English) are attached as appendices to this document (Appendix 1.)

5.1.7 Measurement methods

From each child participating to the study, the following information/samples were collected based on the written informed consent of their parents/legal guardian (Table 1).

Table 1: Sources of information collected from the children

Source of the information	Information/samples
Administrative registers	Anthropometric measurements of height and weight, blood pressure (Avohilmo) Medical history and follow-up information (Avohilmo and Hilmo) Medical prescriptions and entitlement to reimbursement of drug expenses (KELA)
Questionnaire	Dietary habits Living environment Lifestyle Health Socio-demographic information
Biological samples	One spot urine sample
Informed consent	Name and social security number

Phthalates and bisphenols were analysed from urine sample and remaining urine samples were stored for potential future analysis. For the potential new analyses, separate ethical approval, and necessary informed consent, will be obtained.

Chemical Risks team at the Environmental Health Unit of THL performed the chemical analysis of phthalates and bisphenols from urine (Larsson et al., 2014) with an accredited methods FINAS, testing laboratory (T077, SFS-EN ISO/IEC 17025). This laboratory also participated in the HBM4EU quality control rounds and passed them for phthalates and bisphenols.

The questionnaire of background information and chemical specific questions on lifestyle and living environment was based on the general, broad, questionnaire prepared within HBM4EU. However,

KouBio questionnaire was shortened to a total of 11 pages by removing all questions that were not relevant for phthalates and bisphenols. It was anticipated that participation rate would be increased with a questionnaire of moderate length.

5.1.8 Conducting the study

The study was conducted by the Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL), Finland. The Principal Investigator was prof. Hannu Kiviranta. Other researchers of the study group from THL included MD Jouni Tuomisto, senior researchers Hanna Tolonen, Panu Rantakokko, Merja Korkalainen and Päivi Ruokojärvi and chemist Jani Koponen who was responsible for the analysis of phthalates and bisphenols.

5.1.9 Timing of the study

The originally planned timeline of the study is given in the table below (Table 2). All preparations for fieldwork were planned to be ready in early autumn, term starting in August 2019.

Table 2: Original timeline

	2018		2019											
	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Preparation of the study plan														
Contacts to school and school health care systems														
Contacts to individual schools														
Process of obtaining ethical approval														
Questionnaire and other material (electronic material, printing etc.)														
Fieldwork														

Laboratory analysis of the biological samples and reporting of the results were planned to be finished during the first half of 2020.

The actual timeline (Table 3) turned out to be very different due to delay in obtaining required approval from the city authorities and ethical board, strike of the postal services and at the final stage, the COVID-19 pandemic. Detailed reasons for the delay are explained in the section 5.2 *Experiences and self-assessment* below.

Table 3: Actual timeline

	2018		2019											
	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Preparation of the study plan														
Contacts to school and school health care systems														
Contacts to individual schools														
Process of obtaining ethical approval														
Questionnaire and other material (electronic material, printing etc.)														

Actual timelines for fieldwork and laboratory analysis are shown in the Table 4 below.

Table 4: Actual timelines for fieldwork and laboratory analysis

	2020												2021			
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4
Fieldwork																
Contacts to individual schools																
Laboratory analysis of the urine samples																
Start of the reporting of the results																

5.1.10 Budget and funding

There was a funding from HBM4EU (50%) and THL/STM (50%) for study preparation and sample collection until the end of 2019. The funding covered 8 months of researcher time (37 600€ including employment side costs) and purchase of materials and services (5 000€). Total funded budget was 50 000€, which included 7 500€ of overhead.

No direct financial resources from the city of Kuopio were obtained. However, working hours of teachers were needed to help to inform about the study and to distribute the material to children.

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5.1.11 Ethics and data confidentiality

Ethical approval for KouBio-KUOPIO study was applied from the Ethical Board of the Kuopio University hospital (Ethical approval no 887/2019 dated on 30 July 2019). Application contained study plan and several other documents related to the study. After ethical acceptance, schools were contacted. When the willingness of the schools to participate was confirmed, parents/guardians were contacted.

Children and their parents/guardians who were interested to participate to the study were provided with an information letter (see Appendix 1), which contained detailed information about the study and its aims. Participation to the study was voluntary and each participant had an opportunity to withdraw from the study at any stage without further explanations.

A written informed consent of the parents/legal guardian of the children was obtained before urine sample was collected or questions were asked (see Appendix 1).

Data confidentiality had a high priority. All samples and data collected in the project were collected, processed, stored and disposed of in accordance with the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) Regulation. Privacy statement (see Appendix 1) for the study was prepared, presented at the study web site and provided as a written copy to the parents/legal guardians.

All questionnaires and sample collection material were pseudonymised. Access to the personal information was limited only to a few people at THL. THL's data is stored in secure environments such as databases, registries and network drives, which are access-controlled and backed up regularly. Access to THL's servers is provided only for ICT maintenance purposes and to dedicated personnel. THL has a standardised backup procedure, which is monitored and tested.

5.1.12 Publication of study results

Results of the study will be published nationally. Due to low number of participants, only descriptive results can be published. Data will be made available for the HBM4EU community and possible international publication of the results will be conducted together with other HBM4EU project results.

The results of individual subjects are not reported to the above-mentioned reports because there are no reference values for the compounds to be measured, which would allow meaningful interpretation of the results.

5.2 Experiences and self-assessment

5.2.1 Planning and preparation

There were several surprisingly time-consuming phases in the arrangement of the HBM study and in obtaining the ethical permission from the ethical board of the Kuopio University Hospital, which is necessary for studies involving human subjects. Steps and timelines needed to get all required permissions are described below.

Preparation of a general study brochure for the City of Kuopio day care and school authorities was finished in November 2018. Their primary approval was needed before the study plan could be sent to the ethical board of the Kuopio University Hospital. The first contact to the school authorities in order to address the brochure to the right decision-makers took place on the 30th November 2018.

After sending some emails requesting for the right contacts, on the 4th December 2018 the study brochure was sent to the persons in charge, who had the authority to either approve or reject the

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study proposal on behalf of the City of Kuopio. After several unanswered emails and phone calls to the key persons (and to the potential secondary persons), a reply was finally received on the 14th of February 2019 (i.e. after 2.5 months waiting). A link to a detailed Research Permission Form of the City of Kuopio was received. In order to fill in the form some more background work and a full study plan had to be prepared. After a detailed preparation, the Research Permission Form was submitted on the 27th of February 2019. After several emails to confirm the receipt of our application, a positive decision for the conduct of the research was received from the City of Kuopio on the 26th of March 2019.

The applications to the Ethical Board of the Kuopio University Hospital required six additional documents with the main research plan: information letter, informed consent form, study questionnaire, Finnish summary of the study plan (original was in English), self-assessment of the ethical issues and data protection notification. It was particularly complex to interpret how GDPR-requirements could be met by the informed consent. A data protection officer in THL was consulted in this matter. Next viable deadline for the submission of the material to the Ethical Board was on the 6th of May 2019 and their meeting was held on the 21st of May. A list containing 18 correction requests was required to be answered by the 24th of May. This was a relatively long and extensive list considering that our team in THL consisted of experienced experts in human health surveys and HBM.

Corrections were sent to the next ethical board meeting, which was held on the 7th of June. Again, the Ethical Board required two more corrections dealing with the GDPR and insurance details of the study subjects, and these were to be answered by the 28th of June. The corrections were submitted on the 8th of July. As July is a holiday season in Finland, a positive answer wasn't received until the 30th of July 2019. The total time from the first contact to the Kuopio day care and school authorities to the ethical permission was 8 months, which turned out to be critical as described below.

In the original study plan blood samples were aimed to be taken in addition to urine samples. Sampling was planned to take place within the context of regular health check-ups conducted at the age of 10-12 years by a doctor and a nurse. In the first version of the study plan sent to the ethical board, the following text was written concerning the sampling plans:

“During the regular health check-up at the school nurse/doctor, height and weight of the child will be measured as well as blood pressure. During this visit, a spot urine sample will be collected. If allowed by the ethical approval and parents of the child, also venous blood sample will be collected and processed by THL study personnel.”

The ethical board requested for more detailed description of the process of receiving the informed consent prior to the sampling conducted at the health check-ups. The delays in the process before receiving the ethical permission revealed that there was not enough time to obtain the informed consents from parents well in advance before the check-ups, which would start a few weeks after pupils return to school in early August. For this reason, it was decided to take urine samples at home. As the decision was taken to move sampling from the schools to homes, the blood samples were dropped out. This decision was easy to make, since the Ethical Board had also called for more detailed justification for blood sampling. The participation rate was hoped to be increased by donating cinema tickets to children, and this was indicated in the information letter to parents and children. However, the Ethical board disallowed this.

5.2.2 Fieldwork

After receiving the ethical approval, the contacts to the schools were initiated. The plan was to start the fieldwork in November 2019, but this had to be postponed due to the strike of the postal

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service, which might have jeopardised the transfer of urine samples. Finally, the fieldwork was started in February 2020, but had to be stopped shortly after in March 2020 due to the COVID-19 pandemic. By that time, five out of seven originally planned schools had been visited. In order to plan the missing visits, the remaining schools were contacted after school summer holidays (July-mid-August 2020) when the COVID-19 situation in Finland was very good. The schools still had restrictions, i.e. outside visitors were not allowed. Therefore, an alternative approach had to be worked out again. The material was provided to the schools, and teachers distributed it to pupils.

After all, the recruitment and sampling procedure shown in the study plan was followed. Some comments concerning the process:

- Contacts preceding the visits to the schools went well, although it was not always clear who was responsible for arranging the visit at the schools (a principal, a class-level team leader or an individual teacher).
- Teachers were generally not interested in the research, which in part may have been reflected in the students.
- The teachers should have been informed about the research before the school visits, so that they would have been able to motivate and inspire the children.
- The visits themselves went well. Only one of the schools didn't have an audio-video equipment and the teachers hadn't been informed about the content of the visit in advance.
- If the presentations at the schools had been more participatory, perhaps the interest in participating in the research would have been increased.
- The group sizes in the schools were too large for the presentations to allow the students to participate.
- After the presentations, more than half of the students tried to leave without the sampling packages.
- Participation in the study was voluntary, which meant that some students might not have participated because an adult/a parent/a guardian "tells you to do so".
- Sampling should have been conducted during health check-ups as originally planned to obtain better participation.
- More efforts would have been needed to get guardians excited about the study and motivate children to participate.
- A short non-response questionnaire was distributed to the parents through the schools. Only 18 responses were received. Reasons for non-participating were either that they were not interested in the study or their child did not want to provide a urine sample. Also, COVID-19 isolation was mentioned as a reason.
- 12% of the participants limited their informed consent to the EU, i.e. they did not allow data to be transferred outside the EU/EEA countries.

5.2.3 Sample analysis and record linkage

The fieldwork was finalised in November 2020. It turned out that the applied process was not successful, i.e. only 66 responses and urine samples out of 1 200 potential participants originally recruited (about 6%) were obtained. Samples and data are analysed in 2021.

Due to very low number of participants, planned record linkage to the administrative registers was not conducted as it would not have provided any usable data for further analysis.

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5.2.4 Cost-effectiveness of the study

The budget for study preparation and fieldwork was 50 000€ (see above), i.e. the cost per collected sample was 760€. When analysis is added to the cost, it adds up to a total of more than 900€/sample. Cost per invited children was approximately 38€. Due to changes in data collection protocol (mailed samples etc.), sample collection costs were higher than anticipated.

This kind of costs do not make studies with the current setup feasible.

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6 German feasibility study

6.1 Study preparation and description of the study

6.1.1 Background

Major aim of the HBM4EU initiative is to link Health Examination Surveys (HES) and Human Biomonitoring (HBM) Surveys to gain the maximum benefit from the resulting synergy effects which could result in a more cost-effective implementation of both. The study design of HES and HBM surveys has major operational and infrastructural aspects in common, but it still differs in specific requirements regarding fieldwork, pre-analytical and analytical phase, as well as sample storage. In accordance with standard operating procedures (SOPs) developed in HBM4EU WP 7 and the guidelines for linking HBM and health studies developed in HBM4EU WP11, the Fraunhofer IBMT developed a concept for an HBM module and a strategy for its integration in the LIFE-Adult study. The conducted feasibility study was focused on the integration of this HBM module in the well-established HES LIFE in Germany (https://life.uni-leipzig.de/de/erwachsenen_kohorten/life_adult.html).

This HBM module has been set up considering specifications of HBM4EU to guarantee comparable sampling procedures and, thus, to gather comparable data. Collected data and samples of this feasibility study will be available for HBM4EU partners and will provide valuable and additional data complementary to the GerES VI operated by the German Environment Agency (UBA). The region around Leipzig and Halle was and is a major industrial site with chemical industry and soft coal opencast mining and brown coal power stations.

6.1.2 Requirement Analysis

As a first step towards the integration of an HBM module into the ongoing HES LIFE, the following documents and processes were screened by IBMT to determine whether they meet the requirements of HBM:

- general requirements (Table 5),
- ethical and legal documents (Table 6)
- personnel requirements for HBM (Table 7),
- requirements for fieldwork site (Table 10),
- available questionnaires & data (Table 9, Table 11 and Table 12),
- pre-analytical processes (e.g. sampling, sample preparation, storage) including sample types (matrix, volume, sample containers) (Table 8 and Table 12), and
- quality assurance and quality control.

The aim of this analysis was the identification of gaps and potential for optimisation and harmonisation to fulfil HBM specific requirements. Required alterations to make the LIFE-Adult procedures suitable for HBM purposes were identified, and a specific HBM module was developed to be integrated in the follow-up programme.

The assessment of suitability of the LIFE-Adult study protocols and procedures for HBM purposes was based on comparing the respective LIFE-Adult study protocols and questionnaires to the guidelines for integration of HES and HBM surveys developed by WP11 (Deliverable D11.1 at <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/>). The following sections represent a listing of prerequisites for integration of HBM into HES surveys as laid out in the guidelines of D11.1, and whether they are fulfilled by the LIFE-Adult study.

Table 5: General requirements for sampling

	HBM survey	Fulfilled in LIFE	Remarks
Definition of target population (geographical coverage, age, etc.)	General population of people with permanent residence in the country/study area	√	
	Age group 0-79 years	(√)	Age at baseline examination: 18-79 (main age-range from 40-79 years) First Follow-up: all participants with brain MRI in baseline
Sampling frame	Depends on national availability and legal possibilities to use different sampling frames. Whenever possible, a central file with the most recent and best coverage of the people in the target population should be used. Ideally this would be a population register.	√	Baseline: Address lists of randomly sampled citizens were provided by the resident's registration office of the city of Leipzig
Sample size (N of persons to be invited)	At least 500 persons/country, depending on participation rate. I.e. data from at least 300 participants is expected.	√	Baseline: 10k Follow up: 2k+
Eligibility criteria	Within defined age group, alive and still living in the study area	(√)	Baseline: age and gender stratified; Leipzig main residence Follow up: still alive, with brain MRI at baseline
Sampling scheme	Two-stage sampling	√	
	PSU: Study area/geographical area	√	
	SSU: people, addresses, household or dwellings depending on available sampling frames	√	
Expected participation rate	60%	√	Baseline 33% Follow up: 72%

Table 6: Ethical and legal requirements for HBM

	HBM survey	Fulfilled in LIFE	Remarks
Regulation/legislation	National acts regulating the status and/or rights of the patients and national medical research acts must be followed	√	
	National ethical principles of research involving humans and international biomedical research guidelines must be considered	√	
Ethical approval	Ethical approval must be obtained from a relevant ethics committee	√	
Informed consent	Written informed consent is required from all study participants before any measurements or biological sample collection can be initiated	√	
Data protection	Data protection, national regulations and institutional guidelines must be followed, safeguarding all personal data of the survey participants	√	

Table 7: Personnel requirements for HBM

	HBM survey	Fulfilled in LIFE	Remarks
Coordinator	Project leader/Principle investigator(s)	√	
	Fieldwork supervisor	√	
	ICT support for fieldwork team(s) if ICT systems are used	√	
Fieldwork	Qualifications and number of fieldwork team members is dependent on included measurements, sample size and its geographical extend, and length of the fieldwork	√	
	Nurses	√	
	Laboratory personnel (in some countries it is required that blood samples are drawn by certified phlebotomists)	√	
	Interviewers (if self-administered questionnaires are not used)	√	
Sample handling and processing	Laboratory personnel	√	
Data handling and processing	Data-entry clerks	√	
	ICT experts (data management)	√	
	Scientists	√	
Reporting	Scientists	√	
	Public health experts	(√)	participating scientists from various research institutions

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Table 8: Requirements for the collection of biological samples in HBM

	HBM survey	Fulfilled in LIFE	Remarks
Sample types	Blood (serum, plasma, whole blood)	√	
	Urine (preferably 24h pool but first morning void and random spot may be used)	√	Random spot samples
Pre-analytic requirements	Urine: for collection of first morning void it is relevant to note the time of the collection as well as the time of the void prior to the collected. For 24-hour pools note the time of the last void before start of collection and the time of the last void collected.	√	Known time of urine sample (in study center)
	Equipment used for sample collection (e.g. tubes, needles, containers etc.) should preferably be tested, for if they contain/leak the compounds to be analysed, they could be a source of contamination of samples. If contamination is detected, the source should be replaced, if possible.	√	
Amount	Blood: plain serum gel tube (9/8 mL)	√	Basis - Serum: 8*750 µL (Kryo)+ 12 * 500 µL (Straws) = 12 mL Follow-up – Serum: 5*500 µL (Straws) = 2.5 mL
	Urine: At least one 2 mL, preferably more for long term storage	√	Basis – Urine: 3*750 µL (Kryo) = 2.25 mL
Sample collection	Blood:		
	Sitting posture preceded by 10-15 min rest	√	
	From the arm that was not used for blood pressure measurement, i.e. from left arm	√	
	Avoiding prolonged venous occlusion by tourniquet	√	
	Blood and urine: Field blank samples should preferably be collected in parallel with sampling of the biological samples	x	Implemented for urine in the HBM module
Sample handling and processing on the field	Blood:		
	Before centrifugation, make sure that the blood has clotted in the plain serum and plasma tubes (at least 20 minutes)	√	
	Centrifugate tubes at room temperature (20-25°C) for 10 minutes at 2000rpm. Plain serum tubes within 30-60 minutes from venipuncture. Plasma tubes within 60 minutes from venipuncture.	x	10 min, 2750 x g, T= 15°C Plain serum tubes within 30-45 minutes from venipuncture.

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	HBM survey	Fulfilled in LIFE	Remarks
			Plasma tubes within 120 minutes from venepuncture max (mean time is 90 min).
	Immediately after centrifugation transfer serum/plasma into storage tubes	√	
	Urine:		
	Transfer into storage tubes	√	
	For 24-hour urine: measure and record the volume of the full pool before transferring aliquots into storage tubes	Not applicable	
Sample storage on the field	Blood and urine:		
	Samples should be frozen as soon as possible but can be kept at 4-8°C for up to 24h	√	
	Long term storage at least -20°C but preferably -70°C or less	√	-80°C or < -150°C
Sample transfer	Either the primary or secondary receptacle must be leak proof	√	
	For liquids, add enough absorbent to the primary containers	√	
	For frozen or refrigerated samples, place dry ice/refrigerant packs outside of secondary packaging	√	

Table 9: Key health examinations and analysis of biomarkers in HBM

	HBM survey	Fulfilled in LIFE	Remarks
Anthropometric measurements	Mandatory:		
	Height	√	
	Weight	√	
	Waist circumference	√	
	Additionally:		
	Hip circumference	√	
	Body composition by bioimpedance	√	
Clinical measurements	Mandatory:		
	Blood pressure	√	
	Additionally:		

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	HBM survey	Fulfilled in LIFE	Remarks
	Pulse	√	
	Cognitive function test	√	
	Multiple other measurements: e.g. Ultrasound of vascular system, ECG, liver elasticity ultrasound, ...	√	
Biological measurements	Mandatory:		
	Urinary creatinine	√	At baseline
	Cotinine (sensitive biomarkers for exposure to tobacco smoke)	x	
	Additionally (useful to maximise the possibilities to interpretive levels of exposure for metals and to link to potential health issues):		
	Iron status (blood ferritin and transferritin)	√	At baseline
	Iodine status (T4, TSH)	√	At baseline
	Glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c)	√	At baseline
	Biomarkers of renal dysfunction (some contaminants being quantified in urine)	√	At baseline

Table 10: Requirements for fieldwork site

	HBM survey	Fulfilled in LIFE	Remarks
Blood pressure	Quiet room with comfortable temperature	√	
Anthropometrics	Privacy	√	
Collection of biological samples	Room where potential external contamination can be avoided	√	

In more detail, the following questionnaires of the LIFE study were carefully screened by IBMT regarding their usability for HBM purposes:

- socio-demographic status,
- occupation and occupational exposure,
- self-reported height and weight,
- lifestyle questions on smoking,
- general health status,
- use of medication,
- minimum European health module, and
- home and household environment.

Table 11: Key questionnaire topics for HBM

		HBM survey	Fulfilled in LIFE	Remarks
Contents	<u>SES background</u>	Sex	√	
		Age/date of birth	√	
		Marital status (additional information)	√	
		Education	√	
		Labour status	√	
		Employment status and profession	√	
		Household composition (optional information)/Family structure	√	Number of people within household, number of people < 14 years old
		Income	√	
		Nationality and/or place of birth	√	
		Ethnic origin (if accepted by national legislation)	x	
		Area of residence	√	
		Workplace area/address	√	
	<u>Health status</u>	General health	√	
		Medical history	√	
		Family health related history	√	Available in baseline
	<u>Use of health care services</u>	Visits to the doctor	(x)	Limited info available, possibly obtainable via health insurance providers
		Previous hospital admissions	(√)	Available for major diseases (e.g. myocardial infarction, stroke, depression)
		Prescription of medicines by a doctor	√	
	<u>Anthropometrics</u>	Self-reported height and weight	√	
	<u>Lifestyle</u>	Smoking and E-cigarette	√	
		Alcohol consumption	√	

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		HBM survey	Fulfilled in LIFE	Remarks
		Sun exposure	√	
		Physical activity	√	
		Occupational activities and exposures	(√)	Current occupation/ last occupation before retirement no info on exposures
		Sedentary behaviours	x	
		Diet (depending on chemical substance also data on packaging, cooking process and hygiene)	(√)	No info on cooking process and hygiene
		Consumption of locally produced foods	x	
		Individual and domestic uses of chemicals (depending on chemical substance)	(√)	Available for a subset of the participants
		Living environment (in terms of environmental exposure: industries, farms, traffic)	(√)	Use of register data of the Saxon authorities, allocation of the loads to geodata of the residential address
		Hobbies	x	
Mode of data collection		Self-administered or interview depending on national practices and the setting of the fieldwork	√	

6.1.3 Subset of prioritised substances

The following subset of prioritised substances was selected to fulfil the requirements as laid out in the HBM4EU guidelines of D11.1 (see D11.1 at <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/>), to focus on substances relevant for the geographic region, and to avoid overstraining of participants:

- Phthalates
- Arsenic and its compounds
- Mercury and its organic compounds

As a further criterion for the selection, the availability of suitable samples from the baseline examination of LIFE Adult Study participants in the LIFE biobank with sufficient volume for the respective analysis was considered (Table 12.). Measuring the urinary concentrations of these chemicals or their metabolites is the most common biomonitoring approach for assessing human exposure with the advantage that urine can be collected fast, easy, and non-invasive. It was

therefore decided to collect spot urine samples from a subset of 400 participants of the LIFE follow-up.

However, since only a limited sample volume was collected so far, we adapted the collection procedure of spot urine samples and increased the sample volume to 3 x 4mL spot urine for each participant and introduced sample tubes with a respective sample volume.

Table 12: Requirements for 1st priority chemicals

Chemical	Sample	Amount of sample	Storage	Accepted materials	Special requirements	Fulfilled in LIFE	Remarks
Phthalates / DINCH	Urine	0.25-0.50 mL	-20 °C or lower	PP- and PE-plastic	Phthalate-containing materials must be avoided	√	
Bisphenols	Urine	0.25-0.50 mL	-20 °C or lower	PP- and PE-plastic		√	
Per-/Poly-fluorinated compounds	Serum	0.25-0.50 mL	-20 °C or lower	PP- and PE-plastic	No special requirement, except fluorinated materials must be avoided	√	
Flame Retardants	Urine	5-10 mL	-20 °C or lower	PP- and PE-plastic	Potential target compound contamination by sampling devices should be explored before sampling if possible	x	Needed volume not available
	Serum	1-2 mL				√	
Cd, Cr	Urine	20 mL	-20 °C or lower	PP- and PE-plastic	Special-washed containers must be used, and no preservatives may be added. Specimen is prone to contamination.	x	Needed volume not available
Cd	Blood	5 mL whole blood	-20 °C or lower	heparinised vacuum tube	Specimen is prone to contamination	x	Needed volume not available
PAHs and air pollutants	Urine	5-10 mL	-20 °C or lower	PP- and PE-plastic		x	Needed volume not available
Aniline family: Aniline, 4.4'-MDA, MOCA	Urine	20 mL	-20 °C or lower	PP- and PE-plastic	Specimens are prone to contamination. Aniline: no preservative 4.4'-MDA: sulfamic acid added as preservative	x	Needed volume not available

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Chemical	Sample	Amount of sample	Storage	Accepted materials	Special requirements	Fulfilled in LIFE	Remarks
					MOCA: no preservative		
Chemical mixtures	Urine	5-10 mL	-20 °C or lower	PP- and PE-plastic	Potential target compound contamination by sampling devices should be explored before sampling if possible	x	Needed volume not available
	Serum	1-2 mL				√	
Emerging chemicals	Urine	5-10 mL	-20 °C or lower	PP- and PE-plastic	Potential target compound contamination by sampling devices should be explored before sampling if possible	x	Needed volume not available
	Serum	1-2 mL				√	

6.1.4 Development of a questionnaire

Based on the following questionnaires provided by HBM4EU a combined questionnaire was developed focusing on the selected, above-mentioned compounds:

- D7.6 – Annex 1.1 Single Questionnaire (1st round priority substances)
- D7.6 – Annex 1.2: Basic questionnaire (2nd round priority substances)
- D7.6 – Annex 1.4: Matrix-specific questionnaires to accompany the sampling of urine and blood (2nd round priority substances)

In order to avoid double data collection, the HBM module was compared with the LIFE questionnaires. especially designed for the integration in the LIFE were translated into German (the German forms can be found in Appendix Only information, which was not already surveyed with the LIFE questionnaire, was recorded. As no German questionnaire versions were available, all questions of the questionnaire 2).

6.1.5 Study design -Target group

The LIFE-Adult-Study is a population-based cohort study. In the study, the baseline examination has been completed for 10,000 randomly selected inhabitants of Leipzig in 2014. Leipzig is a major city of 550,000 inhabitants located in the east of Germany. The LIFE-Adult-Study is the first study of this kind and size among an urban population from the east of Germany. The study is conducted by the Leipzig Research Center for Civilisation Diseases (LIFE). LIFE is part of the Medical Faculty of the University of Leipzig, enabling participation of clinical and epidemiological researchers experienced in the field of metabolic, neurological, cardiovascular, allergic and ophthalmological disorders.

The LIFE-Adult-Study pursues the following major goals:

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- to assess the prevalence and incidence of common diseases and subclinical disease phenotypes,
- to investigate the complex interactions between molecular-genetic and lifestyle factors regarding co-occurrence and development of subclinical phenotypes and diseases, and
- to investigate in a longitudinal extension of the study the role of biomarkers to predict risks for disease progression.

In 2017, the first follow-up was started aiming to recruit approximately 2,700 participants (most of them 60 years and older) of the 10,000 participants of the baseline study. This provided the opportunity to integrate an HBM module into the LIFE Health Survey. This HBM-tool was tested by a subset of 400 participants in the final stage of the follow-up (2019-2020).

6.1.6 Ethics and data confidentiality

Prior to the study, a study protocol was drawn up and a vote of the competent ethics committee (Ethics Committee at the Medical Faculty of the University Leipzig - 201/17-ek) was obtained. All participants who had taken part in the MRI examination of the LIFE basic examination and whose consent for re-contacting was given, were invited to participate in the follow-up examination.

One of the aims of the LIFE Adult study is to search for environmental factors influencing development of civilisation diseases in a population-based cohort. For this reason, the study protocol and the informed consent is very broad, and it was possible to implement all necessary processes to conduct this pilot study in the study programme.

6.1.7 Recruitment of study population

All 10,000 participants in the LIFE Adult study were randomly selected from the population register for the basic survey (2011-2014). The sample was drawn based on age and gender.

Between 2018 and 2020 all eligible subjects (inclusion criterion: head MRI at baseline) received an invitation letter to participate in the follow-up study. After replying to this letter appointments were arranged by telephone. In addition, participants could also contact the study center by phone or e-mail to arrange an appointment for the examination. Persons who did not respond to the first letter of invitation received a second letter, followed by telephone contact attempts (a maximum of 5 call attempts).

In cases where letters were undeliverable, the residential addresses of persons were searched in the registration register, the addresses were corrected, and the persons went through the invitation process again.

In addition to the investigation programme of the LIFE follow-up, new components for HBM were added. The extensive HBM questionnaire modules had to be translated first into German. Electronic entry masks had to be created and the HBM study parts had to be integrated into the standard program. Based on the HBM specifications, a comprehensive 21-page questionnaire with the following modules was prepared and included in the LIFE programme:

- living environment and domestic exposure,
- food/beverage consumption,
- lifestyle,
- professional history,
- dental health, and
- recent exposure.

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The questionnaire was provided both on pen and paper and web-based in Lime Survey. However, the questionnaire had to be filled in the day of the examination at the study center.

Urine collection, which was not part of the LIFE follow-up, had to be established for HBM and integrated into the study process. In addition to some health data the study participants received a compensation of expenses in the amount of 15 €.

6.1.8 Sampling

As mentioned above, it was decided to process and store spot urine samples of 400 participants. This was carried out using especially pre-treated urine collection devices. Before using, the urine collection devices were rinsed with ultrapure water in a beaker for 2-3 min and dried overnight on lint-free paper towels.

The team of the LIFE-Adult Outpatient Clinic instructed the study participants how to dispense urine, and the team was responsible for appropriate labelling of the material and the transport of the urine samples to the pre-analytical laboratory. In the laboratory, three 4 mL urine aliquots per volunteer were prepared and stored for later analysis. For the storage of the urine samples at -80°C, the specially purified (decontaminated) 4 mL cryotubes provided by the IBMT were used.

5% of all samples were collected as field-blank samples for reference purposes (1-2 field-blank samples/week, depending on sample volume). The field-blank samples were prepared by using pre-treated urine collection devices, which were filled with 80 mL ultrapure water, closed, swivelled, and then left for 10 min. Afterwards the field-blank sample were treated and processed like a 'normal sample'.

6.1.9 Chemical Analysis

Since the call of the HBM4EU IC did not include the analysis of samples, the scope of this feasibility study does not include any chemical analysis of samples. Neither LIFE nor IBMT are responsible for its realisation. However, the collected spot urine samples can be provided to HBM4EU partners for analysis.

6.2 Experiences and self-assessment

6.2.1 Planning and preparation

The LIFE Adult study aims to unravel the interaction between genetic predisposition, metabolism, environment and individual lifestyle in a population-based cohort. Overall, the study protocol is very broad, and all necessary processes to conduct this pilot study were successfully implemented in the study programme. To check whether the data actually hosted in the LIFE database would fit for HBM purposes, all questionnaires, examination data and existing data of the laboratory analysis were reviewed (Table 11). Also sample acquisition, preparation, and storage processes for the retrospective part of the study were checked. Limitations in sample use were identified due to the limited sample volume of the collected samples and the sample containers used.

To fulfil the requirements of modern pollutant analysis, new sample containers were introduced, and sample volume was increased. Before use, sample containers (4 mL cryotubes) were rinsed with nitric acid, methanol, and ultra-pure water according to the respective SOP of the German Environmental Specimen Bank (ESB) to reduce production-related contaminations using an automated cleaning platform at Fraunhofer IBMT to guarantee a highly standardised cleaning process and comparability of data.

Pertaining to this HBM4EU IC, the major issue for the implementation of HBM module in an HES is the financial model. Although the day-to-day business in an HES such as contacting, recruitment etc. is comparable to the needs of an HBM study, some additional steps and processes must be

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implemented in an HES to fit the HBM purpose. Some of the questionnaires are very specific and extremely detailed, and the preparation of devices for the sample collection is very time consuming. The financing rate of only 50% is too low for the additional work and does not allow cost-covering. It is very expensive to conduct large cohort studies in which participants are followed over long periods.

Obviously, it is a good option to add HBM modules to existing cohorts, but due to the HBM4EU specific funding issue this seems to be problematic. This would lead to a lack of continuity and the overall scientific value would be low. It is advisable to select suitable cohorts that, ideally, have already undergone follow-up studies (visits), and finance them sufficiently. This would give an opportunity to monitor health and lifestyle of the study participants over many years. Follow-up studies could then be supplemented by toxicological analyses. It would also be advisable to use publicly available measurement data such as air pollution, soil analysis, or data related to industrial and agricultural contamination.

6.2.2 Fieldwork

The HBM4EU standard questionnaire must be adopted to the specific study under consideration. Some of the contents of the HBM4EU standard questionnaire are problematic because they are not relevant to the specific study or study region, e.g. pollution from certain industries. This could unnecessarily inflate the programme for the participant and should be considered when compiling the questionnaires as realised in this feasibility study. If there are too many questions which do not fit to the current study, participants might become dissatisfied and reluctant in answering them.

Points of critique regarding the HBM4EU questionnaires:

- incoherent order of the answer options (Yes/No/Don't know versus No/Don't know/Yes),
- hobbies, do it yourself (DIY) activities block contains answer options that don't fit in the block and can thus be easily misinterpreted,
- generally mixed level of detail in many question blocks,
- food question block contains confusing categories,
- example:
 - Leafy vegetables (Basil, potatoes, leafy vegetables)
 - Other vegetables (Oranges, apples, grapes)
- food question block for mercury does not distinguish between large predatory and small fish, and
- food block: mixed level of detail and overlapping categories make answering confusing.

6.2.3 Chemical Analysis

It would have been beneficial to include the opportunity to apply for the costs for the chemical analysis of samples in the HBM4EU IC1. Since this was not the case, a third partner that would have been able to conduct the chemical analysis was not included, and samples were not analysed within this feasibility study. Collected samples of the German feasibility study are now stored in the LIFE Biobank and will be provided to any HBM4EU partner that is interested in analysing the samples - considering the HBM4EU funding scheme of 50% co-fund.

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7 England - UK feasibility study

7.1 Study preparation and description of the study

7.1.1 Background

The Health Survey for England (HSfE) is an annual survey which commenced in England in 1991. It is well established as a *Gold Standard* health survey and aims to collect information about the health of the population resident in England. It is an ideal platform for the integration of a Human Biomonitoring module (HBM).

HSfE is commissioned by National Health Service (NHS) Digital and carried out by the Joint Health Surveys Unit of National Centre for Social Research (NatCen) in collaboration with the Research Department of Epidemiology and Public Health at University College London (UCL). HSfE carries out what they call a dress-rehearsal to test the process and any additional questions on an annual basis. The first stage of the survey is the interview where a detailed questionnaire is administered. The questionnaire covers issues such as demographics, health status, occupation, and lifestyle.

After the interview is completed the participant has the option of a visit from a specialist nurse to conduct measurements and collect any biological samples required. As such, HSfE is a cross-sectional survey of the population which examines associations between health status, personal characteristics, and behaviour. The results, associations, and trends are reported annually and are used by health and social care professionals to support policy development and monitoring. Due to the study design, it is not possible to make causal links as this would require further assessment.

In the first instance, integration of an HBM module into an HES will be limited to England. However, Scotland has an established HES, Scottish Health Survey (SHeS), which will be explored when expansion of the HBM programme (to include all 4 UK nations) is considered. The Scottish survey provides data extending back over 20 years and has been running to a continuous design since 2008. It collects data on health and lifestyle factors, with a particular interest in cardiovascular disease, which is a leading cause of health morbidity and mortality in Scotland. The survey is designed to provide a representative sample of adults at health board level over a 4-year period. Scotland is divided into 14 regional health boards and they aim to deliver frontline services and improve their populations' health.

The last survey set (2012-2016), targeted over 4,000 adults, with a minimum of 125 per Health Board. In 2016, a Child Boost, with a target of 1,785 children, and a Health Board Boost for several Health Boards were added. The latest SHeS includes questions on topics such as demographics and general health and undertaking biological assessments aided by the collection of saliva and urine samples to assess cotinine and sodium. The protocol for HSfE will serve as a model for integration of an HBM module within SHeS.

In Wales the analogous survey is the National Survey for Wales (NSW) which is carried out by the Office of National Statistics on behalf of the Welsh Government. The survey commenced in 2016-17 following a pilot scheme (2012-15) and replaced the Welsh Health Survey (WHS) which ran from 2003-15. It is usually a face-to-face interview with a random sample of over 10,000 adults per year, however, due to COVID-19 a streamlined version of the questionnaire has been administered by telephone in 2020.

In Northern Ireland a health survey is carried out every year by Health Survey Northern Ireland. The survey commenced in April 2010 and covers a variety of health topics relevant to the lives of the national population. Separate modules for different policy areas are included in different financial years so requesting the inclusion of an HBM module should not be challenging.

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The first step in the development of an HBM programme in the UK will involve undertaking a pilot study for the integration of the module (HBM) into HsfE and commenced in April 2021.

7.1.2 Chemical exposure and health

HBM methods enable the evaluation of exposure to chemicals and are means to understand the body burden and explore health relationships at a population level. The UK does not have an established HBM programme nor does it systematically collect robust exposure data. There are cohort and *ad hoc* programmes such as ALSPAC (<http://www.bristol.ac.uk/alspac/>) (does not address environmental chemicals) and the Cornwall Study (Middleton et al., 2016) (only assessed exposure to arsenic from drinking water) which have collected biological samples with particular topics in mind but these are not coordinated efforts and cannot therefore provide baseline data for routine use to inform national public health policy or other areas.

7.1.3 Aim and purpose of the study

HBM is an essential tool to enable the UK Government to improve public health by understanding the burden of disease and economic cost of chemicals in the environment and implement evidence-based public health policy. The Prime Minister (Boris Johnson) identified the protection and enhancement of the natural environment as a central priority for the Government as part of delivering its manifesto pledge to “to be the first generation to leave the environment in a better state than we inherited it”. The 25 Year Environmental Plan (A Green Future: Our 25 Year Plan to Improve the Environment) was published in January 2018. One of the goals in the plan is to publish an overarching Chemicals Strategy to set out the UKs approach having left the European Union (EU).

Indicators have been developed to evaluate the success of this plan and report progress to Parliament. Managing exposure to chemicals is one of the targets set. Even though it remains difficult to quantify the impacts of environmental chemicals in terms of morbidity and mortality or social costs, HBM data will provide evidence needed to monitor and evaluate the success of the UK Chemicals Strategy.

Many thousands of chemicals are approved for use in the EU and very few of these are monitored in the population. HBM evaluates exposure to chemicals and uses markers of effect to facilitate our understanding of health impacts at a population level. The proposal is to develop a sustainable HBM programme linked to HSfE. The programme of work will enable data to be collected on the levels of environmental chemicals, early adverse effects as well as geographic and socioeconomic variations. The data will enable human health risk assessment to be refined and reduce uncertainties in the assessment.

7.1.4 Target group and sample selection

HSfE collects a population representative sample of children 2-15 years and adults (16+ years as defined by HSfE). Approximately 8,000 adults and 2,000 children participate in the survey annually, and the proposal for the HBM module is to use a sub-set of 300 participants for the initial feasibility study. The survey uses a multi-stage stratified probability sampling design. The populations surveyed live in private housing; those living in institutions are not included. The sampling frame is based on Postcode Address Files (PAF). Postcode sectors containing fewer than 500 PAF are combined to create primary sampling units (PSUs). The PSUs are then stratified by region to ensure a regional balance.

The most effective and appropriate means to select the households for the HBM module will be agreed at the start of the programme. Variations due to region have been seen in past national surveys hence it will not be possible to use only one region for HBM sample population. It will more

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likely be necessary to randomly select 20 to 30 sectors. Addresses in these sectors are then systematically selected. In households having more than one adolescent in the 16-19 years age group, only one will be randomly selected, it will be necessary to select between 360 and 540 addresses in order to achieve our optimum sample size of 300 participants. The sample frame is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Sample frame for HSfE with adaptations for integrating an HBM module

In order to align with HBM4EU, the aim will be to achieve a minimum 200 but ideally 300 participants (adolescents and adults) covering two age groups. Adolescents and adults have been selected due to costs constraints and the inherent difficulties that are encountered when trying to obtain samples from children. Discussions with NatCen are exploring only administering the questionnaire to those who have agreed to provide a biological sample to ensure that the 300 participants sample size is achieved. The age groups stated below are defined by month/year at the date of receipt of the invitation as follows:

- 16-19 years (a sub-set of adolescents as defined by HBM4EU)
- 20-49 years (adults)

HSfE have validated methods which have been approved by the Research Ethics Committee (REC) and will be discussed later in this document.

7.1.5 Recruitment of study population

Those households selected for inclusion in the survey are sent a letter (a leaflet summarising general information about the survey is also included) seeking permission to be interviewed and participate. At the initial visit the interviewer administers a questionnaire (further details provided below) and seeks agreement for the second stage visit of a nurse to collect samples and take

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measurements. Before to 2018, all households included in stage 1 were offered a nurse's visit. Currently 16 of the 18 addresses are randomly selected for the stage 2. Earlier, a token of 10£ voucher used to be given to the participants, however it hasn't been determined yet whether there will be some incentives given in the stage 2.

7.1.6 Collection of information

The selected participants will complete a questionnaire to enable collection of all the necessary information concerning individual characteristics (of the participants) and on different sources and routes of exposure to some of the 1st list priority substances selected for study: Phthalates/DINCH, Bisphenols (BPA and BPS), per-/polyfluorinated compounds, and flame retardants. Metals (e.g., mercury, lead, cadmium, chromium) will also be included.

Depending on resources and national priorities, a few chemicals from the 2nd list of priority substances e.g., pesticides, may also be included. The agreed questions included in the module will be an appropriate extract from that designed within WP7 of the HBM4EU project (see Annex 2.1.1 of the D7.2 at <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/>) and merged with the questionnaire used by HSfE. Due to the length of the HSfE questionnaire it will only be possible to include a maximum of additional 10 minutes of questions for the HBM module.

Hence the more generic questions will be done during the interview and the participant will be asked to complete an online survey afterwards (taking approximately 15 minutes to complete) to ascertain occupational exposure to those substances of interest for this study. It is not expected that all participants will complete the online survey and only those who indicate that they may have occupational exposure to the selected substances will be requested to do so. The online survey will be tested on a selected number of volunteers to determine if the questions are comprehensible and complete.

The HSfE component of the questionnaire is well validated, and information is collected at both household and individual level. Some extracts of the information collated shown below demonstrates a degree of compliance with the EHES.

- Socio-demographic status
 - Home ownership, housing benefit
 - Number of cars
 - Employment
 - Education
- General information about the household including the household environment
 - House type and location
 - Heating
 - Condition of the house
- Occupation and occupational exposure
- Lifestyle questions on smoking and drinking
- General health status
 - Breathing
 - Asthma
 - Skin conditions
- Use of medications
- Dietary consumption

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The interviewer measures the participants' height and weight after administering the questionnaire.

The second stage involves the nurse's visit at which point more detailed questions about prescribed medication and health status are asked. Waist and hip measurements are taken for participants aged 11 years and older as well as blood pressure for those older than 5 years old. In the HSfE programme, non-fasting blood samples are collected from adults for analysis of total cholesterol, HDL cholesterol and glycated hemoglobin. Samples of saliva are also taken from children aged 4 years or over for analysis of cotinine. For the implementation of the HBM module, additional blood samples as well as urine specimens will be collected for analysis of the selected substances.

7.1.7 Measurement methods

All biological samples collected for the HBM module will be transported to DH-PHE laboratories where they will be stored and analysed. All analysis will be done in-house but inter-laboratory comparisons for some assays will be conducted for some substances which can be analysed in other government department laboratories e.g., Environment Agency (EA) and Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (Defra). Where possible, effort will be made to ensure the quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC) conforms to that of HBM4EU to enable comparisons to be made with some degree of confidence. However, at the time of writing the detailed of the methodologies were not fully developed.

In 2018, the Royal Victoria Infirmary (RVI), Newcastle-upon-Tyne Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust was used for the analyses of blood samples collected for HSfE. Saliva cotinine analyses was done by ABS Laboratories in Welwyn Garden City, Hertfordshire. Details of the analytical methods used for these blood and saliva samples are provided at <https://files.digital.nhs.uk/CA/2393EF/HSE18-Methods-rep.pdf>.

7.1.8 Conducting the study

All fieldwork for the programme of work will be led by the Joint Health Surveys Unit of National Centre for Social Research (NatCen). They have been commissioned by NHS Digital to lead the survey since 1991. Data analysis is undertaken in collaboration with the Research Department of Epidemiology and Public Health at University College London (UCL). This would remain unchanged and any analysis and results from the HBM module would be subject to time scales stipulated by NHS Digital before release.

7.1.9 Timing of the study

The anticipated timescales for this programme of work are shown in Table 13.

Table 13: Timescales for HBM/HSfE study - the year may change

Year		1 (21/22)		2 (22/23)		3 (23/24)		Reporting
Month		1-6	7-12	13-18	19-24	25-30	31-36	Period
Activity	Priority setting by DHSC and OGD	Cycle 1		Cycle 2*				
	Develop all material integrating with HSfE							
	Dress- rehearsal**							
	Develop and establish analytical methods							
	Complete fieldwork**							
	Analyse biological samples							
	Quality control meta data (task of HSfE)**							
	Integrate auxiliary data from questionnaires and health checks with chemical analysis into code books							
	Produce reports and integrated assessment of exposure and effect markers							
	Programme Steering Group meeting (F2F or TC)	Quarterly						
	Programme Team Management meetings	Monthly						
Milestones	Establish a cross government steering group to oversee the management and governance of the programme.							
	Launch the programme: including public engagement							
	Complete first cycle of biological sample and questionnaire data collection							
	Establishment of a biobank of samples for future research							
	Communication campaign - results disseminated to scientists, the public and policy makers							
Deliverables	Complete fieldwork manual							
	Report analytical methods							
	Policy Brief for DHSC and OGDs							
	First HBM and HSfE Report Published							
	*As preparation for further spending reviews or other sources of funding							
	** Activities carried out solely by HSfE core work							

DHSC - Department for Health and Social Care; OGD – Other Government Department; F2F – Face to face meeting; TC - Teleconference

7.1.10 Budget and funding

The fieldwork and laboratory analysis of the pilot study is been funded through the National Institute for Health Research (NIHR) – Health Protection Research Unit (HPRU) programme. Funding is currently being sought to undertake a national (England) programme of work which could eventually be extended to Wales, Scotland, and Northern Ireland to create a UK HBM database.

7.1.11 Ethics and data confidentiality

Every year since the survey commenced it is reviewed by an independent group of people (REC). The purpose of this review is to protect the safety, rights, wellbeing and dignity of those taking part in the survey. Since 2016 the survey has been reviewed by the East Midlands Nottingham 2 REC (reference no 15/EM/0254).

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Each year the survey seeks an amendment to their ethical approval which covers the selected topics for that year. For the 2021 programme which will include the HBM module ethical approval will be sought for the collection of the additional information and biological samples. Given that it is impossible to anticipate future research, ethical approval will be sought to biobank the biological samples collected for the HBM module and utilise them for such work if appropriate; that is obtain blanket approval for the use of the samples. Consent will be based on an explanation and understanding of the purpose of the study and the use and storage of their samples as well as data generated.

The answers from the questionnaires are put together anonymously and are published in a report and tables which are freely available on the NHS Digital Website. The findings do not identify anyone who took part in the survey. The Anonymisation Standard for Publishing Health and Social Care Data - is available at <https://digital.nhs.uk/data-and-information/information-standards/information-standards-and-data-collections-including-extractions/publications-and-notifications/standards-and-collections/isb1523-anonymisation-standard-for-publishing-health-and-social-care-data>. This standard was developed and tested in partnership with a range of stakeholders, including the UK Information Commissioner's Office (ICO) who is responsible for data protection issues. The HBM module would have to comply and mirror the confidentiality requirements of the HSfE.

HSfE has a validated set of communication materials. The material produced in HBM4EU has been adapted and merged with HSfE material as necessary.

7.1.12 Publication of study results

The HBM module will be subject to the timescales and protocols of the HSfE. Data cleaning, thorough QA/QC and data verification/ratification is undertaken to ensure anonymity of participants and adherence to all ethical and confidentiality agreements. Hence results from a programme of work which commences in 2021 will not be available until 2024 at the earliest.

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8 External evaluation

Due to COVID-19 pandemic, evaluation had to be organised virtually instead of evaluation visits as originally planned. Each feasibility study organiser/coordinator was asked to prepare a written material (presented as description in sections 5-7 in this report) including a general description of their study, and a description of successes and shortcomings during the preparation and fieldwork. This written material was provided for the evaluation team Stine Agergaard Holmboe (RegionH), Anna-Maria Andersson (RegionH), Madlen David (UBA) and Hanna Tolonen (THL) for their review.

A virtual Evaluation meeting took place on the 3rd of March 2021 via Teams (9:00-11:00 CET). Representatives from all three feasibility studies and the evaluation team took part in the meeting: Stine Agergaard Holmboe and Anna-Maria Andersson from Denmark, Lorraine Stewart and Ovnair Sepai from UK, Dominik Lermen, Madlen David and Ronny Baber from Germany and Hanna Tolonen, Elsi Haverinen, Hanna Elonheimo, Panu Rantakokko, Jani Koponen, Päivi Ruokojärvi and Merja Korkalainen from Finland.

The aim of the meeting was to discuss the country-specific feasibility studies; how did the studies evolve and take place, what was learned from the studies, and what could be the recommendations for the future. Finland, Germany and UK presented their studies by introducing activities, possibilities, obstacles, future steps and recommendations of each of the studies (all the presentations are found in **Appendix 3**). After presentation of each of the feasibility study, the evaluation team and representatives of the other feasibility studies had a possibility to ask clarifying questions and provide their observations and possible recommendations for the future.

Here are summarised the key points from the discussions by topic.

8.1 Ethical permissions

The Finnish feasibility study faced serious obstacles regarding the ethical permission. It took a considerable long time to obtain the permission from the ethical board (approx. 3 months), and the board denied combining of the biomonitoring study with the mandatory school health check-ups. Also, in the UK, the ethical requirements are considered strict and new HBM module needs to follow the timelines of the HSfE when applying for ethical approval. In Germany, on the other hand, the ethical permissions are most often processed quickly and smoothly.

As a conclusion, enough time should be allowed for the preparation of the materials for the review of the ethics committee and possible revisions. Ethical guidelines/practices may hinder the implementation of HBM studies.

8.2 Preparation of combined HES and HBM study

In the UK feasibility study, the Health Survey for England (HSfE) was aimed to be linked with the HBM module of Public Health England (PHE). Combining of HBM modules with representative national samples is an important aspect to consider. Strong partnership between the different actors is necessary for HBM activities to be successful. Having a partnership with established HESs can provide both benefits and challenges for data collection, timelines, and reporting.

It should be recognised that in all the feasibility studies, preparatory phase was very time consuming.

8.3 Recruitment of participants

In Finland, there were difficulties to get children to participate. This may partly be because teachers who were involved in the recruitment events were not that interested in the study itself. There were

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no incentives for participation as ethics committee did not allow providing movie tickets for those who participated. It was reported that also in the DEMOCOPHES study (<http://www.eu-hbm.info/democophes>), where recruitment was done through the schools, students and parents were not keen on participating. Similarly, in Danish alignment study, recruitment of students through schools required a lot of effort from the staff to communicate with schools and get students interested.

To enhance the recruitment of children, co-operation with parents is essential. This obviously may be age dependent as 5th and 6th graders in Finland are 10-12 years old and tend to have their own opinions, which may also affect participation in the study such as this.

It is acknowledged, that non-response questionnaires can provide important information for future activities. Furthermore, in Finland, using of SMSs as reminders to encourage participation in other health studies is a common procedure and seems to be effective. Applying of SMSs could be more extensively used but may be limited due to the availability of mobile phone numbers.

8.4 Questionnaires

In all the feasibility studies, it was realised that the HBM4EU standard questionnaire is long and rather difficult to incorporate to the ongoing HES without any modifications/shortening. In Finland, only questions which were seen relevant for the Finnish society and specifically for this study were included. In the UK/England, a maximum of 10 minutes additional questionnaire module could be included to the HSfE, while in Germany, the full questionnaire was included. Shortening the questionnaire may compromise some of the comparability between countries, however asking questions which are not reasonable, or to which participants cannot respond may increase item but also overall non-response to the total study. One alternative would be to have a short obligatory questionnaire with key questions and longer voluntary questionnaire(s) to obtain additional information. It is also important to ensure that participants understand the reasonings behind the questions posed for them.

Although standardised questionnaires exist, applying context-specific questionnaires is important, and adapting the questionnaires to specific countries and populations is crucial. It is important to provide both pen and paper and online questionnaires for different participating groups.

8.5 Participation rates

In the Finnish feasibility study, the participation rate was very low (6 %). Low participation rates constitute challenges in other countries as well, e.g. in the DEMOCOPHES-study (<http://www.eu-hbm.info/democophes>) similar low participation rates have been encountered. Sometimes small incentives have been given to children to increase the participation rates (e.g. in Germany and the UK). Denmark has some experience from the studies conducted in schools, and participation rates have been dependent on e.g. the participation of the so-called leading students. Communication is very crucial in ensuring the success of the studies and involving key communicators can be highly beneficial in increasing the participation rates. It should be carefully considered, if the use of incentives and motivating the parents could increase the participation rate in the possibly challenging age groups.

On the other hand, in Germany, combining the HBM module into the Life Adult cohort study ensured exceptionally high participation rate (91 %). The long-established cohort study enabled the HBM module to be regarded as an additional "health check-up", which might have increased the participation rate.

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8.6 COVID-19 pandemic

The COVID-19-pandemic has caused overall challenges for the feasibility studies especially in terms of timing. Obviously, there have been various confusing and surprising aspects emerging due to the pandemic, not least due to various restrictions, which have hindered conducting studies. The COVID-19 pandemic caused an overall feeling of uncertainty especially regarding the fieldwork phases in some occasions. E.g. in the Finnish feasibility study, two schools were left unvisited when the pandemic hit, and even later in the autumn these remaining schools couldn't be visited according to the original plan due to the visiting restrictions. The research material was distributed to the schools, but a substantial amount of information and motivation was left unavailable because the research team couldn't personally visit the schools and give information about the research.

8.7 General remarks

Several benefits were identified related to adding HBM module to existing HESs. Study participants will get some health-related results for themselves as an incentive. Establishing a completely new survey is a huge effort and very costly hence tapping into with an existing survey allows to use already existing infrastructure.

In most countries, HESs are conducted among adults, and only few countries have HES on children/adolescents. For any survey, obtaining long term funding is challenging.

When organising a combination of HBM and HES, it should be considered whether data is collected primarily for research or monitoring purposes. Usually, research requires longer time before well-analysed results are reported, while for monitoring, fast results are required. Depending on the country, choice of the data collection may also affect ethical approval and funding possibilities.

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9 Recommendations and lessons learnt

This chapter is based on the evaluation meeting and the country-specific reports and presentations, and it briefly summarises the recommendations and lessons learnt from all the countries involved: Finland, Germany, and the UK.

- Long processes and demands of ethical boards can cause substantial delays for the studies, let alone global pandemics such as COVID-19.
- Enough time, at least one year, should be reserved for study preparation to get everything ready before the planned starting date of the fieldwork.
- GDPR implications might hinder conducting HBM studies, especially in school environments. This became evident e.g., in the Finnish feasibility study, where the schools were unwilling to provide the list of students to the research group. Thus, information regarding study subjects can be difficult to obtain due to strict legislative rules and regulations.
- Low participation rates are a shared concern. Recruitment efforts should be adjusted for each study. Key issues are sufficient information for invitees, motivating of e.g. teachers and guardians when children are concerned, small incentives if applicable and frequent reminders via SMS etc.
- Non-response questionnaire to obtain information about profiles of the non-respondents is recommended.
- Length and contents of the questionnaires and questions should be carefully considered, as too long and complicated questionnaires might hinder response rates.
- Using the HBM4EU specific standard questionnaires can be problematic since their contents are not always relevant to specific study region, and they do not adequately target e.g., country specific exposure routes. Therefore, national adaptations may be needed.
- In the future, combining of HBM studies to existing HESs might be more feasible and cost-effective way to conduct biomonitoring studies.
- Trained and qualified staff is a basic requirement for successful HBM data collection.
- Access to stored (biobank) samples can be an advantage.
- Invasive exposure assessment methods such as blood sampling can be prohibitively expensive.
- Long-term funding, analytical capabilities and data management procedures are needed for sustainable monitoring programmes but obtaining funding can be problematic.
- Relatively short transition time between the data collection, analysis and reporting results often seen in the health monitoring and health surveys, might increase the policy value of HBM studies.

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10 Conclusions

All three feasibility studies were very different from each other which is beneficial since the aim was to pilot how HBM modules could be included to the health surveys under different settings. It was commonly agreed that combining HBM modules to HESs can provide a feasible and cost-effective method to conduct HBM studies.

Given that participation rates tend to be low, it should be recognised, that participation rates have been higher in those HBM studies which have been combined to HESs. One additional benefit is the combining of HBM data with other health data from HESs, which provides added value and diversity to data content and gathering.

Preparation of the combined HBM and health surveys is time consuming, and enough time should be reserved for this. Especially ethical questions and GDPR compliance requires a lot of preparatory work.

Currently, majority of HES and HBM modules focus on adult population. Thus far children have been less studied, and ethical rules and requirements, national regulations as well as GDPR issues are rightfully more protective and stricter regarding children. Conducting HBM studies in school-setting could be valuable in terms of gathering important exposure data of younger populations, but a lot of effort is needed from the research team to motivate and activate children to participate. Furthermore, use of incentives, which often are seen to increase participation rates, is not always allowed due to national/ethical regulations.

These feasibility studies faced an additional challenge due to the COVID-19 pandemic and related restriction measures in the countries. On the other hand, it also showed that studies are ready to adapt relatively fast for changing situations to make the best out of existing situations.

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12 Appendixes

12.1 Appendix 1. Finnish feasibility study forms

12.1.1 Data Protection Notice in Finnish and English

KOULULAISTEN BIOMONITOROINTI – KUOPIO (KOUPIO-KUOPIO)

• www.thl.fi/koubio

TIETOA TUTKIMUKSEEN OSALLISTUVALLE

TIETEELLISEN TUTKIMUKSEN TIETOSUOJAILMOITUS

EU:n yleinen tietosuoja-asetus, 12-14 artikla

Tässä selosteessa kuvataan, miten henkilötietojasi käsitellään Koululaisten Biomonitorointi – KUOPIO-tutkimuksessa (KouBio-KUOPIO). Lähtökohtaisesti tutkimukseen osallistuminen on vapaaehtoista. Sinuun ei kohdistu mitään negatiivista seuraamusta, jos et osallistu tutkimukseen tai jos keskeytät osallistumisesi tutkimukseen. Jos keskeytät osallistumisesi tutkimukseen, ennen keskeytystä kerättyä aineistoa voidaan kuitenkin käyttää tutkimuksessa. Tämän selosteen kohdassa 17 kerrotaan tarkemmin, mitä oikeuksia sinulla on ja miten voit vaikuttaa tietojesi käsittelyyn.

1. TUTKIMUKSEN REKISTERINPITÄJÄ

Terveyden ja hyvinvoinnin laitos, THL
PL 30 00271 Helsinki puh. 029 524 6000
Yhteyshenkilö tutkimusta koskevista asioista:
Nimi: Hannu Kiviranta
Osoite: Terveyden ja hyvinvoinnin laitos (THL), TETO / TEYM, PL 30, 00271 Helsinki
Puhelinnumero: 029 524 6361 Sähköpostiosoite: hannu.kiviranta@thl.fi

2. KUVAUS TUTKIMUSHANKKEESTA JA HENKILÖTIETOJEN KÄSITTELYN TARKOITUS

KouBio-KUOPIO -tutkimuksen tavoitteena on selvittää kouluikäisten lasten altistumista elinympäristössä yleisesti esiintyville kemikaaleille kuten ftalaateille ja bisfenoleille. Lisäksi

tutkimuksessa pyritään selvittämään voiko altistuminen näille kemikaaleille näkyä jollain tavalla lasten terveydessä. Tutkimus on osa laajempaa HMB4EU-hanketta.

Tutkimuksessa on välttämätöntä kerätä lasten henkilötiedot, jotta tutkittavien kemiallisten analyysien tulokset ja kyselykaavakkeiden tiedot voidaan yhdistää eri rekistereistä saataviin terveystietoihin. Henkilötietojen käsittely perustuu yleisen edun mukaiseen tieteelliseen tutkimukseen.

Tutkimuksessa lapsenne henkilöllisyys on ainoastaan tutkimushenkilökunnan tiedossa, ja he kaikki ovat salassapitovelvollisia. Tutkimuksessa käsitellään ja henkilötiedoista tallennetaan vain tutkimuksen tarkoituksen kannalta välttämättömät henkilötiedot. Lapsenne nimeä, henkilötunnusta, yhteystietoja tai mitään muutakaan henkilötietoja ei anneta tutkimuksen koordinaatioryhmän ulkopuolisille. Kaikkia lapseltanne kerättäviä tietoja ja

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otettua näytettä käsitellään koodattuina, eikä hänen tietojaan voida tunnistaa tutkimukseen liittyvistä tutkimustuloksista, selvityksistä tai julkaisuista. Koodeja, joita on käytetty lapsenne henkilötietojen salaamiseen, säilytetään erikseen tutkimusrekisteristä, ja aina tietosuojatuissa tiloissa.

3. YHTEISTYÖHANKKEENA TEHTÄVÄN TUTKIMUKSEN OSAPUOLET JA VASTUUNJAKO

THL vastaa aineiston keräämisestä ja ylläpidosta.

Tutkimuksessa kyselylomakkeella kerättyjä tietoja mm. elintavoista ja ravitsemuksesta, virtsanäytteistä analysoituja tuloksia sekä rekistereistä kerättäviä terveystietojen pohjalta muodostettavia terveyteen liittyviä muuttujia (ei yksittäisen käynnin syitä tai tietoja) voidaan käyttää biomonitorointitutkimukseen, jota THL tekee yhteistyössä eri yliopistojen ja tutkimuslaitosten kanssa Suomessa, Euroopassa ja sen ulkopuolella. Kerättyihin tietoihin voidaan antaa yhteistyötutkimuksissa käyttöoikeus yhteistyökumppaneille tai tietokantoihin (myös EU- ja ETA-alueen ulkopuolelle), mutta aina niin, ettei niistä ole ketään suoraan tunnistettavissa, ts. ilman nimiä tai muita tunnistetietoja. Tällaisesta yhteistyöstä tehdään aina etukäteen kirjallinen sopimus THL:n ja yhteistyötahon kanssa. Mikäli tietoja halutaan käyttää muuhun kuin tässä tiedotteessa kuvattuun tutkimukseen, haetaan siihen uusi eettisen toimikunnan lausunto ja viranomaisluvut sekä pyydämme teiltä tarvittaessa uuden suostumuksen.

4. TUTKIMUKSEN VASTUULLINEN JOHTAJA TAI SIITÄ VASTAAVA RYHMÄ

Nimi: Hannu Kiviranta

Osoite: Terveyden ja hyvinvoinnin laitos (THL), TETO / TEYM, PL 30, 00271 Helsinki

Puhelinnumero: 029 524 6361

Sähköpostiosoite: hannu.kiviranta@thl.fi

5. TIETOSUOJAVASTAAVAN YHTEYSTIEDOT

THL:n tietosuojavastaavan sähköpostiosoite: tietosuoja@thl.fi

6. TUTKIMUKSEN SUORITTAJAT

Terveyden ja hyvinvoinnin laitoksen KouBio-KUOPIO - tutkimuksen tutkijat ja tutkimusavustajat

7. TUTKIMUKSEN NIMI, LUONNE JA KESTOAIKA

Tutkimuksen nimi: KouBio-KUOPIO -tutkimus

* Kertatutkimus Seurantatutkimus

Tutkimuksen kesto aika (kuinka kauan henkilötietoja käsitellään):

Tutkimuksen kenttävaihe toteutetaan vuonna 2019, tutkittavilta saatua tietoa ja rekisteritietoa perustuvaa tutkimusta jatketaan ainakin HBM4EU-hankkeen keston ajan vuoteen 2021 asti.

8. HENKILÖTIETOJEN KÄSITTELYN OIKEUSPERUSTE

Henkilötietojen käsittelyn peruste on EU:n yleisen tietosuojasetuksen 6 artiklan 1 kohdan mukaisesti seuraava:

Tutkittavan suostumus

Lakisääteisen velvoitteen noudattaminen

* Yleistä etua koskeva tieteellinen tai historiallinen tutkimus, tilastointi tai rekisterinpitäjälle kuuluvan julkisen vallan käyttö (tietosuojalain 4 §:n 3 kohta)

9. ARKALUONTEISET HENKILÖTIEDOT

Tutkimuksessa ei käsitellä arkaluonteisia henkilötietoja.

Tutkimuksessa käsitellään seuraavia arkaluonteisia henkilötietoja:

Rotu tai etninen alkuperä

Poliittiset mielipiteet

Uskonnollinen tai filosofinen vakaumus

Ammattiliiton jäsenyys

Geneettiset tiedot

Biometrinen tietojen käsittely henkilön yksiselitteistä tunnistamista varten

* Terveystiedot

Luonnollisen henkilön seksuaalinen käyttäytyminen tai suuntautuminen

Arkaluonteisten tietojen käsittely perustuu seuraavaan tietosuojasetuksen 9 artiklan 2 kohdan mukaiseen erityisehtoon:

Tutkittavan nimenomainen suostumus

* Tieteellinen tai historiallinen tutkimustarkoitus tai tilastollinen tarkoitus

Tutkimus- ja kulttuuriperintöaineiston yleishyödyllinen arkistointitarkoitus

Tutkittava on saattanut käsiteltävät arkaluonteiset tiedot julkisiksi

Käsittely on tarpeen tärkeän yleisen edun vuoksi

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Käsittely on tarpeen kansanterveyteen liittyvän yleisen edun vuoksi

Käsittelystä on säädetty laissa tai johtuu välittömästi rekisterinpitäjälle säädetystä tehtävästä

Käsittelystä on säädetty laissa tai johtuu välittömästi rekisterinpitäjälle säädetystä tehtävästä

10. MITÄ HENKILÖTIETOJA TUTKIMUSAINEISTO SISÄLTÄÄ

Henkilön yksilöintitietoina kerätään nimi, henkilötunnus ja yhteystiedot. Tiedot elintavoista ja ruokavaliosta kerätään kyselylomakkeella. Eri rekisterinpitäjiltä saadaan tietoja sairauksien hoidosta, vastaanottokäynneistä ja toimenpiteistä ja tietoja resepteistä, ostetuista lääkkeistä ja muista maksutuista etuuksista ja korvauksista.

Tutkittavilta kerätään virstanäytteet, joista määritetään ftalaattien ja bisfenolien pitoisuudet.

11. MISTÄ LÄHTEISTÄ HENKILÖTIETOJA KERÄTÄÄN

Tutkittavan henkilötiedot (nimi, henkilötunnus ja yhteystiedot) saadaan vanhemmilta kysymällä.

Muita tietoja saadaan Terveiden ja hyvinvoinnin laitoksen rekistereistä (mm. tietoja sairauksien hoidosta, vastaanottokäynneistä ja toimenpiteistä), Kansaneläkelaitoksesta (mm. tietoja resepteistä, ostetuista lääkkeistä ja muista maksetuista etuuksista ja korvauksista), Tilastokeskukselta (mm. tietoja sosioekonomisesta asemasta) ja Väestörekisterikeskukselta (mm. nimi, syntymäaika ja -paikka, osoitetietoja, sukupuoli, äidinkieli, kansalaisuus).

Virtsanäytteet kerätään kotona vanhempien/huoltajien avustuksella.

12. TIETOJEN SIIRTO TAI LUOVUTTAMINEN TUTKIMUSRYHMÄN ULKOPUOLELLE

Tutkimuksessa kerättyjä tietoja ja näytteitä voidaan käyttää tutkimukseen, jota THL tekee yhteistyössä eli yliopistojen ja tutkimuslaitosten kanssa Suomessa, Euroopassa ja sen ulkopuolella. Kerättyjä tietoja voidaan luovuttaa koodattuna kansallisesti ja kansainvälisesti yhteistyökumppaneille tai tietokantoihin, myös EU- ja ETA-alueen ulkopuolelle (mm. USA:han, jossa tietosuojan taso ja suojatoimet voivat poiketa EU:n tietosuojan tasosta). Tällaisten yhteistyötahot saavat käyttöönsä tarvittavat tiedot ja näytteet ilman henkilötunnistietoja, niin ettei yksittäistä tutkittavaa voida suoraan tunnistaa.

13. TIETOJEN SIIRTO EU:N TAI EUROOPAN TALOUSALUEEN ULKOPUOLELLE

Tutkimus on osa laajempaa Eurooppalaista HBM4EU (European Human Biomonitoring Initiative, <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/>) hanketta.

Kerättyjä tietoja tullaan käyttämään tämän hankkeen puitteissa EU:ssa. Mikäli tietoja on tarve siirtää yhteistyötutkimuksen merkeissä EU/ETA-maiden ulkopuolelle, tullaan tässä noudattamaan vallitsevaa lainsäädäntöä.

Henkilötietojen siirto EU/ETA-maiden ulkopuolelle on mahdollista vain, jos tietyt tietosuoja-asetuksissa säädetty edellytykset täyttyvät. EU:n komissio voi ensinnäkin tehdä päätöksen siitä, että jokin EU:n ulkopuolinen maa tai sen alue tai tietty toimiala (esimerkiksi lääketeollisuus) täyttää saman tasoiset tietosuojavaatimukset, kuin mitä EU-mailta edellytetään. Jos komission päätöstä ei ole, saa tiedot siirtää vain, jos ulkopuolinen maa on hyväksynyt ja sitoutunut EU:n laatiin vakioehtoihin tietosuojasta ja tästä on tehty erillinen sopimus. Yhdysvaltalaiset toimijat voivat myös päästä niin sanotulle Privacy Shield-listalle, joka tarkoittaa, että heidän osaltaan on varmistettu riittävä henkilötietojen suoja. Tietojen siirto voi myös perustua tutkittavan nimenomaiseen suostumukseen.

14. AUTOMATISOITU PÄÄTÖKSENTEKO

Automaattisia päätöksiä ei tehdä.

15. HENKILÖTIETOJEN SUOJAUKSEN PERIAATTEET

Tiedot ovat salassa pidettäviä.

Manuaalisen aineiston suojaaminen: ____ Tietojärjestelmissä käsiteltävät tiedot:

käyttäjätunnus Salasana käytön rekisteröinti
 kulunvalvonta

muu, mikä: tunnistetiedot suojataan erilliskoodein analysointivaiheessa

Suorien tunnistetietojen käsittely:

Suorat tunnistetiedot poistetaan analysointivaiheessa
 Aineisto analysoidaan suoraan tunnistetiedoin, koska (peruste suorien tunnistetietojen säilyttämiselle):

16. HENKILÖTIETOJEN KÄSITTELY TUTKIMUKSEN PÄÄTTÄMISEN JÄLKEEN

Tutkimusrekisteri hävitetään

Tutkimusrekisteri arkistoidaan:

ilman tunnistetietoja tunnistetiedoin

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Mihin aineisto arkistoidaan ja miten pitkäksi aikaa:
 Terveyden ja hyvinvoinnin laitoksen arkistoon pysyvästi

17. REKISTERÖIDYN OIKEUDET JA NIIDEN MAHDOLLINEN RAJOITTAMINEN

Tietosuojalainsäädäntö takaa tutkittavalle alla mainittuja oikeuksia, joilla tutkittava voi varmistaa perusoikeuksiin kuuluvan yksityisyyden suojan toteutumisen. **Mikäli tutkittava haluaa käyttää oikeuttaan, ota yhteyttä THL:n kirjaamoon (kirjaamo@thl.fi).**

Suostumuksen peruuttaminen (tietosuoja-asetuksen 7 artikla)

Sinulla on oikeus peruuttaa antamasi suostumus, mikäli henkilötietojen käsittely perustuu suostumukseen. Suostumuksen peruuttaminen ei vaikuta suostumuksen perusteella ennen sen peruuttamista suoritetun käsittelyn lainmukaisuuteen.

Oikeus saada pääsy tietoihin (tietosuoja-asetuksen 15 artikla)

Sinulla on oikeus saada tieto siitä, käsitelläänkö henkilötietojasi tutkimuksessa ja mitä henkilötietojasi tutkimuksessa käsitellään. Voit myös halutessasi pyytää jäljennöksen käsiteltävistä henkilötiedoista. Oikeus tietojen oikaisemiseen (tietosuoja-asetuksen 16 artikla)

Jos käsiteltävissä henkilötiedoissasi on epätarkkuuksia tai virheitä, sinulla on oikeus pyytää niiden oikaisua tai täydennystä. Oikeus tietojen poistamiseen (tietosuoja-asetuksen 17 artikla)

Sinulla on oikeus vaatia henkilötietojesi poistamista seuraavissa tapauksissa:

- henkilötietoja ei enää tarvita niihin tarkoituksiin, joita varten ne kerättiin tai joita varten niitä muutoin käsiteltiin
- peruutat suostumuksen, johon käsittely on perustunut, eikä käsittelyyn ole muuta laillista perustetta
- vastustat käsittelyä eikä käsittelyyn ole olemassa perusteltua syytä
- henkilötietoja on käsitelty lainvastaisesti; tai
- henkilötiedot on poistettava unionin oikeuteen tai jäsenvaltion lainsäädäntöön perustuvan rekisterinpitäjään sovellettavan lakisääteisen veloitteen noudattamiseksi.

Oikeuksista poikkeaminen

Tässä kohdassa **17 Mitä oikeuksia sinulla on ja oikeuksista poikkeaminen** kuvatuista oikeuksista saatetaan poiketa tietosuojaa koskevan lainsäädännön mukaisilla perusteilla

siltä osin, kuin oikeudet estävät tieteellisen tai historiallisen tutkimustarkoituksen tai tilastollisen tarkoituksen saavuttamisen ai vaikeuttavat sitä suuresti. Tarvetta poiketa oikeuksista arvioidaan aina tapauskohtaisesti.

Valitusoikeus

Sinulla on oikeus tehdä valitus tietosuojaavaltuutetun toimistoon, mikäli katsot, että henkilötietojesi käsittelyssä on rikottu voimassa olevaa tietosuojalainsäädäntöä.

YHTEYSTIEDOT

Tietosuojaavaltuutetun toimisto

Käyntiosoite: Ratapihantie 9, 6. krs, 00520 Helsinki

Postiosoite: PL 800, 00521 Helsinki

Vaihde: 029 56 66700

Faksi: 029 56 66735

Sähköposti: tietosuoja@om.fi

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 **Terveyden ja
hyvinvoinnin laitos**

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BIOMONITORING OF SCHOOLCHILDREN – KUOPIO (KOUPIO-KUOPIO)

www.thl.fi/koupio

INFORMATION FOR THE RESEARCH PARTICIPANT

SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH PRIVACY STATEMENT

The general data protection regulation of the EU, articles 12-14

This statement describes how your personal information is handled by Schoolchildren Biomonitoring - in the KUOPIO research (KouBio-KUOPIO). In principle, participation in the research is voluntary. You will not be penalised in any way if you do not participate in the research or if you suspend your participation in the research. However, if you suspend your participation in the research, the material collected prior to the suspension can be used in the research. In this leaflet, the section 17 explains in more detail what rights you have and how you can influence the processing of your data.

1. THE REGISTRAR OF THE RESEARCH

Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare, THL
 PO box 30
 00271 Helsinki
 Tel. 029 524 6000

Contact person for research matters:

Name: Hannu Kiviranta
 Address: Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL), TETO / TEYM, PO box 30, 00271 Helsinki
 Tel: 029 524 6361
 Email: hannu.kiviranta@thl.fi

2. DESCRIPTION OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT AND PURPOSE OF THE PROCESSING OF PERSONAL DATA

The aim of the KouBio-KUOPIO research is to investigate the exposure of school age children to chemicals commonly found in the habitat such as phthalates and bisphenols. In addition, the research seeks to find out if the exposure to these chemicals may show up in some way in the health of children. The research is a part of a larger HMB4EU project.

In the research, it is necessary to collect children's personal information in order to be able to combine the results of the chemical analyses and the data from the questionnaires with the health data from different registers. Processing of personal data is based on scientific research according to the public interest.

In the research, the identity of your child is only known only the research staff, and they are all bound by confidentiality obligation. In the research, personal data is processed and stored only for the necessary research purposes. Name of your child, social security number, contact information, or any other personal information are not given to persons outside the coordination group of the research. All information and samples collected from your child will be processed coded, and his/her data cannot be identified from research results, studies or publications related to the research.

Codes that have been used to encrypt your child's personal information are stored separately from the research register, and always in data-protected premises.

3. COOPERATION RESEARCH PARTIES AND DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONSIBILITIES

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THL is responsible for collecting and maintaining the material.

The data collected in the research with a questionnaire regarding e.g. lifestyles and nutrition, results analysed from urine samples, and health data related variables collected from the registries (no reasons or data regarding individual visits) can be used for biomonitoring research conducted by THL in collaboration with various universities and research institutes in Finland, Europe and outside Europe. Access to the collected data can be given in collaborative studies to partners or databases (also outside the EU and the EEA), but always so, that no one is directly identifiable, i.e. without names or other identifying information. Such cooperation shall always be the subject of a prior written agreement with THL and a partner. If the data of this research is wished to be used for other research than that described in this bulletin, a new ethics committee statement and regulatory approvals will be retrieved, and we will ask you for new consent if necessary.

4. RESEARCH DIRECTOR OR RESPONSIBLE GROUP OF RESEARCH

Name: Hannu Kiviranta

Address: Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL), TETO / TEYM, PO box 30, 00271 Helsinki

Tel: 029 524 6361

Email: hannu.kiviranta@thl.fi

5. CONTACT DETAILS OF THE DATA PROTECTION OFFICER

Email-address of THL`s data protection officer: tietosuoja@thl.fi

6. EXECUTORS OF THE RESEARCH

The researchers and research assistants of the Finnish Institute of Health and Welfare from KouBio-KUOPIO research.

7. NAME, NATURE AND DURATION OF THE RESEARCH

The name of the research: KouBio-KUOPIO-research One-time examination Follow-up study

Duration of the research (for how long personal data will be processed):

The field phase of the research will be carried out in 2019, the information obtained from the research subjects and the investigation based on the register information will be continued at least for the duration of the HBM4EU project until the year 2021.

8. LEGAL BASIS FOR THE PROCESSING OF THE PERSONAL DATA

The basis for the processing of personal data is the general EU data protection regulation in accordance with Article 6 (1) as follows:

Consent of the subject

Compliance with a legal obligation

Scientific or historical research of general interest, keeping statistics or exercising public power of the

registrar of the research (Data Protection Act Section 4 (3))

9. SENSITIVE PERSONAL DATA

The research does not deal with sensitive personal data.

The research deals with the following sensitive personal data:

Race or ethnic origin

Political opinions

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Religious or philosophical belief

Trade union membership

Genetic information

Processing of biometric data for unambiguous identification of a person Health information

Sexual behavior or orientation of a natural person

The processing of sensitive data is based on the following special condition pursuant to Article 9 (2) of the regulation

Explicit consent of the subject Scientific or historical research purpose or statistical purpose

Non-profit archiving purpose for research and cultural heritage material

The subject has made the sensitive information public

Processing is necessary for the public interest

Processing is necessary for the public health interest

Processing is regulated by law or is due to immediate prescribed task to the controller

10. WHAT KIND OF PERSONAL DATA IS INCLUDED IN THE RESEARCH DATA

Name, personal identity number and contact information are collected as a person's identification information. Information on lifestyles and diet is collected through a questionnaire. Information on disease treatment, reception visits, procedures, information on prescriptions, medicines purchased, and other benefits and compensation paid is obtained from various data controllers and registers. Urine samples are collected from subjects for defining phthalates and bisphenols concentrations.

11. FROM WHICH SOURCES PERSONAL DATA IS COLLECTED FROM

The personal data of a subject (name, personal identity number and contact information) are obtained by asking from parents.

Other information is obtained from the registers of the National Institute for Health and Welfare (e.g. information on disease treatment, reception visits and procedures), from the Social Insurance Institution (e.g. information on prescriptions, purchased medicines and other benefits and allowances paid), from the Statistics Finland (e.g. information on socio-economic status) and from the Population Data Services Agency (e.g. name, date and place of birth, address details, gender, mother tongue, citizenship).

Urine samples are collected at home with the help of parents / guardians.

12. TRANSMISSION OR ADMITTING OF DATA OUTSIDE THE RESEARCH GROUP

The data and samples collected in the research can be used for the research, which THL conducts in collaboration with universities and research institutes in Finland, Europe and beyond. Coded collected data can be admitted to national and international partners or databases, including the areas outside the EU and EEA (e.g. to the US, where the level of data protection and safety procedures can deviate from the EU levels of data protection). Such collaborators will receive the necessary data and samples without personal identification data, so that the individual subject cannot be directly identified.

13. DATA TRANSMISSION OUTSIDE THE EU OR EEA

The research is a part of the wider European HBM4EU (European Human Biomonitoring Initiative, <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/>) project. The data collected will be used in the framework of this project in

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the EU. If there is a need to transmit data in the context of a collaborative research outside the EU / EEA countries, will the prevailing legislation be followed.

Transmission of personal data outside the EU / EEA countries is possible only if certain conditions laid down in the Data Protection Regulation are met. First, the EU Commission can decide that a country, region or specific branch of activity (e.g. pharmaceutical industry) outside the EU meets the same level of data protection requirements as what the EU countries are required. In the absence of a Commission decision, the data may be transmitted only if the third country has accepted and committed to the EU standard terms and conditions on data protection and a separate agreement has been reached. The US operators can also access so-called Privacy Shield list, which means that the adequate protection of personal data on their behalf is ensured. Data transmission can also be based on the express consent of the subject.

14. AUTOMATED DECISION MAKING

No automatic decisions are made.

15. PRINCIPLES FOR THE PROTECTION OF PERSONAL DATA

Information is confidential.

Protecting of manual material: _

Information processed in information systems:

username, password, use registration, access control, other, what: the identification data is

protected by separate codes during the analysis phase

Processing of direct identification data: Direct identification data is deleted during the analysis phase. The data is analysed with direct identifiers because (the basis of direct retention of identification data):

16. PROCESSING OF PERSONAL DATA AFTER THE END OF THE RESEARCH

The research register will be destroyed The research register is archived: without identification information with identification information

Where is the material archived and for how long: permanently in the archives of the Institute of Health and Welfare

17. RIGHTS OF THE REGISTERED SUBJECT AND POSSIBLE LIMITATIONS OF THE RIGHTS

Data protection law guarantees the following rights to a research subject, with which the subject can ensure personal privacy as a fundamental right. If the subject wishes to exercise his or her right, please contact THL's registry office (kirjaamo@thl.fi).

Withdrawal of consent (Article 7 of the Data Protection Regulation)

You have the right to withdraw your consent in the case if personal data processing is based on a consent. Withdrawal of consent does not affect the lawfulness of the processing based on the consent given before its withdrawal.

Right of access to information (Article 15 of the Data Protection Regulation)

You have the right to be informed whether your personal data will be processed in the research and which personal data is processed in the research. You can also, if you wish, request a copy of the personal data being processed.

Right to rectification of information (Article 16 of the Data Protection Regulation)

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If there are inaccuracies or errors in your personal data processed, you have a right to request their correction or supplementation.

Right to delete data (Article 17 of the Data Protection Regulation)

You have a right to request deletion of your personal data in the following cases:

personal data are no longer needed for the purposes for which they were collected or for which they were otherwise processed

you withdraw the consent on which the processing is based, and there is no other legal basis for processing

you oppose the processing and there is no justification for the processing

personal data have been processed unlawfully; or

personal data must be deleted in order to comply with the Union rights or with the Member State statutory law applicable to the controller.

Deviations from the rights

The rights described in this section 17 *What rights do you have and deviations from those rights* may be deviated from in relation to data protection to the extent permitted by law regarding attaining of or hindering of scientific or historical research purpose or statistical purpose. The need to deviate from the rights is always assessed on a case-by-case basis.

Right of appeal

You have a right to make a complaint at the Office of the Data Protection Officer, if you believe that existing data protection legislation has been violated in the processing of your personal data.

CONTACT INFORMATION

Office of the Data Protection Officer

Visiting address: Ratapihantie 9, 6th floor, 00520 Helsinki

Postal address: PL 800, 00521 Helsinki

Switchboard: 029 56 66700

Fax: 029 56 66735

Email: tietosuoja@om.fi

Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare

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12.1.2 Information and consent in Finnish and English

KOULULAISTEN BIOMONITOROINTI – KUOPIO (KOUPIO-KUOPIO)

www.thl.fi/koubio

TIEDOTE TUTKITTAVAN VANHEMILLE JA TUTKITTAVALLE TIETOA TUTKIMUKSESTA

Lukekaa rauhassa tämä tiedote. Jos Teillä on kysyttävää, voitte olla yhteydessä tutkijoihin, joiden yhteystiedot löytyvät asiakirjan lopusta.

Lastanne pyydetään mukaan tutkimukseen, jossa selvitetään kouluikäisten lasten altistumista muutamille sisäympäristöjen keskeisille kemikaaleille, kuten ftalaateille ja bisfenoleille. Lapsenne soveltuu mukaan tutkimukseen, koska hän kuuluu tutkimukseen valikoituun alueeseen ja ikäryhmään (Kuopion alueen koulujen 5. ja 6. luokkien 10-12-vuotiaat oppilaat). Tämä tiedote kuvaa tutkimusta ja lapsenne mahdollista osuutta siinä.

Tutkimuksella on Kuopion kaupungilta saatu lupa (2563/2019) ja Pohjois-Savon sairaanhoitopiirin tutkimuseettisen toimikunnan puoltava lausunto (887-13.02.00/2019).

TUTKIMUKSEN TAUSTA JA TARKOITUS

Ihmiset altistuvat päivittäisessä elämässään monimutkaisille kemikaalien seoksille ympäristön, kuluttajatuotteiden, elintarvikkeiden, juomaveden sekä työperäisten olosuhteiden kautta. Esimerkiksi ftalaatteja löytyy useista muovipakkauksista ja -kelmuista, puhdistusaineista, ilmanraikastimista ja hygieniatuotteista, kuten saippuoista ja shampoista. Myös monet muovina sisältävät rakennusmateriaalit sisältävät ftalaatteja. Vastaavasti bisfenolia on mm. erilaisissa muovisissa astioissa ja pakkauksissa, auton osissa sekä useissa kassakuiteissa. Epidemiologisissa tutkimuksissa altistuminen ftalaateille on yhdistetty mm. lihavuuteen, astmaan sekä eriasteisiin keskittymishäiriöihin kuten ADD ja ADHD. Bisfenolille altistuminen on yhdistetty mm. lihavuuteen sekä erilaisiin toimintakyvyn ja käytöksen kehityshäiriöihin.

Jotta pystyisimme arvioimaan, kuinka paljon ihmiset todellisuudessa altistuvat erilaisille kemikaaleille ja mitkä

niiden mahdolliset terveysvaikutukset ovat, on meidän tehtävä ns.

biomonitorointitutkimusta. Biomonitoroinnilla tarkoitetaan kemikaalien tai niiden aineenvaihduntatuotteiden mittaamista ihmisestä otettavista näytteistä, kuten virtsasta, hiuksista, syljestä tai verestä.

KouBio-KUOPIO hankkeessa selvitetään kouluikäisten lasten altistumista ftalaateille ja bisfenoleille. Tavoitteena on rekrytoida noin 300 lasta Kuopion alueen koulujen 5. ja 6. luokkalaisista oppilaista (10-12-vuotiaat). Yhteensä hankkeeseen valitaan vähintään 4-6 koulua. Hanke pyrkii myös selvittämään, heijastuvatko eri-ikäiset tai -kuntoiset kouluikäiset myös oppilaiden biomonitorointinäytteistä saataviin tuloksiin. Esimerkiksi ftalaateista osa on kielletty rakennusmateriaaleissa jo noin 10 vuotta sitten. Valitsemalla tutkimukseen oppilaita sekä vanhoista että uusista kouluista voimme suuremmissa ryhmissä onnistua näkemään eroja ftalaattien pitoisuuksissa, mikä kuvastaa kemikaalisääntelyn merkitystä arjen altistuksessa.

Oppilaisiin otetaan yhteyttä koulujen kautta yhteistyössä opettajien kanssa. Tutkittavilta kerätään tietoja mm. elintavoista ja ruokavaliosta kyselylomakkeella, jonka vanhemmat/hoitajat täyttävät. Lisäksi kerätään yksi virtsanäyte, josta määritetään ftalaatteja ja bisfenoleita. Osa näytteestä tullaan säilyttämään mahdollisia jatkoanalyysyjä varten, joille tullaan aina hakemaan erillinen eettisen toimikunnan lausunto ja muut mahdollisesti tarvittavat luvat. Kerättyihin tietoihin voidaan yhdistää tietoja eri rekisterinpitäjiltä: Terveyden

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ja hyvinvoinnin laitoksen rekistereistä (mm. tietoja sairauksista, sairauksien hoidosta, vastaanottokäynneistä ja toimenpiteistä), ja Kansaneläkelaitokselta (mm. tietoja resepteistä, ostetuista lääkkeistä ja muista maksetuista mahdollisiin sairauksiin liittyvistä

etuuksista ja korvauksista). Tietojen yhdistämistä varten haemme erilliset luvat kullakin rekisterinpitäjältä.

Hanke on osa laajempaa eurooppalaista HBM4EU (European Human Biomonitoring Initiative, <http://www.hbm4eu.eu>) hanketta, joka toteutetaan vuosina 2017-2021. HBM4EU-hanke tulee tuottamaan tietoa väestön altistumisesta kemikaaleille Euroopassa, lisäämään ymmärtämystä niihin liittyvistä terveysvaikutuksista ja parantamaan kemiallista riskinarviointia. Yksittäisten ihmisten biomonitorointitiedot voivat ohjeistaa lääketieteellistä hoitoa tai altistumisen vähentämistarvetta. Lisäksi HBM4EU-hankkeen tuloksilla parannetaan kemikaalien turvallista hallintaa, suunnitellaan toimenpiteitä haitallisen kemikaalialtistumisen vähentämiseksi ja suojellaan näin ihmisten terveyttä Euroopassa.

KouBio-KUOPIO hanketta rahoittaa Terveyden ja hyvinvoinnin laitos (THL), Sosiaali- ja terveysministeriö (STM) ja EU. Hankkeen tulokset, ilman mahdollisuutta tunnistaa yksittäistä tutkittavaa, raportoidaan STM:lle ja HBM4EU-hankkeelle. Hankkeen tuloksista tehdään koulukohtainen yhteenveto Kuopion kaupungille ja niistä käydään pitämässä lyhyt opetustilaisuus tutkimukseen osallistuneilla kouluilla.

TUTKIMUKSEN MAHDOLLISET HYÖDYT

Tutkimukseen osallistumisesta ei ole lapsellenne välitöntä hyötyä. Tutkimustulokset auttavat kuitenkin osaltaan parantamaan kemikaalien turvallista hallintaa, suunnittelemaan toimenpiteitä haitallisen kemikaalialtistumisen vähentämiseksi ja suojelemaan näin ihmisten terveyttä. Yksittäisen tutkimushenkilön tuloksia ei kuitenkaan ilmoiteta ko. henkilölle,

koska mitattaville yhdisteille ei ole vielä viitearvoja, jotka mahdollistaisivat tulosten mielekkään tulkinnan.

TUTKIMUKSESTA MAHDOLLISESTI AIHEUTUVAT HAITAT JA EPÄMUKAVUUDET JA POTILASVAKUUTUS

Tutkimuksesta ei ole haittaa tutkittaville. Virtsanäytteenotto on täysin turvallista ja se suoritetaan kotona vanhempien/huoltajien avustuksella.

Terveyden ja hyvinvoinnin laitoksella on voimassaoleva Potilasvakuutuskeskuksen kanssa solmittu potilasvakuutussopimus, joka kattaa potilasvahinkolaissa tarkemmin säädellyn perustein tutkimuksen toteuttavien henkilöiden toiminnasta tai tutkimuksessa käytettävistä laitteista potilaalle aiheutuvan henkilövahingon.

TIETOJEN LUOTTAMUKSELLISUUS JA TIETOSUOJA

Tähän tutkimukseen osallistuminen on vapaaehtoista. Tutkimuksessa on välttämätöntä kerätä lasten henkilötiedot, jotta tutkittavien kemiallisten analyysien tulokset ja kyselykaavakkeiden tiedot voidaan yhdistää eri rekistereistä saataviin terveystietoihin. Henkilötietojen käsittely perustuu yleisen edun mukaiseen tieteelliseen tutkimukseen. Pyydämme suostumuksen tutkimukseen osallistumiseksi. Voitte kieltää lapsenne osallistumisen tutkimukseen tai peruuttaa suostumuksenne syytä ilmoittamatta milloin tahansa tutkimuksen aikana. Peruuttaminen tulee tehdä kirjallisesti lähettämällä joko kirje tai sähköposti jollekin tiedotteen lopussa merkityistä vastuuhenkilöistä. Voitte myös kieltää tietojen luovuttamisen EU:n ulkopuolelle, tai peruuttaa suostumuksenne luovuttaa tietoja EU:n ulkopuolelle, syytä ilmoittamatta milloin tahansa tutkimuksen aikana. Tutkimuksessa lapsenne henkilöllisyys on ainoastaan tutkimushenkilökunnan tiedossa, ja he kaikki ovat salassapitovelvollisia. Tutkimuksessa käsitellään ja henkilötiedoista tallennetaan vain tutkimuksen tarkoituksen kannalta välttämättömät henkilötiedot. Lapsenne nimeä, henkilötunnusta, yhteystietoja tai mitään muutakaan henkilötietoa ei anneta tutkimuksen koordinaatioryhmän

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ulkopuolisille. Kaikkia lapseltanne kerättäviä tietoja ja otettua näytettä käsitellään koodattuina, eikä hänen tietojaan voida tunnistaa tutkimukseen liittyvistä tutkimustuloksista, selvityksistä tai julkaisuista. Koodeja, joita on käytetty lapsenne henkilötietojen salaamiseen, säilytetään erikseen tutkimusrekisteristä, ja aina tietosuojatuissa tiloissa.

Tutkimusrekisteristä vastaa tässä tutkimuksessa Terveyden ja hyvinvoinnin laitos (THL), PL 30, 00271 Helsinki.

THL:ssä on oma tietosuojavastaava (tietosuoja@thl.fi), joka seuraa tietosuojasääntöjen noudattamista. Lisäksi Suomessa tietosuojaan toteutumista valvoo tietosuojavaltuutettu. Tutkimuksesta on laadittu myös oheinen tietosuojailmoitus.

Tutkimuksessa kyselylomakkeella kerättyjä tietoja mm. elintavoista ja ravitsemuksesta, virtsanäytteistä analysoituja tuloksia sekä rekistereistä kerättäviä terveystietojen pohjalta muodostettavia terveyteen liittyviä muuttujia (ei yksittäisen käynnin syitä tai tietoja) voidaan käyttää biomonitorointitutkimukseen, jota THL tekee yhteistyössä eri yliopistojen ja tutkimuslaitosten kanssa Suomessa, Tämän tutkimuksen toteuttaa THL. Tutkimuksen rekisterinpitäjä on THL, joka vastaa tutkimuksen yhteydessä tapahtuvan henkilötietojen käsittelyn lainmukaisuudesta.

Jos Teillä on kysyttävää tutkimuksesta, voitte olla yhteydessä tutkijoihin tai muuhun tutkimushenkilökuntaan. Heidän kanssaan voitte keskustella kaikista tutkimuksen liittyvistä mahdollisesti mieltänne askarruttavista asioista.

Vastuullinen tutkija:

Muut tutkijat:

Hannu Kiviranta, Tutkimusprofessori

Hanna Tolonen, Tutkimuspäällikkö

**Panu Rantakokko,
Erikoistutkija**

THL

THL

THL

Neulaniementie 4, 70210 Kuopio

Mannerheimintie 166, 00300 Helsinki

Neulaniementie 4, 70210
Kuopio

Puhelin: 029 524 6361

Puhelin: 029 524 8638

Puhelin: 029 524 6395

Sähköposti: hannu.kiviranta@thl.fi

Sähköposti: hanna.tolonen@thl.fi

Sähköposti:
panu.rantakokko@thl.fi

Euroopassa ja sen ulkopuolella. Kerättyihin tietoihin voidaan antaa yhteistyötutkimuksissa käyttöoikeus yhteistyökumppaneille tai tietokantoihin (myös EU- ja ETA-alueen ulkopuolelle), mutta aina niin, ettei niistä ole ketään suoraan tunnistettavissa, ts. ilman nimiä tai muita tunnistetietoja. Tällaisesta yhteistyöstä tehdään aina etukäteen kirjallinen sopimus THL:n ja yhteistyötahon kanssa. Mikäli tietoja halutaan käyttää muuhun kuin tässä tiedotteessa kuvattuun tutkimukseen, haetaan siihen uusi eettisen toimikunnan lausunto ja viranomaisluvut sekä pyydämme teiltä tarvittaessa uuden suostumuksen. Jos päätätte, että lapsenne voi osallistua tutkimukseen, Teitä ja lastanne pyydetään allekirjoittamaan oheinen suostumuslomake kahtena (2) kappaleena, joista toinen jää Teille.

LAPSENNE TIETOJEN SÄILYTYSAIKA

Tutkimuksen tietojen ja materiaalin säilytysaika on 15 vuotta.

LISÄTIETOJA

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Tämä kappale palautetaan näytteiden kanssa

Lomaketarra

SUOSTUMUS TUTKIMUKSEEN

Lastani on pyydetty osallistumaan Koululaisten Biomonitorointi – KUOPIO tutkimukseen.

Olen perehtynyt edellä olevaan tiedotteeseen ja saanut riittävästi tietoa kyseisestä tutkimuksesta ja sen yhteydessä suoritettavasta tietojen keräämisestä, käsittelystä ja luovuttamisesta. Minulla on ollut riittävästi aikaa harkita tutkimukseen osallistumista.

Ymmärrän, että tähän tutkimukseen osallistuminen on vapaaehtoista. Minulla ja lapsellani on oikeus, milloin tahansa tutkimuksen aikana ja syytä ilmoittamatta keskeyttää tutkimukseen osallistuminen. Suostumuksen peruuttamisesta ei aiheudu minulle eikä lapselleni kielteisiä seuraamuksia, eikä se vaikuta lapseni asemaan terveydenhuollon asiakkaana. Olen tietoinen siitä, että suostumuksen peruuttamiseen mennessä kerättyjä tietoja käytetään osana tutkimusaineistoa. Olen saanut tiedon myös oikeuksistani koskien lapseni tietojen käyttöä ja tiedon siitä, kuinka voin näitä oikeuksia käyttää.

Olen ymmärtänyt, että EU/ETA-maiden ulkopuolelle voidaan luovuttaa lapseni tietojani, mutta tämä tapahtuu aina ilman henkilötunnisteita, ts. lastani ei voida suoraan tunnistaa aineistosta tai siitä julkaistavista tuloksista. Tietosuojan taso ja suojatoimenpiteet voivat poiketa tai olla huonompia Suomessa noudattavasta tietosuojan tasosta. Mikäli tietoja halutaan käyttää muuhun kuin tiedotteessa kuvattuun tutkimukseen, haetaan siihen uusi eettisen toimikunnan lausunto ja viranomaisluvut sekä pyydetään minulta uusi suostumus.

Allekirjoituksellani vahvistan, että lapseni osallistuu tässä asiakirjassa kuvattuun tutkimukseen ja hän suostuu vapaaehtoisesti tutkittavaksi.

Allekirjoitus (vanhempi/huoltaja)

Päiväys

Nimen selvennys

Henkilötunnus

Osoite

Allekirjoitus (tutkittava)

Päiväys

Nimen selvennys

Henkilötunnus

Suostun siihen, että lapseni tietoja voidaan luovuttaa EU/ETA-maiden ulkopuolelle

Allekirjoitus (vanhempi/huoltaja)

Päiväys

Nimen selvennys

Suostumus vastaanotettu (tämän täyttää tutkimushenkilökunta, saatuaan lomakkeen postitse)

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Suostumuksen vastaanottajan allekirjoitus

Päiväys

Nimen selvennys

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Tämä kappale teille itsellenne

Lomaketarra

SUOSTUMUS TUTKIMUKSEEN

Lastani on pyydetty osallistumaan Koululaisten Biomonitorointi – KUOPIO tutkimukseen.

Olen perehtynyt edellä olevaan tiedotteeseen ja saanut riittävästi tietoa kyseisestä tutkimuksesta ja sen yhteydessä suoritettavasta tietojen keräämisestä, käsittelystä ja luovuttamisesta. Minulla on ollut riittävästi aikaa harkita tutkimukseen osallistumista.

Ymmärrän, että tähän tutkimukseen osallistuminen on vapaaehtoista. Minulla ja lapsellani on oikeus, milloin tahansa tutkimuksen aikana ja syytä ilmoittamatta keskeyttää tutkimukseen osallistuminen. Suostumuksen peruuttamisesta ei aiheudu minulle eikä lapselleni kielteisiä seuraamuksia, eikä se vaikuta lapseni asemaan terveydenhuollon asiakkaana. Olen tietoinen siitä, että suostumuksen peruuttamiseen mennessä kerättyjä tietoja käytetään osana tutkimusaineistoa. Olen saanut tiedon myös oikeuksistani koskien lapseni tietojen käyttöä ja tiedon siitä, kuinka voin näitä oikeuksia käyttää.

Olen ymmärtänyt, että EU/ETA-maiden ulkopuolelle voidaan luovuttaa lapseni tietojani, mutta tämä tapahtuu aina ilman henkilötunneita, ts. lastani ei voida suoraan tunnistaa aineistosta tai siitä julkaistavista tuloksista. Tietosuojan taso ja suojaustoimenpiteet voivat poiketa tai olla huonompia Suomessa noudattavasta tietosuojan tasosta. Mikäli tietoja halutaan käyttää muuhun kuin tiedotteessa kuvattuun tutkimukseen, haetaan siihen uusi eettisen toimikunnan lausunto ja viranomaisluvat sekä pyydetään minulta uusi suostumus.

Allekirjoituksellani vahvistan, että lapseni osallistuu tässä asiakirjassa kuvattuun tutkimukseen ja hän suostuu vapaaehtoisesti tutkittavaksi.

Allekirjoitus (vanhempi/huoltaja)

Päiväys

Nimen selvennys

Henkilötunnus

Osoite

Allekirjoitus (tutkittava)

Päiväys

Nimen selvennys

Henkilötunnus

Suostun siihen, että lapseni tietoja voidaan luovuttaa EU/ETA-maiden ulkopuolelle

Allekirjoitus (vanhempi/huoltaja)

Päiväys

Nimen selvennys

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CHILDREN'S BIOMONITORING RESEARCH –KOUPIO

- www.thl.fi/koubio

INFORMATION FOR THE PARENTS AND PARTICIPATING CHILD

Information about the research

Please read this bulletin. If you have any questions, you can contact the researchers whose contact details can be found at the end of the document.

Your child will be asked to participate in a study on the exposure of school-age children to some key chemicals in the indoor environment, such as phthalates and bisphenols. Your child would be eligible for the study because he / she belongs to the selected area and age group (10-12-year-old pupils of 5th and 6th grades in Kuopio area schools). This bulletin describes the research and your child's potential contribution. The study has the permission of the City of Kuopio (2563/2019) and the assent of the North Savo Medical District Research Ethics Committee (887-13.02.00 / 2019).

Background and purpose of the study

People are exposed to complex mixtures of chemicals in their daily lives through the environment, consumer products, food, drinking water and work-related conditions. For example, phthalates can be found in many plastic wraps and films, detergents, air fresheners and toiletries such as soaps and shampoos. Many building materials containing plastic also contain phthalates. Correspondingly, bisphenol is e.g. in various plastic containers and packages, in car parts and in many cash receipts. In epidemiological studies, exposure to phthalates has been combined, e.g. obesity, asthma and various degrees of concentration disorders such as ADD and ADHD. Exposure to bisphenol has been combined e.g. obesity as well as various functional and behavioral disorders.

In order to be able to estimate how much people are actually exposed to various chemicals and what their potential health effects are, we need to do a Human Biomonitoring study. Human Biomonitoring refers to the measurement of chemicals or their metabolites in human samples, such as urine, hair, saliva or blood.

The KouBio-KUOPIO project investigates the exposure of school-age children to phthalates and bisphenols. The goal is to recruit about 300 children from the 5th and 6th grade (10-12 years) of the Kuopio area schools. A total of at least 4-6 schools will be selected for the project. The project also seeks to determine whether school properties of different ages or condition are also reflected in the results of the students' biomonitoring samples. For example, some phthalates have been banned in building materials for about 10 years. By selecting students from both old and new schools to study, we are able to see differences in phthalate levels in larger groups, reflecting the importance of chemical regulation in everyday exposure.

Pupils are contacted through schools in collaboration with teachers. Information is collected from the subjects e.g. lifestyle and diet through a questionnaire completed by parents / guardians. In addition, one urine sample is collected for phthalates and bisphenols. Part of the sample will be stored for possible further analysis, which will always be subject to a separate

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Ethics Committee opinion and other necessary permits. The data collected can be linked to different administrative registers: the registers of the National Institute for Health and Welfare (including information on illnesses, treatment, visits to the health care and procedures conducted), and the Social Insurance Institution of Finland (including information on prescriptions, medicines purchased, and other benefits and reimbursements paid). For the purpose of aggregation, we seek separate permissions from each register owner.

The project is part of a larger European HBM4EU (European Human Biomonitoring Initiative, <http://www.hbm4u.eu>) project, which will be implemented in 2017-2021. The HBM4EU project will provide information on the exposure of the population to chemicals in Europe, raise awareness of their associated health effects and improve chemical risk assessment. Individual Human Biomonitoring data can guide medical treatment or exposure reduction needs. In addition, the results of the HBM4EU project will improve the safe management of chemicals, design measures to reduce harmful chemical exposure and thus protect human health in Europe.

The KouBio-KUOPIO project is funded by the National Institute for Health and Welfare (THL), the Ministry of Social Affairs and Health (STM) and the EU. The results of the project, without being able to identify the individual subject, will be reported to the STM and the HBM4EU project. The results of the project will be summarised on a school-specific basis for the City of Kuopio and a short teaching session will be held at the participating schools.

Potential benefits of the research

There is no immediate benefit to your child from participating in the study. However, the results of the research will help to improve the safe management of chemicals, to design measures to reduce harmful chemical exposure and thus to protect human health. However, the results of an individual subject are not reported because there is no reference value for the compounds to be measured which would allow a meaningful interpretation of the results.

Possible disadvantages and inconveniences caused by the study and patient insurance

The study does not harm the subjects. Urine sampling is completely safe and is done at home with the help of parents / guardians.

The National Institute for Health and Welfare has a valid patient insurance contract with the Patient Insurance Center, which covers personal injury to the patient caused by the activities of the persons conducting the research or the equipment used in the research, on more precisely regulated grounds in the Patient Insurance Act.

Data confidentiality and privacy

Participation in this study is voluntary. It is essential for the study to collect children's personal data in order to combine the results of the chemical analyses and the questionnaires with the health records from the various registers. The processing of personal data is based on scientific research in the public interest. We ask for your consent to participate in the study. You may refuse your child's participation in the study or withdraw your consent at any time during the study without giving any reason. Cancellations must be made in writing by either sending a letter or email to one of the persons listed at the end of this notice. You may also prohibit the disclosure of information outside the EU or revoke your consent to release information outside the EU without giving any reason at any time during the investigation.

In research, the identity of your child is only known to the research staff, and they have all keeping information confidential. Only personal data necessary for the purpose of the study will

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be processed and stored in the study. Your child's name, social security number, contact information or any other personal information will not be shared with anyone outside the research coordination team. All data collected and samples taken by your child will be coded and will not be identifiable from research results, reports, or publications related to the study. The codes used to encrypt your child's personal information are stored separately from the research record, and always in privacy-protected areas.

The Research Register is maintained by the National Institute for Health and Welfare (THL), PO Box 30, 00271 Helsinki, Finland.

THL has its own Privacy Officer (Tietosuoja@thl.fi), which monitors compliance with the Privacy Policy. In addition, in Finland, the Data Protection Supervisor monitors the implementation of data protection. The study is also subject to the attached privacy statement.

The data collected through the questionnaire, e.g. results from lifestyle and nutrition, urine samples, and health-related health variables (not individual visit reasons or data) collected from registers can be used for biomonitoring research by THL in collaboration with universities and research institutes in Finland, Europe and beyond. Collected information may be accessed by partners or databases (including outside the EU and EEA) in collaborative research, but always without anyone being directly identifiable, ie without names or other identifying information. Such cooperation will always be subject to prior written agreement with THL and the entity. If the information is to be used for purposes other than those described in this bulletin, we will seek a new Ethics Committee opinion and regulatory approval, and we will ask for your new consent if necessary.

If you decide that your child may participate in the study, you and your child will be asked to sign the attached consent form in two (2) copies, one of which will remain with you.

Your child's data retention period

The data and material of the study is kept for 15 years.

The researcher

This research is being carried out by THL. The controller of the investigation is THL, which is responsible for the lawfulness of the processing of personal data in connection with the investigation.

More information

If you have any questions about the research, you can contact the researchers or other research staff. With them, you can discuss any research related issues that may be of interest to you.

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12.1.3 Invitation letter in Finnish and English

Lomakkeen ID tarra ja salasana

Kutsu lapsellenne osallistua KouBio-Kuopio tutkimukseen

Terveyden ja hyvinvoinnin laitos toteuttaa alkuvuoden 2020 aikana lapsenne koulussa tutkimushankkeen, joka on osa laajaa eurooppalaista yhteistyöhanketta (HBM4EU, <http://www.hbm4eu.eu>). Hankkeen tarkoituksena on selvittää kouluikäisten lasten altistumista kahdelle ympäristökemikaalille (ftalaatit ja bisfenolit). Vierailimme lapsenne koululla kertomassa hankkeesta ja ympäristökemikaaleista yleensä. Teille tarkempaa tietoa hankkeesta on oheisessa Tietoa tutkimuksesta –tiedotteessa.

Tutkimukseen osallistuakseen lapsenne tulisi yhdessä teidän kanssanne täyttää kyselylomake netissä osoitteessa <https://www3.thl.fi/lomake/koubio> käyttämällä tämän kirjeen oikeassa yläkulmassa olevaa käyttäjätunnusta ja salasana. Vaihtoehtoisesti voitte täyttää oheisen paperisen lomakkeen ja palauttaa sen meille. Tämän lisäksi toivoisimme lapsenne antavan virtsanäytteen ohessa olevan ohjeen mukaisesti käyttämällä kutsun mukana tulleita näytteen keräys- ja lähetysmateriaaleja.

Pidämme tärkeänä saada hankkeeseen tietoa myös suomalaisten lasten osalta ja olemme iloisia, että Kuopion kaupunki on lähtenyt mukaan tähän hankkeeseen. Osallistuminen on turvallista ja vapaaehtoista.

Toivomme, että lapsenne voisi osallistua tähän tutkimukseen. **Virtsanäytteet tulee toimittaa oheisen ohjeen mukaan postitse** (paketti jätettävä joko postin toimipisteeseen tai asiamiespostiin, ei postilaatikkoon). **Näytteiden mukaan liitetään täytettyinä oheinen suostumuslomake, virtsanäytteen ottoon liittyvä lomake (ohjeen kääntöpuolella) sekä kyselylomake, mikäli olette täyttäneet sen paperilla ettekä netissä.**

Tutkimustulokset auttavat parantamaan kemikaalien turvallista hallintaa, suunnittelemaan toimenpiteitä haitallisen kemikaalialtistumisen vähentämiseksi ja suojelemaan näin ihmisten terveyttä. Tämän vuoksi olisi ensiarvoisen tärkeää, että lapsenne pystyisi osallistumaan tutkimukseen.

Vastaamme mielellämme kaikkiin aiheeseen liittyviin kysymyksiinne. Lisää tietoa tutkimuksesta löytyy www.thl.fi/koubio.

Kiitos yhteistyöstä.

Ystävällisin terveisin,

Hannu Kiviranta
Tutkimusprofessori
Terveyden ja hyvinvoinnin laitos
puh. 029-524 6361

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Invitation to participate in KouBio-Kuopio research

The Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare is conducting a research at your child's school during the year 2020. The research is a part of the European Biomonitoring Initiative HBM4EU (<http://www.hbm4eu.eu>). The objective of the study is to examine school aged children's exposure to two common environmental chemicals (phthalates and bisphenols). We visited your child's school to present the purpose of the study and gave information about environmental chemicals in general. More information about the research is provided for you in the Information about the research –leaflet.

To participate in the study, you and your child should fill in a questionnaire online <https://www3.thl.fi/lomake/koubio> by using the username and password given in the upper right hand corner of this letter. Alternatively, you can fill in the attached paper form and return it to us. In addition, we are requesting for a urine sample, according to the instructions given. Sampling and mailing materials are provided for you child.

It is important to investigate Finnish children and their chemical exposure levels. We are pleased that the city of Kuopio has agreed to participate in this study. Participation is voluntary and has no harmful health effects on your child.

We wish that you and your child participate in this study. **Urine sample must be delivered in the package provided and according to the instructions given** (the package can be left at a postal office, not in a mailbox. Return fee is already paid). **With the samples, please return:**

consent form

information letter concerning urine sample (please fill in the back of the leaflet)

questionnaire, if not filled online

With the results from this study, more knowledge on exposure from the chemicals, safe procedures and possibilities to decrease chemical exposure can be gained. This is important in order to protect human health and minimise adverse health effects. For these reasons, it is of utmost importance that your child would participate in the research.

We are happy to response to any inquiries you might have. More information on the research can be found on www.thl.fi/koubio.

Thank you for your cooperation,

Hannu Kiviranta
Research Professor
Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare
+358 29 524 6361

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12.1.4 Questionnaire in Finnish and English

Lomaketarra

Koululaisten Biomonitorointi

KUOPIO

KouBio-KUOPIO

OHJEET VASTAAJALLE

Tämän lomakkeen voitte täyttää myös netissä osoitteessa: <https://www3.thl.fi/lomake/koubio>.
Nettilomakkeen täyttämiseksi tarvittava tutkimusnumero ja salasana ovat kutsukirjeen oikeassa yläkulmassa.

Rastittakaa kuulakärkikynällä sopiva vaihtoehto tai kirjoittakaa kysytty tieto sille varattuun tilaan.
Älkää mietellään käyttäkö lyijykynää.

Mikäli teette merkintöjä vastausruutuun, johon ette ole niitä tarkoittanut, pyydämme, että mustaatte koko ruudun.

Valitkaa kunkin kysymyksen kohdalla vain yksi, parhaiten sopiva vaihtoehto, ellei kysymyksen kohdalla erikseen mainita, että vaihtoehtoja voi valita useita.

Muistakaa vastata kaikkiin kysymyksiin. Merkitkää myös kieltävä vastaus näkyviin joko rastittamalla vaihtoehto "ei" tai merkitsemällä "0" vastaukselle varattuun tilaan.

HENKILÖTIEDOT

Lapsen nimi:

2. Lapsen sukupuoli

Poika

Tyttö

TAUSTATIETOJA

3. Lapsen syntymäaika

|__|__| kuukausi

|__|__|__|__| vuosi

4. Missä te ja lapsenne olette syntyneet? (kunta, maa)

Kunta	Maa
-------	-----

Lapsi

Äiti

Isä

Muu
huoltaja

Huoltajien tiedot, ikä

Äidin ikä |__|__|
vuotta

Isän ikä |__|__| vuotta

Muun huoltajan ikä

|__|__| vuotta

7. Huoltajan koulutustaso

	Äiti	Isä	Muu huoltaja
Ei ammattikoulutusta	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ammattikurssi tai vastaava (alle 6 kk)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ammattikurssi tai vastaava (6 kk-2 vuotta)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Alempi keskiasteen ammattitutkinto (esim. ammatti- tai kauppakoulu)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ylempi keskiasteen ammattitutkinto (esim. sairaanhoito- tai kauppaopisto, teknillinen opisto)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ammattikorkeakoulu (esim. tradenomi, insinööri)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Alempi korkea-aste (esim. hum. kand.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ylempi korkea-aste (esim. maisteri, ekonomi, diplomi-insinööri)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Tutkijakoulutus (lisensiaatti, tohtori)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

5. Kuinka kauan lapsenne on asunut?

Suomessa vuotta |__|__|

kuukautta |__|__|

6.

Nykyisessä osoitteessa vuotta |__|__|

kuukautta |__|__|

En tiedä

8. Huoltajan tiedot, työssäkäynti

	Äiti	Isä	Muu huoltaja
Kokopäivätyössä (yli 35 tuntia viikossa)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Puolipäivätyössä (15-34 tuntia viikossa)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Osa-aikatyössä (alle 15 tuntia viikossa)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Avustava perheenjäsen perheyrytyksessä	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Työtön	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Opiskelija tai koululainen	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Eläkkeellä iän tai työvuosien perusteella	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Eläkkeellä muusta syystä	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Varusmies- tai siviilipalveluksessa	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Hoitaa kotitaloutta	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Vanhempainlomalla	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Muu	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

9. Huoltajan ammattiasema

	Äiti	Isä	Muu huoltaja
Johtaja	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Erityisasiantuntija	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Asiantuntija	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Toimisto- ja asiakaspalvelutyöntekijä	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Palvelu- ja myynti- ja hoitotyöntekijä	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Maanviljelijät, metsätyöntekijä ym.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Rakennus-, korjaus- ja valmistustyöntekijä	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Prosessi- ja kuljetustyöntekijä	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Muu työntekijä	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sotilas	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Muu luokitus	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

10. Jos laskette yhteen kotitaloutenne kaikki tulos, kuinka paljon kotitaloutenne nettotulos (tulot verojen jälkeen) ovat yhteensä kuukaudessa? Jos ette tiedä tarkkaa lukua, voitte kertoa arvionne.

- Alle 500 €
- 500 – 999 €
- 1000 – 1499 €
- 1500 – 1999 €
- 2000 – 2499 €
- 2500 – 2999 €
- 3000 – 4999 €
- 5000 – 7499 €
- 7500 – 10000€
- Yli 10000€

ASUINYMPÄRISTÖ JA KOTI

12. Sijaitseeko lähelle lapsenne kotia (300 metrin sisällä) jokin seuraavista?

	Kyllä	Ei	En tiedä
Huoltoasema tai polttoaineen jakelupiste	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Turvetta, puuta tai öljyä käyttävä voimalaitos	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Autokorjaamo	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Puusepän versta	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Metallintyöstöä	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Painotalo	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Kierrätyslaitos (käsittelylaitos tms, ei kirpputoria)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Viljelysmaata	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Muita teollisuuslaitoksia	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Mitä.....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

11. Millä alueella lapsenne koti sijaitsee? Tarvittaessa voitte valita myös useamman vaihtoehdon.

- Kaupungin keskusta (ruutukaava-alue)
- Muu kaupunkialue lähellä keskustaa (esim. Niirala, Haapaniemi)
- Asuinlähiö (esim. Neulamäki, Petonen, Saaristokaupunki, Julkula)
- Maaseutu tai haja-asutusalue (ei taaja)

13. Mikä seuraavista vaihtoehdoista kuvaa parhaiten lapsenne kotia? Tarvittaessa voitte valita myös useamman vaihtoehdon.

- Omakotitalo
- Paritalo
- Rivitalo
- Kerrostalo
- Muu, mikä

- 2008 jälkeen
- En tiedä

15. Mikä on lapsenne kodin sisäpinta-ala?

- ____|____|____| m²
- En tiedä

14. Osaatko arvioida, milloin lapsenne nykyinen koti on rakennettu? Tarvittaessa voitte valita myös useamman vaihtoehdon (tehty merkittäviä lisäosia tai peruskorjauksia).

- Ennen 1950
- 1950-1965
- 1966-1981
- 1982-1997
- 1998-2008

16. Mitä lattiamateriaaleja lapsenne kodissa enimmäkseen käytetään?

- Puuparkettia tai lautta
- Laminaattia
- Muovimatto
- Keraaminen laatta
- Kokolattiamatto
- Muu, mikä

17. Onko lapsenne kodissa ollut viime aikoina jotakin seuraavista kosteuteen liittyvistä ongelmista?

	Kyllä	Ei	En tiedä
Hometta, homepilkkuja seinillä tai pinnoille, homeen hajua	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Vesivahinko (esim. rikkoutuneita tai vuotavia putkia)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Maalin kuoriutumista seiniltä tai muilta pinnoilta	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

18. Kuinka usein lapsenne koti siivotaan (esim. imurointi)?

- Useammin kuin kerran viikossa
- Kerran viikossa
- Harvemmin kuin kerran viikossa
- En tiedä

19. Oletteko käyttäneet lapsenne kodissa viimeisen 1-2 kuukauden aikana jotain alla mainituista tuotteista?

	Ei	Kyllä
Pintojen pesuaineita (esim. keittiö, kylpyhuone, lattia, ikkunat)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Lattiavahaa	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ilmanraikastin	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Tahranpoistoaineita	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pintakäsittelyaineita tai sumutteita (kenkiin, vaatteisiin, sohviin, jne.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

20. Onko lapsenne kotona lemmikkejä? Mitä ja kuinka monta?

	Ei	Kyllä	Lkm
Koira	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	____
Kissa	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	____
Hamsteri, marsu, tms.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	____
Muu, mikä _____	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	____

RUOKAILUTOTTUMUKSET

21. Kuinka usein lapsenne syö seuraavia ruokia?

21a Kalaa

	Tuskin koskaan	1-3 kertaa kuukaudessa	Kerran viikossa	Useita kertoja viikossa	Joka päivä
Kasvatettu kala (esim. kirjolohi)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Luonnon kala (esim. ahven, silakka, muikku)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Säilykekala (mm. tonnikalasäilykkeet)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Kalapakasteet (mm. kalapuikot)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Äyriäiset (esim. hummeri, ravut, katkaravut)	<input type="checkbox"/>				

21b Lihaa

	Tuskin koskaan	1-3 kertaa kuukaudessa	Kerran viikossa	Useita kertoja viikossa	Joka päivä
Vaalea liha (kana, kalkkuna)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Punainen liha (mm. sian-, naudan-, lampaanliha)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Sisäelimet (maksat, munuaiset)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Riista (mm. riistalinnut, hirvi, jänis)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Säilykeliha	<input type="checkbox"/>				

21c Maitotuotteita ja kananmunia

	Tuskin koskaan	1-3 kertaa kuukaudessa	Kerran viikossa	Useita kertoja viikossa	Joka päivä
Voi	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Maito	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Juusto	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Jogurtti	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Kananmunat	<input type="checkbox"/>				

21d Viljatuotteita

	Tuskin koskaan	1-3 kertaa kuukaudessa	Kerran viikossa	Useita kertoja viikossa	Joka päivä
Vaalea leipä	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Kokojyväleipä (esim. ruisleipä, kauraleipä)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Viljatuotteet (keksit, korput, ym.)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Ohra-, kaura- tai ruishiutaleet tai –puurot	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Mysli, murot	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Pasta, makaroni	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Riisi	<input type="checkbox"/>				

21e Rasvoja

	Tuskin koskaan	1-3 kertaa kuukaudessa	Kerran viikossa	Useita kertoja viikossa	Joka päivä
Kasvirasvat	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Voikasvisöljyseos	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Eläinperäiset rasvat (esim. voi)	<input type="checkbox"/>				

21f Kasviksia ja hedelmiä

	Tuskin koskaan	1-3 kertaa kuukaudessa	Kerran viikossa	Useita kertoja viikossa	Joka päivä
Vihannekset tuoreina	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Vihannekset valmisteina	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Hedelmät tai marjat tuoreina	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Hedelmät tai marjat valmisteina	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Hedelmä-, marja- tai vihannesmehut

21g Välipaloja, herkkuja ja pikaruokaa

	Tuskin koskaan	1-3 kertaa kuukaudessa	Kerran viikossa	Useita kertoja viikossa	Joka päivä
Suklaa	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Pähkinät ja siemenet	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Pähkinä- tai suklaalevite	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Perunalastut ja/tai popcorn	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Jäätelö	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Makeiset	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Hampurilaiset, hotdog	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Ranskalaiset	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Pizza tai kebab	<input type="checkbox"/>				

21h Muita

	Tuskin koskaan	1-3 kertaa kuukaudessa	Kerran viikossa	Useita kertoja viikossa	Joka päivä
Savustettu ruoka (savukinkku tai -lohi)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Avotulella tai muuten grillattu ruoka	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Paistettu ruoka	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Valmisateriat	<input type="checkbox"/>				

22. Kuinka usein käytätte ruuanlaitossa seuraavanlaisia materiaaleja sisältäviä astioita

	Tuskin koskaan	1-3 kertaa kuukaudessa	Kerran viikossa	Useita kertoja viikossa	Joka päivä
Terästä, keramiikkaa tai lasia	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Teflon-pintaisia paistinpannuja tai vuokia	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Muovia	<input type="checkbox"/>				

23. Jos lapsenne on syönyt pikaruokaa tai käyttänyt virvoitusjuomia viimeisen kuukauden aikana, niin kuinka ne oli pakattu?

	Ei koskaan	Joskus	Useimmiten
Pahvilaatikko	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Paperi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Muovi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Alumiini	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pahvikuppi juomille	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Muovikuppi juomille	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Alumiinitölkki juomille	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

24. Kuinka usein käytätte seuraavia astioita ruuan säilytykseen jääkaapissa tai pidempään säilytykseen pakastimessa?

	Emme käytä ollenkaan	Harvoin	Joskus	Usein
Kovamuovisia astioita	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pehmeämuovisia astioita	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Leivinpapereita	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Muovipusseja	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Keraamisia tai lasiastioita	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

25. Kuinka usein käytätte seuraavia astioita ruuan valmistamiseen tai lämmittämiseen mikroaaltouunissa?

	Emme käytä ollenkaan	Harvoin	Joskus	Usein
Kovamuovisia astioita	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pehmeämuovisia astioita	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pahvirasioita	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Keraamisia tai lasiastioita	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

26. Käyttääkö lapsenne seuraavia ravintolisiä?

	Kyllä	Ei
A-vitamiini	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B-vitamiini/B-vitamiiniseos	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
C-vitamiini	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
D-vitamiini	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
E-vitamiini	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Rauta	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Kalsium	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Muita	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

27. Kuinka usein lapsenne juo pullovetä?

- Tuskin koskaan
- Kerran viikossa
- Useita kertoja viikossa
- Päivittäin

ELINTAVAT

28. Kuinka usein lapsenne altistuu tupakan savulle?

- Ei koskaan
- Harvoin (<1/kuukausi)
- Joskus (<1/viikko)
- Kerran viikossa
- Useita kertoja viikossa
- Päivittäin

29. Kuinka paljon lapsenne liikkuu/harrastaa liikuntaa (sisältää koulumatkat, koulussa tapahtuvan liikunnan ja vapaa-ajan liikunnan)

- Hän ei liiku ollenkaan

- Kevyttä liikuntaan ainakin 10 min ajan harvemmin kuin 3 kertaa viikossa
- Reipasta liikuntaa ainakin 10 min ajan harvemmin kuin 3 kertaa viikossa
- Kevyttä tai reipasta liikuntaa ainakin 10 min ajan 3-6 kertaa viikossa
- Päivittäin reipasta yli 30 min kestäväää liikuntaa

30. Kuinka paljon aikaa keskimäärin lapsenne viettää seuraavissa paikoissa?

	Arkipäivisin	Viikonloppuna
Kotona sisätiloissa	__ __ tuntia __ __ minuuttia	__ __ tuntia __ __ minuuttia
Koulussa sisätiloissa	__ __ tuntia __ __ minuuttia	__ __ tuntia __ __ minuuttia
Muissa sisätiloissa (mm. kaupoissa, elokuvissa, sisäliikuntatiloissa jne.)	__ __ tuntia __ __ minuuttia	__ __ tuntia __ __ minuuttia
Henkilöautossa tai bussissa	__ __ tuntia __ __ minuuttia	__ __ tuntia __ __ minuuttia
Ulkona liikenteen lähellä (jalan tai pyörällä liikennöityjen alueiden vierellä)	__ __ tuntia __ __ minuuttia	__ __ tuntia __ __ minuuttia
Ulkoilualueilla (pihalla, puistossa, metsässä, urheilukentällä, jne.)	__ __ tuntia __ __ minuuttia	__ __ tuntia __ __ minuuttia

31. Onko lapsellanne harrastuksia, joissa hän on käyttänyt seuraavia aineita viimeisen kuukauden aikana?

	Kyllä	Ei
Maalit, liimat	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Liuottimet, ohenteet, puhdistuskemikaalit	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Voiteluöljyt	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Kolvaus- tai hitsaushöyryt	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Väriaineet tai musteet	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

32. Kuinka usein lapsenne on käyttänyt edellisen kuukauden aikana seuraavia tuotteita?

32.1 Hiustuotteet

	Ei koskaan	Joskus	Useita kertoja/kk	Viikoittain	Päivittäin
Hiuslakka, -spray, -geeli, -vaha tai -muotovahto	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Shampoo tai hoitoaine	<input type="checkbox"/>				

32.2 Kosmetiikka

	Ei koskaan	Joskus	Useita kertoja/kk	Viikottain	Päivittäin
Meikkivoide tai -puuteri	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Huulirasva tai -puna	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Silmämeikki (esim. luomi-, rajaus- tai ripsiväri)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Kynsilakka	<input type="checkbox"/>				

32.3 Kehonhoitoaineet

	Ei koskaan	Joskus	Useita kertoja/kk	Viikoittain	Päivittäin
Hajusteet tai hajuvedet	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Vartalo- tai käsivoide	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Deodorantti	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Muu, mikä?	<input type="checkbox"/>				

33. Kuinka paljon keskimäärin lapsenne käyttää kännykkää, tablettia tai tietokonetta päivässä?

- alle 30 min
 30 min – 2 tuntia
 2-4 tuntia
 yli 4 tuntia

TERVEYS

34. Lapsen pituus |__|__|__| cm

35. Lapsen paino |__|__| kg

36. Onko lapsellanne ollut aikaisemmin jokin seuraavista lääkärin diagnosoimista sairauksista tai tiloista? Jos kyllä, ilmoittakaa, kuinka vanha hän oli, kun tämä todettiin ensimmäisen kerran.

	Diagnosointi ikä (vuotta)
Astma	<input type="checkbox"/> Ei <input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, viimeisen 12 kk aikana __ __ vuotta <input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, yli 12 kk sitten
Allergia (nenän vuoto, silmien kirvely, iho-oireita, ruoka- yliherkkyyttä tai muuta)	<input type="checkbox"/> Ei <input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, viimeisen 12 kk aikana __ __ vuotta <input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, yli 12 kk sitten

	Diagnosointi ikä (vuotta)	
Tyypin 1 diabetes	<input type="checkbox"/> Ei	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, viimeisen 12 kk aikana	__ __ vuotta
	<input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, yli 12 kk sitten	
Kilpirauhassairaus	<input type="checkbox"/> Ei	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, viimeisen 12 kk aikana	__ __ vuotta
	<input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, yli 12 kk sitten	
Selkä- tai niskakipua	<input type="checkbox"/> Ei	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, viimeisen 12 kk aikana	__ __ vuotta
	<input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, yli 12 kk sitten	
Lasten reuma	<input type="checkbox"/> Ei	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, viimeisen 12 kk aikana	__ __ vuotta
	<input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, yli 12 kk sitten	
Kova pääsärky tai migreeni	<input type="checkbox"/> Ei	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, viimeisen 12 kk aikana	__ __ vuotta
	<input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, yli 12 kk sitten	
Virtsaamisvaikeuksia tai virtsan karkailua	<input type="checkbox"/> Ei	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, viimeisen 12 kk aikana	__ __ vuotta
	<input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, yli 12 kk sitten	
Oppimisvaikeuksia	<input type="checkbox"/> Ei	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, viimeisen 12 kk aikana	__ __ vuotta
	<input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, yli 12 kk sitten	
Ahdistuneisuutta tai masennusta	<input type="checkbox"/> Ei	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, viimeisen 12 kk aikana	__ __ vuotta
	<input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, yli 12 kk sitten	
Keskittymishäiriöitä (ADHD, ADD)	<input type="checkbox"/> Ei	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, viimeisen 12 kk aikana	__ __ vuotta
	<input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, yli 12 kk sitten	

	Diagnosointi ikä (vuotta)	
Autismi	<input type="checkbox"/> Ei	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, viimeisen 12 kk aikana	__ __ vuotta
	<input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, yli 12 kk sitten	
Aspergerin syndrooma	<input type="checkbox"/> Ei	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, viimeisen 12 kk aikana	__ __ vuotta
	<input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, yli 12 kk sitten	
Onnettomuuden aiheuttama pysyvä vamma	<input type="checkbox"/> Ei	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, viimeisen 12 kk aikana	__ __ vuotta
	<input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, yli 12 kk sitten	
Syöpä (esim. leukemia tai lymfooma)	<input type="checkbox"/> Ei	
	<input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, viimeisen 12 kk aikana	__ __ vuotta
	<input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, yli 12 kk sitten	
Muu sairaus.	<input type="checkbox"/> Ei	
Mikä:	<input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, viimeisen 12 kk aikana	__ __ vuotta
	<input type="checkbox"/> Kyllä, yli 12 kk sitten	

37. Onko lapsenne saanut seuraavia rokotteita?

	Kyllä	Ei	En tiedä
Kausi-influenssa	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Hepatiitti B	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Polio	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
MPR (tuhkarokko, sikotauti, vihurirokko)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
DTaP (kurkkumätä, jäykkäkouristus, hinkuyskä)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Vesirokko	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

38. Onko lapsenne hampaissa muovipaikkoja?

- Kyllä, kuinka monta _____
- Ei

39. Milloin viimeisin paikka on laitettu?

|__|__| vuotta |__|__| kuukautta sitten

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40. Käyttääkö lapsenne muovisia hampaiden oikomiskojeita tai –tukia?

Kyllä

Ei

KIITOS VASTAUKSISTANNE!

Biomonitoring of school children in Kuopio
(KouBio-KUOPIO)

Questionnaire

General questions

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 733032 and from the Ministry of Social Affairs and Health

PERSONAL INFORMATION

1. Name of children:

2. Sex: male female

SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION

3. What is your child's birth date? |_|_| month |_|_|_|_| year

4. Where were your child and her/his parents born? (country, city)

Child
Mother
Father
Other guardian

5. How long has your child been living in...? Please indicate the number of years (or months if less than 1 year)

In Finland	Years _ _ Months _ _
Current address	Years _ _ Months _ _

6-9. Please, give us the following information on all members of your household.

Answer options:

Education (highest level of education attained)

1. ISCED 0: no formal education or below ISCED 1, 2. ISCED 1: primary education, 3. ISCED 2: lower secondary education, or second stage of basic education, 4. ISCED 3: upper secondary education, 5. ISCED 4: post-secondary non-tertiary education, 6. ISCED 5: Short-cycle tertiary education, 7. ISCED 6: Bachelor's or equivalent level, 8. ISCED 7: Master's or equivalent level, 9. ISCED 8: Doctoral or equivalent level, 10. Don't know

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Labour status

1. Employee working full-time, 2. Employee working part-time, 3. Self-employed working full-time (including family worker), 4. Self-employed working part-time (including family worker), 5. Unemployed, 6. Pupil, student, further training, unpaid work experience, 7. In retirement or in early retirement or has given up business, 8. Permanently disabled or/and unfit to work, 9. In compulsory military community or service, 10. Fulfilling domestic tasks and care responsibilities, 11. Other inactive person, 12. Other status

Professional category

1. Manager, 2. Professional, 3. Technician or associate professional, 4. Clerical support worker, 5. Service or sales worker, 6. Skilled agricultural, forestry or fishery worker work experience, 7. Craft and related trade worker, 8. Plant or machine operator or assembler, 9. Elementary occupation, 10. Armed forces occupation, 11. Other categories

Member	Relationship (mother/ father/ other guardian)	Age	Gender	Education	Labour status	Professional category
No.1						
No.2						
No.3						

10. Could you provide the approximate range of your total household income? (It is referred to annual gross incomes from all members of your household)

less than 500 €	<input type="checkbox"/>	2500-2999 €	<input type="checkbox"/>
500-999 €	<input type="checkbox"/>	3000-4999 €	<input type="checkbox"/>
1000-1499 €	<input type="checkbox"/>	5000-7499 €	<input type="checkbox"/>
1500-1999 €	<input type="checkbox"/>	7500-10000 €	<input type="checkbox"/>
2000-2499 €	<input type="checkbox"/>	over 10 000 €	<input type="checkbox"/>

RESIDENTIAL ENVIRONMENT AND HOME EXPOSURES

11. In which area is your home located?

1. City centre	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Near city centre	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Suburb/housing estate	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Rural/Village	<input type="checkbox"/>

12. Is there any of the following facilities within 300 m of your home?

	Yes	No	Don't know
1. A petrol station	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. A power plant using coal, oil, wood etc	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. A car repair plant	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. A carpentry	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. A metalworking business	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. A printing business	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7. A recycling plant	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8. A farmland	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
9. Other industrial facilities, specify.....	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

13. Which of the following options best describes your home...?

1. Detached house	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Semi-detached house	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Terraced house	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. A flat/apartment	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Other, specify	<input type="checkbox"/>

14. Do you know approximately when your home was built (or major repairs or renovations done)?

1. Before 1950	<input type="checkbox"/>	5. 1998-2008	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. 1950-1965	<input type="checkbox"/>	6. After 2008	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. 1966-1981	<input type="checkbox"/>	7. Don't know	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. 1982-1997	<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>

15. What is the living surface (in m²) of your home?m² Don't know

16. What materials are most of the floor covering your home made of?

Wood-parquet or wooden planks	<input type="checkbox"/>
Laminate	<input type="checkbox"/>

Plastic carpet	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ceramic tiles	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fitted carpet	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other, specify	<input type="checkbox"/>

17. Do you have or have recently had any of the following problems in your home?

	Yes	No	Don't know
1. Mould or mildew on walls or other home surfaces	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Water damage (e.g. broken pipes, a leaky roof or floods)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Peeling paint on the walls or window sills	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

18. How often is general cleaning done in your home?

More than once a week <input type="checkbox"/>	Once a week <input type="checkbox"/>	Less than once a week <input type="checkbox"/>	Don't know <input type="checkbox"/>
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19. In the last two months, were any of the cleaning products listed below used in your home, at least once a week?

	No	Yes
1. Cleaning products (e.g. for kitchen, bathroom, floor, windows)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Floor wax	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Air freshener	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Spot remover products	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Impregnation fluids (e.g. for upholstery, shoes)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

20. Do you have any pets at home? If yes, specify number

1. Dog	<input type="checkbox"/> No.
2. Cat	<input type="checkbox"/> No.
3. Hamster, guinea pig	<input type="checkbox"/> No.
4. Other, specify.....	<input type="checkbox"/> No.

DIETARY HABITS

21. How often did your child consume the following food items in the last 4 weeks?

Food item	(nearly) never	1-3 per month	Once per week	Several times per week	Every day
21a. FISH					
Farmed fish (e.g. salmon)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Wild fish	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Tinned fish (e.g. tuna)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Frozen fish (e.g. fish fingers)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Crustaceans and shellfish (lobster, crayfish, scampi, crab, prawns, oysters, mussels, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
21b. MEAT					
White meat (poultry, turkey, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Red meat (pork, beef, lamb, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Offal (liver, kidney, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Game meat (bird, venison, rabbit, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Canned meat	<input type="checkbox"/>				
21c. DAIRY PRODUCTS (NOT SKIMMED) AND EGGS					
Butter	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Milk	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Cheese	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Yogurt	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Eggs	<input type="checkbox"/>				
21d. CEREALS					
White bread	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Whole grain bread	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Cereal products (crackers, rusk...)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Barley, oat and rye flakes/porridges	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Muesli, cereals	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Pasta	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Rice	<input type="checkbox"/>				
21e. FATS					

Food item	(nearly) never	1-3 per month	Once per week	Several times per week	Every day
Vegetal fats	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Butter-vegetable oil mixtures					
Animal fat, excepted butter	<input type="checkbox"/>				
21f. VEGETABLES AND FRUIT					
Raw vegetables	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Cooked vegetables	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Fresh fruits or berries	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Fruits or berries preparations	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Fruit, berry or vegetable juices	<input type="checkbox"/>				
21g. SNACKS, DELICACIES AND FAST FOOD					
Chocolate / candies	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Nuts and seeds	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Chocolate or hazelnut spread	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Potato chips / Popcorn	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Ice cream	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Confectionary	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Hamburgers, hotdogs	<input type="checkbox"/>				
French fries	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Pizza or kebab	<input type="checkbox"/>				
21h. OTHERS					
Smoked food (ham, smoked cheese, salmon)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Food grilled over an open flame/burning embers	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Fried food	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Ready-to-eat meals	<input type="checkbox"/>				

22. How often do you use following materials for cooking?

Use	(nearly) never	1-3 per month	Once per week	Several times per week	Every day
Steel, ceramic or glass	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Teflon baking tray/covered pan	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Plastic	<input type="checkbox"/>				

23. If your child has consumed Fast food during last month, how they were packed?

Type of pack	(nearly) never	Occasionally	Often
In cardboard box	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
In paper	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
In plastic (e.g. bag, box)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
In aluminium	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
In paper cup (for drinks)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
In plastic cup (for drinks)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
In aluminium containers (for drinks)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

24. How often do you use the following containers/materials for keeping your child's food in the refrigerator or for longer-time storage in the freezer?

Type of container	Not at all	Rarely	Occasionally	Often
Hard plastic containers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Soft plastic containers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Baking paper	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Plastic bags	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ceramic or glass containers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

25. How often do you use the following containers/materials for cooking or heating your child's food in the microwave oven?

Type of container	Not at all	Rarely	Occasionally	Often
Hard plastic containers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Soft plastic containers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cardboard boxes	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ceramic or glass containers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

26. Does your child consume following dietary supplements (e.g. vitamins and minerals)?

Vitamin A <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes	Vitamin E <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes
Vitamin B/ B-complex <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes	Iron <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes
Vitamin C <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes	Calcium <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes
Vitamin D <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes	Other supplements, specify..... <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes

27. How often does your child drink bottled water?

Hardly ever	Once per week	Several times per week	Every day
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

LIFESTYLE

28. How often is your child exposed to tobacco smoke?

Hardly ever/never	Seldom (<1/month)	Sometimes (<1/week)	Once a week	Several times per week	Every day
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

29. How much does your child dedicate to sport and/or physical activities (at school, after-school activities, hobbies etc.)

1. No exercise at all	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Light exercise for at least 10 min less than 3 times a week	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Brisk exercise for at least 10 minutes less than 3 times a week	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Light or brisk physical exercise for at least 10 minutes 3 to 6 times a week	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Daily brisk exercise over 30 min	<input type="checkbox"/>

30. How much time on average does your child spend in the following places?

	Workdays	Weekends
1. Inside your home	_ _ hours _ _ minutes	_ _ hours _ _ minutes
2. Inside at school	_ _ hours _ _ minutes	_ _ hours _ _ minutes
3. In other indoor spaces (e.g. shopping centre, sports club, cinema, restaurant etc.)	_ _ hours _ _ minutes	_ _ hours _ _ minutes
4. In the car or bus	_ _ hours _ _ minutes	_ _ hours _ _ minutes
6. Outdoor traffic (on foot, bicycle, motorbike, skating, at train stations or bus stops etc.)	_ _ hours _ _ minutes	_ _ hours _ _ minutes

	Workdays	Weekends
7. Outdoors, away from home (park, garden, forest, beach, outdoor sports area etc.)	_ _ hours _ _ minutes	_ _ hours _ _ minutes

31. In the last month, did your child carry out any of the following activities at home or school as DIY activities or hobbies, or was he/she direct or indirectly exposed to any of these substances at home or school? Please, consider all the activities carried out, including those conducted by your child or other family member(s).

SURFACE TREATMENT	Yes	No
Paints, adhesives	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Solvents, thinners, degreasers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Lubricating oils	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Welding fumes	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Dyes or inks	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

32. How often did your child use the following cosmetic and hygiene products in the last month?

HAIR PRODUCTS AND COSMETICS	Never	Ocasionally	Several times per month	Once per week	Every day
32.1 Hair products					
Spray, lacquer, gel/mousse, wax	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Shampoo or conditioner	<input type="checkbox"/>				
32.2 Cosmetics					
Make-up (e.g. foundation, blusher)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Lip balm or lipstick	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Eye make-up (e.g. eye shadow, eyeliner or mascara)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Nail polish or nail polish remover	<input type="checkbox"/>				
32.3 Body care products					
Perfume / eau de Cologne	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Body or hand lotion (cream, milk etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Deodorant	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Other products, specify.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				

33. How much does your child use electronic devices, such as mobile phones, computers, tablets, on average per day?

<30 min	30 min – 2 hours	2-4 hours	>4 hours
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

HEALTH

34. Child length cm and
35. weight..... kg

36. Does your child have or has your child ever had any of the following diseases or conditions, diagnosed by a medical doctor? If yes, please specify how old he/she was when this was first diagnosed

2.1 Asthma (allergic asthma included)	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Age at diagnosis ___ ___
	Yes, in the past 12 months <input type="checkbox"/>	
	Yes, more than 1 year ago <input type="checkbox"/>	
2.2 Allergy, such as rhinitis, eye inflammation, dermatitis, food allergy or other (allergic asthma excluded)	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Age at diagnosis ___ ___
	Yes, in the past 12 months <input type="checkbox"/>	
	Yes, more than 1 year ago <input type="checkbox"/>	
2.3 Diabetes (type 1)	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Age at diagnosis ___ ___
	Yes, in the past 12 months <input type="checkbox"/>	
	Yes, more than 1 year ago <input type="checkbox"/>	

36. Does your child have or has your child ever had any of the following diseases or conditions, diagnosed by a medical doctor? If yes, please specify how old he/she was when this was first diagnosed

2.4 Thyroid condition	Never <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, in the past 12 months <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, more than 1 year ago <input type="checkbox"/>	Age at diagnosis ____ ____
2.5 Back or neck pain	Never <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, in the past 12 months <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, more than 1 year ago <input type="checkbox"/>	Age at diagnosis ____ ____
2.6 Rheumatoid arthritis juvenilis (inflammation of the joints in children)	Never <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, in the past 12 months <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, more than 1 year ago <input type="checkbox"/>	Age at diagnosis ____ ____
2.7 Severe headache such as migraine	Never <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, in the past 12 months <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, more than 1 year ago <input type="checkbox"/>	Age at diagnosis ____ ____
2.8 Urinary difficulties or incontinence	Never <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, in the past 12 months <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, more than 1 year ago <input type="checkbox"/>	Age at diagnosis ____ ____
2.9 Learning disability	Never <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, in the past 12 months <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, more than 1 year ago <input type="checkbox"/>	Age at diagnosis ____ ____

36. Does your child have or has your child ever had any of the following diseases or conditions, diagnosed by a medical doctor? If yes, please specify how old he/she was when this was first diagnosed

2.10 Chronic anxiety or depression	Never <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, in the past 12 months <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, more than 1 year ago <input type="checkbox"/>	Age at diagnosis ____ ____
2.11 Attention deficit disorders (ADD, ADHD)	Never <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, in the past 12 months <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, more than 1 year ago <input type="checkbox"/>	Age at diagnosis ____ ____
2.12 Autism	Never <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, in the past 12 months <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, more than 1 year ago <input type="checkbox"/>	Age at diagnosis ____ ____
2.13 Asperger syndrome	Never <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, in the past 12 months <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, more than 1 year ago <input type="checkbox"/>	Age at diagnosis ____ ____
2.14 Permanent injury or defect caused by an accident	Never <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, in the past 12 months <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, more than 1 year ago <input type="checkbox"/>	Age at diagnosis ____ ____
2.15 Cancer (malignant tumour, also including leukaemia and lymphoma)	Never <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, in the past 12 months <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, more than 1 year ago <input type="checkbox"/>	Age at diagnosis ____ ____

36. Does your child have or has your child ever had any of the following diseases or conditions, diagnosed by a medical doctor? If yes, please specify how old he/she was when this was first diagnosed

2.16 Other diseases or conditions. specify.....	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Age at diagnosis ____
	Yes, in the past 12 months <input type="checkbox"/>	
	Yes, more than 1 year ago <input type="checkbox"/>	

37. Has your child been vaccinated for?			
Seasonal flu	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>	Don't know <input type="checkbox"/>
Hepatitis B	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>	Don't know <input type="checkbox"/>
Polio	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>	Don't know <input type="checkbox"/>
MMR (measles, mumps, rubella)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>	Don't know <input type="checkbox"/>
DTP (diphtheria, tetanus, pertussis)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>	Don't know <input type="checkbox"/>
Varicella (chicken pox)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>	Don't know <input type="checkbox"/>

38. Does your child have plastic dental fillings in his/her teeth?

Yes How many

No

39. When was the last filling put?

____ years ____ months ago

40. Does your child use plastic dental braces or orthodontic devices?

Yes

No

THANK YOU FOR YOUR ANSWERS!

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8.4.1 Urine sample instructions in Finnish and English

KOULULAISTEN BIOMONITOROINTI – KUOPIO

(KOUPIO-KUOPIO)

• www.thl.fi/koubio

OHJE JA LYHYT LOMAKE VANHEMILLE: VIRTSANÄYTE

Hyvä tutkimukseen osallistuja

Virtsasta määritetään ympäristöstä peräisin olevia kemiallisia altisteita, kuten ftalaatteja ja bisfenoleita. Määrittämisen onnistumisen kannalta olisi tärkeää, että noudatatte annettuja ohjeita. Virtsanäyte otetaan aamun ensimmäisestä pissasta. Virtsanäyteputket (50 ml näyteputki) pakastetaan näytteenoton jälkeen.

TARVIKKEET

500 ml mittakannu virtsan keräystä varten

puinen sekoitustikku

2 kpl 50 ml näyteputkia (Falcon -putki)

muovipussi ½ l ja imeytysliinoja virtsanäyteputkien säilytystä ja pakastamista varten

lyhyt lomake virtsanäytteeseen liittyviä tietoja varten (tämän ohjeen kääntöpuolella) • palautuslaatikko näytteille ja kyselylomakkeelle

NÄYTTEEN OTTAMINEN

1. Ennen näytteen ottamista, pyytäkää lastanne pesemään kädet sekä peskää myös omat kätenne. Välttäkää käsirasvan käyttöä juuri ennen näytteen ottamista.
2. Aamulla lapsen herättyä pyytäkää häntä tyhjentämään rakko pissaamalla mittakannuun.
3. Merkitkää virtsanäytteeseen liittyvään kyselylomakkeeseen (kääntöpuolella) näytteenoton päivämäärä ja kokonaisvirtsamäärä, jonka näette mitta-astiasta.
4. Sekoittakaa virtsaa puisella sekoitustikulla.
5. Avatkaa virtsanäyteputket vasta näytteenoton jälkeen ja varokaa koskettelemasta näyteputkien ja niiden korkkien sisäpintoja kontaminaation välttämiseksi.
6. Kaatakaa virtsaa kahteen näyteputkeen punaisella merkittyyn rajaan asti (50 ml virtsaa/näyteputki). Huom! Täyttäkää putkia vain punaisella merkittyyn rajaan asti, jotta ne eivät pakastuksen aikana rikkoutuisi. Jos virtsaa on vähemmän kuin 100 ml, kaatakaa virtsaa ensin toiseen 50 ml putkeen punaiseen rajaan saakka ja loppu toiseen 50 ml:n putkeen. Sulkekaa näyteputket huolellisesti korkeilla.
7. Kääriäkää näyteputki paketissa mukana olevaan vihreään imeytysliinaan ja laittakaa näyteputket huolellisesti suljetussa muovipussissa (½ l) pakastimeen (-20°C). Pakastakaa putket pystyasennossa.
8. Tyhjentäkää loppuvirtsa mittakannusta WC-pönttöön. Käytetyn mittakannun sekä puisen sekoitustikun voitte hävittää sekajätteen joukossa.
9. Säilyttäkää virtsanäytteitä pakastimessa, kunnes lähetätte ne postitse Terveiden ja hyvinvoinnin laitokselle, HUOM! Virtsanäytteet tulee lähettää jäisinä.
10. Tarkistakaa, että olette täyttäneet kääntöpuolella olevan näytteenottoon liittyvän kyselylomakkeen.

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11. Lähettäkää näytteenottoon liittyvä lomake ja jäiset näyteputket, sekä kyselylomake, mikäli ette täyttäneet sitä netissä, palautuslaatikossa (postimaksu on maksettu puolestanne) kääntöpuolella olevaan osoitteeseen. Kirjoittakaa nimenne paketin vasempaan yläkulmaan sille varattuun kohtaan. Laatikko on vietävä lähimpään postiin tai asiamiespostiin. (Löydät lähimmän palvelupisteen osoitteesta: <https://www.posti.fi/fi/palvelupisteet-kartalla>) HUOM! Älkää lähettäkö näytteitä loppuviikosta vaan mieluummin maanantaina tai tiistaina, jotta ne eivät jää viikonlopuksi Postin tiloihin seisomaan.

Lomaketarra

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VANHEMMAT TÄYTTÄVÄT:

Näytteenottopäivämäärä: _____ / _____ 2020

Kokonaisvirtsamäärä: _____ ml

Muta huomioitavaa:

PALAUTUSOSOITE (JÄISET NÄYTTEET, NÄYTTEENOTTOON LIITTYVÄ LOMAKE SEKÄ TUTKIMUKSEN KYSELYLOMAKE, MIKÄLI ETTE OLE TÄYTTÄNEET SITÄ NETISSÄ):

Terveyden ja hyvinvoinnin laitos

Sirpa Räsänen

Tunnus: 5022139

71006 VASTAUSLÄHETYS

Älkää lähettäkö näytteitä loppuviikosta vaan mieluummin maanantaina tai tiistaina, jotta ne eivät jää viikonlopuksi Postin tiloihin seisomaan.

LISÄTIETOJA

Mikäli teillä on mitä tahansa näytteenottoon liittyvää kysyttävää, ottakaa yhteyttä

Jani Koponen, tutkija

Terveyden ja hyvinvoinnin laitos (THL)

Puhelin: 029 524 6350

Sähköposti: jani.koponen@thl.fi

KIITOS YHTEISTYÖSTÄ!

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CHILDREN'S BIOMONITORING RESEARCH –KUOPIO (KOUPIO-KUOPIO)

- www.thl.fi/koupio

INSTRUCTIONS AND A SHORT QUESTIONNAIRE FOR PARENTS:

URINE SAMPLE

Urine samples can be used to examine environmental chemicals, such as phthalates and bisphenols. To succeed in the analysis, it is important that you follow the given instructions. Urine sample should be taken from the morning urination. Urine samples (50 ml sampling tubes) must be frozen after the sampling.

MATERIALS

- 500 ml canister for collection of urine
- wooden mixing stick
- two pieces of 50 ml sampling tubes (Falcon-sticks)
- plastic bag (0,5 l) and absorbent papers for packing and freezing the sample
- short questionnaire for sample information
- return box for the sample and paper questionnaire

INSTRUCTIONS FOR THE SAMPLE COLLECTION

1. Before starting the sample collection, please ask your child to wash his/her hands and also wash your own hands. Avoid using hand cream just before taking the sample.
2. Ask your child to pass his/her first morning urine to the 500 ml canister (provided).
3. Mark the date for the sample collection and the total amount of urine in the canister on the short questionnaire form.
4. Mix the urine with the wooden mixing stick (provided).
5. Open the sampling tubes (provided) only after the sample collection and avoid touching the inner surfaces of the tubes and caps in order to avoid contamination.
6. Pour the urine into the sampling tubes until you reach the red line (approximately 50 ml of urine in each stick). Note! Please, fill the tube only to the red line to avoid breaking the samples during freezing. If the total amount of urine is less than 100 ml, fill in one tube first until the red line and then fill the rest in the second tube. Close the caps carefully.
7. Wrap the samples inside the green absorbent papers (provided) and close them in a carefully sealed plastic bag (provided). Put the samples in the plastic bag into the freezer (-20 degrees). Please, freeze the samples in upright position.
8. Empty the rest of the urine from the canister into the toilet. You can dispose the plastic canister and wooden stick with normal mixed rubbish.
9. The urine samples should be stored in the freezer until you are ready to mail them to the Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare. Note! The samples must be mailed frozen.
10. Make sure that you have filled in the information on the back of the short questionnaire and have packed it with the sample.
11. Mail the frozen samples, short questionnaire and paper questionnaire, if not already filled online, in the return box (provided) to the address marked on the reverse side. The postal fees have already been paid by the Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare. Write your name and address on the left hand upper corner, on the location reserved for this information. The return box must be taken to the closest postal office (you can find the closest offices at <http://www.posti.fi/fi/palvelupisteet-kartalla>). Note! Please, do not send the return box at the end of the week, but rather on Monday or Tuesday, so that they would arrive fresh.

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PARENTS TO FILL:

Day of the sample: _____ / _____ 2020

Total amount of urine: _____ ml

Notifications:

RETURN ADDRESS (PLEASE, RETURN THE FROZEN SAMPLES, SHORT QUESTIONNAIRE & PAPER QUESTIONNAIRE, IF NOT FILLED ONLINE)

- Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare
- Sirpa Räsänen
- Code: 5022139
- 71006 RETURN MAIL

Please, send the samples on Monday or Tuesday to avoid the samples being stuck on postal offices for the weekend.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

If you have any further questions, please do not hesitate to contact

Jani Koponen, researcher
Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare
+358 29 524 6350
jani.koponen@thl.fi

THANK YOU FOR YOUR COOPERATION!

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12.2 Appendix 2. German feasibility study forms

12.2.1 Information letter in Germany

Teilnehmerinformation

Prospektive bevölkerungsbezogene Kohortenstudie für Erwachsene zur Erforschung von Zivilisationserkrankungen

1. Folgerhebung

Was ist LIFE?

LIFE ist die Abkürzung für "Leipziger Forschungszentrum für Zivilisationserkrankungen". Ziel der Studie ist es, mit modernen Untersuchungsverfahren neue Erkenntnisse über die Ursachen wichtiger Krankheiten zu gewinnen um daraus neue diagnostische und therapeutische Maßnahmen zu entwickeln. Zu diesen Erkrankungen zählen unter anderem Herz-Kreislauferkrankungen, Übergewicht, Zuckerkrankheit (Diabetes), Depression und Demenz.

Wer ist an LIFE beteiligt?

LIFE ist ein Großforschungsprojekt der Universität Leipzig und wird unter der Leitung der Medizinischen Fakultät durchgeführt. Wissenschaftlicher Leiter der Studie ist Professor Dr. med. Markus Löffler. An der Studie sind außerdem viele Kliniken und Institute der Universitätsmedizin und externe Forschungseinrichtungen beteiligt.

Welche Teile umfasst das Untersuchungsprogramm?

Folgendes Untersuchungsprogramm ist u. a. vorgesehen. Einige Untersuchungen werden ggf. nur in bestimmten Altersgruppen durchgeführt.

- Blutdruckmessungen an Hals, Armen und Beinen
- Messung von Körpergröße, Gewicht, Hüft- und Taillenumfang
- Herzstrommessung (Elektrokardiogramm, EKG)
- Ultraschalluntersuchung der Halsschlagader (Arteria Carotis) und Messung der Dicke der inneren Auskleidung (Endothel) zur Diagnostik von Arteriosklerose
- Ultraschalluntersuchung von Beinarterien
- Ultraschalluntersuchung der Leber (Leberelastographie)
- Messung der Körperzusammensetzung (Bioimpedanzanalyse)
- Messung der Körperoberfläche (Body Scan)
- Augenuntersuchung
- Riechtest
- Untersuchung der Hautalterung (Photographie) und des transdermalen Wasserverlustes
- Kernspintomographie des Gehirns und der Bauchregion (MRT)
- Hirnstrommessung (EEG)
- Tragen eines Silikonarmbandes und eines Silikomplasters zur Messung von Umweltschadstoffen
- Fragen zum Gesundheitszustand, zur Einnahme von Medikamenten und zur Lebensweise
- Fragen zu körperlichem und seelischem Wohlbefinden
- Fragen zum Schlaf
- Fragen zur Wohn- und Berufshistorie
- Fragen und Tests zu Gedächtnis, Denken und Konzentration, Verhaltensstrategien und Persönlichkeitszügen
- Fragen zu Ernährung und Genussmitteln
- Blutabnahme für labormedizinische Untersuchungen und um Aussagen zu verschiedenen Krankheiten und angeborenen Faktoren treffen zu können

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Alle Untersuchungen und Befragungen werden von qualifiziertem und besonders geschultem Personal vorgenommen.

Wie werde ich über Untersuchungsergebnisse unterrichtet?

Wenn Sie es wünschen, werden Sie über die wichtigsten Ergebnisse aus der aktuellen Untersuchung persönlich unterrichtet. Falls es sinnvoll ist, aufgrund der Untersuchungsergebnisse Ihren Hausarzt aufzusuchen, werden Sie darauf hingewiesen.

Welche Untersuchungen sollen an meinen Proben durchgeführt werden?

Alle Laboruntersuchungen (einschließlich genetischer Untersuchungen) an Ihren Proben werden nur zu Forschungszwecken durchgeführt. Studien der menschlichen Gene helfen uns, etwas über viele Krankheiten und den Gesundheitszustand zu lernen. Im Rahmen der LIFE-Studie sind Analysen Ihrer Proben für folgende Fragestellungen geplant: Rolle von Genen sowie Umwelt- und Lebensstilfaktoren, die an der Entstehung von allergologischen und immunologischen Erkrankungen, Diabetes, Übergewicht, Herz-Kreislauf-Erkrankungen, Krebs, altersbedingten, neurologischen oder psychiatrischen Erkrankungen beteiligt sind.

Es werden dabei keine Untersuchungen durchgeführt, die der Diagnostik von persönlichen angeborenen Risiken dienen. Wir werden genetische Untersuchungen nur für Forschungszwecke durchführen. Da diese nur auf Gruppenebene interpretierbar sind, ist nicht vorgesehen, diese Ergebnisse mitzuteilen.

Wie lange werden meine Proben aufgehoben?

Wir möchten Ihre Proben solange tiefgekühlt aufbewahren und für zukünftige Forschung über Gesundheit und Krankheit verwenden, bis sie aufgebraucht sind. Im Rahmen von LIFE sind auch zukünftige Analysen für weitere medizinisch bedeutsame Fragestellungen vorgesehen. Da die meisten dieser Fragestellungen sich jedoch erst aus dem Wissenstand der nächsten Jahre ergeben werden, können sie derzeit noch nicht präzise benannt werden. Es wird sich voraussichtlich um Forschungen zur Genetik sowie zu Stoffwechsel, Zell- und Organfunktionen handeln. An dieser Forschung werden ggf. weitere Forschergruppen beteiligt sein.

Wie werden meine Proben und meine Daten wissenschaftlich genutzt?

Ihre Daten und die entnommenen Proben werden ausschließlich pseudonymisiert verwendet und ausgewertet, d. h. ohne direkten Bezug zu Ihrem Namen und Ihrer Anschrift. Die pseudonymisierten Daten und Proben können kooperierenden Forschungseinrichtungen (z. B. anderen Universitäten, Forschungsinstituten und forschenden Unternehmen) auf deren Antrag für medizinische Forschungszwecke zur Verfügung gestellt werden. Daten und Proben, die an Forscher herausgegeben werden, dürfen vom Empfänger nur für den vorbestimmten, beantragten und durch eine Ethikkommission zustimmend bewerteten Forschungszweck genutzt und nicht zu anderen Zwecken weitergegeben werden.

Welche Risiken sind mit der Nutzung meiner Proben und Daten verbunden?

Bei der Erhebung von personenbezogenen Daten im Rahmen von Forschungsprojekten kann sich durch das Hinzuziehen weiterer Informationen, z. B. aus dem Internet oder sozialen Netzwerken, das Risiko einer Rückverfolgbarkeit zu Ihrer Person erhöhen. Das ist insbesondere dann der Fall, wenn Sie selbst genetische oder andere Gesundheitsdaten, z. B. zur Ahnenforschung im Internet, veröffentlichen. *Grundsätzlich erhöht ist das Risiko einer Rückverfolgbarkeit bei genetischen Patientendaten.* Die Erbinformation eines Menschen ist immer eindeutig auf eine Person bezogen, also auch auf Sie. Die Biobank der Medizinischen Fakultät der Universität Leipzig versichert Ihnen, alles nach dem Stand der Technik Mögliche

zum Schutz Ihrer Privatsphäre zu tun und Proben und Daten nur an Projekte weiterzugeben, die ein geeignetes Datenschutzkonzept vorweisen können.

Warum werden Daten von Ärzten, Melderegistern und Gesundheitsämtern angefordert?

Von Ihrem Hausarzt und anderen behandelnden Ärzten möchten wir Diagnose- und Behandlungsinformationen über bei Ihnen bereits bestehende oder während der Laufzeit der Studie neu auftretende Erkrankungen erfragen.

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Für den Todesfall bitten wir Sie um Ihre Einwilligung, z. B. das Todesdatum, den Sterbeort und die Todesursache bei den zuständigen Stellen (Melderegister, Gesundheitsamt, Ärzte) erfragen zu dürfen. Die Informationen zur Todesursache versetzen die Forscher des LIFE-Studienzentrums in die Lage, den Verlauf einer Krankheit bis zum Tode zu verfolgen. So kann untersucht werden, welche Präventionsmaßnahmen und medizinische Interventionen in der Lage sind, die krankheitsspezifische Sterblichkeit wirkungsvoll zu senken.

Wofür wird meine Krankenversicherungsnummer benötigt?

Die Daten der **gesetzlichen oder privaten Krankenversicherung** (GKV bzw. PKV) helfen uns dabei, die Befragungen und Untersuchungen für Sie nicht unnötig in die Länge zu ziehen sowie „Erinnerungslücken“ zu schließen. Außerdem können wir aufgrund der Informationen von der Krankenversicherung zielgerichtet Ihre behandelnden Ärzte kontaktieren, um genauere Informationen zu Krankheitsdiagnosen zu erhalten.

Ihre Krankenversicherung besitzt Daten zu Abrechnungszwecken, die wir für die LIFE-Adult-Studie nutzen möchten. Das heißt, Ärzte, Krankenhäuser und Apotheken melden der GKV oder PKV, welche konkreten Leistungen Sie bei Erkrankungen in Anspruch genommen haben. Die Krankenversicherung erstattet auf dieser Grundlage dann die Kosten. Im Einzelnen liegen der GKV oder PKV Daten über von Ihnen in Anspruch genommene ärztliche Leistungen in der ambulanten Versorgung (z. B. Diagnosen, erhaltene Leistungen), stationäre Aufenthalte (z. B. Haupt- und Nebendiagnosen, Aufnahme- und Entlassungsanlass, erhaltene Leistungen, Dauer der Behandlung), verordnete Heil- und Hilfsmittel (z. B. nicht-ärztliche Leistungen wie etwa Krankengymnastik, Rollstühle, Verbände), verordnete Arzneimittel (z. B. Art und Menge der Medikamente), Angaben zum Bereich Pflege (z. B. Ausmaß der Pflegebedürftigkeit, Zeitpunkte der Einstufungen) sowie bei Erwerbstätigen über Zeiten der Arbeitsunfähigkeit (z. B. Dauer, Diagnosen) vor.

Wer finanziert die Studie?

Die Studie wird finanziert aus Eigenmitteln der beteiligten Forschungseinrichtungen und aus Mitteln der Europäischen Union. Darüber hinaus möchten wir uns die Möglichkeit offen halten, andere Finanzierungsquellen staatlicher Stellen, Stiftungen, Körperschaften und der Industrie zu nutzen. Die dabei eingeworbenen Mittel kommen ausschließlich dem LIFE-Forschungsprogramm zugute.

Wie ist sichergestellt, dass die Datenschutzbestimmungen eingehalten werden?

Im Rahmen der LIFE-Studie werden personenbezogene Daten erhoben und verarbeitet. Die Verarbeitung dieser personenbezogenen Daten wird durch gesetzliche Datenschutzbestimmungen streng geregelt. Diese gesetzlichen Bestimmungen sind insbesondere die europäische Datenschutz-Grundverordnung (DSGVO), sowie die darauf aufbauenden Datenschutzgesetze des Bundes und des Freistaates Sachsen. Das Forschungsprojekt LIFE legt allergrößten Wert auf die strikte Einhaltung dieser Gesetze.

Die Daten werden pseudonymisiert gespeichert (d. h. von Namen und Adressen getrennt). Ihre Anschrift wird nur im LIFE-Studienzentrum gespeichert, um Rückfragen abzuklären, oder Sie - falls Sie es wünschen - über eventuell wichtige Untersuchungsergebnisse zu informieren oder Sie zu Folgestudien einzuladen. Die datenschutzrelevanten Vorgehensweisen wurden vom zuständigen Datenschutzbeauftragten und der Ethikkommission der Medizinischen Fakultät der Universität Leipzig geprüft.

Zweck der Datenverarbeitung

Zweck der personenbezogenen Datenverarbeitung ist die Gewinnung wissenschaftlicher Erkenntnisse über die Ursachen wichtiger Krankheiten, um daraus neue diagnostische und therapeutische Maßnahmen zu entwickeln. Zu diesen Erkrankungen zählen unter anderem Herz-Kreislauferkrankungen, Übergewicht, Zuckerkrankheit, Depression und Demenz. Ihre personenbezogenen Daten werden nur erhoben und verarbeitet, wenn sie ausdrücklich schriftlich einwilligen.

Verantwortlichkeiten:

Verantwortlich im Sinne der DSGVO für die Datenverarbeitung ist die Universität Leipzig, hier vertreten durch den Leiter der Studie:

Prof. Dr. med. Markus Löffler

Universität Leipzig, Medizinische Fakultät

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Institut für Medizinische Informatik, Statistik und Epidemiologie

Härtelstraße 16-18

04107 Leipzig

Der zuständige Datenschutzbeauftragte ist

Ronald Speer

Datenschutzbeauftragter

Medizinische Fakultät der Universität Leipzig

Philipp-Rosenthal-Str. 27

04103 Leipzig

Mail: dsbmf@medizin.uni-leipzig.de

Tel: +49 341 97-16105

Fax: +49 341 97-16729

Ihre Rechte:

Im Zusammenhang mit den datenschutzrechtlichen Aspekten der Studie haben Sie das Recht zur Beschwerde bei einer Aufsichtsbehörde. Die Kontaktdaten der für Sie zuständigen Behörde lauten:

Der Sächsische Datenschutzbeauftragte

Bernhard-von-Lindenau-Platz 1

01067 Dresden

Telefon: 0351/493-5401

Telefax: 0351/493-5490

E-Mail: saechsdsb@slt.sachsen.de

Sie haben ferner folgende Rechte hinsichtlich der Sie betreffenden personenbezogenen Daten:

- Recht auf jederzeitigen Widerruf Ihrer Einwilligung ohne Angabe von Gründen. Die Rechtmäßigkeit der Datenverarbeitung bis zu diesem Widerruf wird dadurch jedoch nicht berührt.
- Recht auf Auskunft inklusive Überlassung einer Kopie
- Recht auf die Korrektur unrichtiger Daten
- Recht auf Löschung der Daten oder Einschränkung der Verarbeitung
- Recht auf Übertragung der Daten

Entsprechende Anträge Ihrerseits sind für Sie kostenlos. Es wird jedoch darauf hingewiesen, dass bei offenkundig unbegründeten oder — insbesondere im Fall von häufiger Wiederholung — exzessiven Anträgen aufgrund der gesetzlichen Bestimmungen ein angemessenes Entgelt von Ihnen verlangt oder der Antrag verweigert werden kann. Anträge hinsichtlich der o.g. Rechte richten Sie bitte an:

Leipziger Forschungszentrum für Zivilisationserkrankungen (LIFE)

Studienzentrum LIFE-Adult

Philipp-Rosenthal-Str. 27/EG

04103 Leipzig

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Telefon: 0341 / 97-16718 und 97-16730

Fax: 0341 / 97-16719

Email: info-adult@life.uni-leipzig.de

Weitergabe von Daten:

Ihre Daten werden durch Wissenschaftler des LIFE-Zentrums und ggf. auch durch Wissenschaftler an kooperierenden Forschungseinrichtungen im In- und Ausland ausgewertet. Dies geschieht stets in pseudonymisierter Form, d.h. ohne direkten Bezug zu Ihrem Namen oder Ihrer Anschrift. Die Weitergabe an Wissenschaftler in Ländern, die nicht den strengen Vorgaben der europäischen Datenschutz-Grundverordnung unterliegen, erfolgt nur nach vorheriger eingehender Prüfung der dort geltenden Datenschutzvorschriften und sorgfältiger Abwägung von etwaigen Risiken durch die verantwortlichen Wissenschaftler des LIFE-Zentrums.

Dauer der Datenspeicherung:

Die LIFE-Studie ist ein Forschungsvorhaben, welches im Wesentlichen durch die langfristige Beobachtung und wiederholte Untersuchung und Befragung von Probanden zum wissenschaftlichen Fortschritt beiträgt. Zukünftig können sich neue wissenschaftliche Fragestellungen ergeben, die anhand der LIFE-Studiendaten untersucht werden sollen. Ihre personenbezogenen Daten müssen deshalb entsprechend langfristig gespeichert werden. Ihre personenbezogenen Daten werden jedoch spätestens 20 Jahre nach der letzten Untersuchung/Befragung anonymisiert (d. h. der Bezug zu Ihrem Namen wird endgültig und unwiderruflich gelöscht).

Überwachung der Aufklärung und Einwilligung:

Zur Überwachung des Aufklärungs- und Einwilligungsprozesses und zur Kontrolle, ob die Daten auch entsprechend ihrer Einwilligung gespeichert und verwendet werden, haben autorisierte Mitarbeiter des Zentrums für klinische Studien (ZKS Leipzig) der Universität Leipzig als unabhängige Einrichtung Zugang zu ihren Probandenunterlagen und ihren Einwilligungserklärungen. Die Einsichtnahme in die Unterlagen erfolgt ausschließlich in der LIFE Studienambulanz. Diese Mitarbeiter sind gemäß Datenschutzgesetz zur Verschwiegenheit verpflichtet.

Wie bin ich gegen etwaige Risiken versichert?

Für die studienbedingten Maßnahmen besteht keine Versicherung. Für den direkten Weg von und zum LIFE-Studienzentrum besteht eine Probanden-Wegeunfallversicherung bei folgendem Versicherungsunternehmen:

Gothaer Allgemeine Versicherung AG

Gothaer Allee 1

50969 Köln

Versicherungsnummer: aus Datenschutzgründen gelöscht

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12.2.2 Informed consent in Germany

Einwilligungserklärung

zur Teilnahme an der Studie "LIFE-Adult-F1"

1. Allgemeines

Ich bin durch eine(n) Mitarbeiter(in) des LIFE-Zentrums über Bedeutung, Ziele, Methoden und Risiken der Studie mündlich aufgeklärt worden. Ich habe eine Kopie der schriftlichen Probandeninformation erhalten und diese gelesen und verstanden. Alle meine aufgetretenen Fragen sind zu meiner Zufriedenheit beantwortet worden. Ich hatte genügend Zeit, um meine Entscheidung zu überdenken und frei zu treffen. Meine folgenden Erklärungen reichen nur so weit, wie mir dies im Rahmen der schriftlichen Probandeninformation und in der mündlichen Erläuterung näher dargelegt wurde.

2. Einwilligung in die Untersuchungen und Befragungen

Ich bin mit der Durchführung folgender Untersuchungen und Befragungen einverstanden. Mir ist bekannt, dass einzelne Untersuchungen möglicherweise nicht durchgeführt werden können, wenn bei mir bestimmte Ausschlusskriterien (z. B. bestimmte Vorerkrankungen) vorliegen. Ich bin damit einverstanden, dass im Rahmen von Machbarkeitsstudien nicht-invasive Untersuchungen auch mehrfach durchgeführt werden, um Aufschlüsse über die Messgenauigkeit einzelner Verfahren zu gewinnen (von den Mehrfach-Durchführungen ist ausgenommen: Blutentnahme).

Ja		Untersuchung
<input type="checkbox"/>		Blutabnahme (bis zu 120 ml) und Laboruntersuchung (einschließlich genetischer Untersuchungen)
<input type="checkbox"/>		Urinprobe
<input type="checkbox"/>		Anthropometrie (Größe, Gewicht, Hüft- und Taillenumfang)
<input type="checkbox"/>		Augenuntersuchung (Visustest, Netzhautfotografie und optische Kohärenztomographie, Biometrie)
<input type="checkbox"/>		Blutdruckmessung (Arm, Hals und Bein/Fuß)
<input type="checkbox"/>		Elektroenzephalographie (EEG)
Ja		Untersuchung
<input type="checkbox"/>		Kernspintomographie des Kopfes
<input type="checkbox"/>		Körperoberflächenmessung (Body-Scan)
<input type="checkbox"/>		Leberelastographie
<input type="checkbox"/>		Messung der Hautalterung und des transdermalen Wasserverlustes
<input type="checkbox"/>		Messung der Körperzusammensetzung (Bioelektrische Impedanz Analyse)
<input type="checkbox"/>		Riechtest

<input type="checkbox"/>		Ruhe-EKG
<input type="checkbox"/>		Langzeit-EKG
<input type="checkbox"/>		Tragen von Silikonarmband, Silikonpflaster und Mitnahme der Fenster-Silikonfolie zum Zwecke der Umweltanalytik
<input type="checkbox"/>		Ultraschalluntersuchung der Beinarterien (A. femoralis comm., A. femoralis superf., A. pop)
<input type="checkbox"/>		Ultraschalluntersuchung der Halsschlagader (Carotissonographie)
<input type="checkbox"/>		Fragen und Interviews zu: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • eigenen Vorerkrankungen und Erkrankungen in der Familie • Einnahme von Medikamenten • Nahrungs- und Genussmitteln • Körperlicher Aktivität • Allergien • Inanspruchnahme von Gesundheitsleistungen, Erwerbsunfähigkeit und Renten • Lebensqualität, sozialen Kontakten und Lebensweise • Fragen zu körperlichem und seelischem Wohlbefinden sowie Fragen und Tests zu Gedächtnis, Denken, Konzentration, Verhaltensstrategien und Persönlichkeitszüge • Schlaf • Wohn- und Berufshistorie

Raum zur Angabe von eventuellen Einschränkungen:

3. Mitteilung von Untersuchungsergebnissen

Mir ist bewusst, dass manche Untersuchungen Abweichungen vom Normalbefund zeigen können, die medizinisch jedoch nicht relevant sind. Bei einigen Veränderungen empfiehlt sich eine weitere Abklärung durch den Hausarzt.

Es ist mir bewusst, dass es sich bei den mitgeteilten Untersuchungsergebnissen nicht um ärztliche Befunde handelt und dass LIFE keine Diagnosen stellt oder Therapieempfehlungen ausspricht. Dies ist Aufgabe meines behandelnden Arztes.

Mir ist bewusst, dass die Kenntnisaufnahme von Untersuchungsergebnissen unter Umständen von persönlicher Bedeutung sein könnte, zum Beispiel im Zusammenhang mit dem Abschluss einer Kranken- oder Lebensversicherung.

Mir ist bewusst, dass es vorkommen kann, dass Wissenschaftler bei der Analyse z. B. meiner Bioproben oder gespeicherten Bilddaten Veränderungen entdecken, die Hinweise auf eine schwere Gefährdung meiner Gesundheit oder der Gesundheit meiner Nachkommen liefern können. Dies wird meist erst viele

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Jahre nach meiner Untersuchung der Fall sein. Aus diesem Grund werde ich über solche Ergebnisse **nicht** persönlich informiert.

Ich wünsche eine Information über die wichtigsten Untersuchungsergebnisse aus den in Abschnitt 2 eingewilligten Untersuchungen, insbesondere über solche, die einer weiteren Abklärung bedürfen.

ja nein

Falls "ja" angekreuzt wurde: Ich erhalte die wichtigsten Ergebnisse der Untersuchung nach Abschluss des Besuchsprogramms. Nur sofern sich darüber hinaus Anhaltspunkte für eine schwerwiegende oder lebensbedrohliche Erkrankung ergeben, wird mir diese umgehend nach der Untersuchung mitgeteilt.

Falls "nein" angekreuzt wurde: In diesem Fall erhalte ich grundsätzlich keine Untersuchungsergebnisse. Mir ist jedoch bewusst, dass bestimmte Ergebnisse der Untersuchung mein Recht auf Selbstbestimmung sowie den Schutz meiner persönlichen Daten berühren können, z. B. wenn hierdurch eine akute Gefährdung für mich oder für Dritte resultieren könnte. In diesem Fall werde ich dennoch über die Ergebnisse aufgeklärt und es werden ggf. medizinische Notfallmaßnahmen eingeleitet.

4. Einwilligung in die Lagerung und Analyse von Bioproben

Ich bin mit der Einlagerung der unter Punkt 2 angekreuzten Bioproben in die Biobank der Medizinischen Fakultät der Universität Leipzig einverstanden. Ich übereignen die mir entnommenen Bioproben an das LIFE-Zentrum der Universität Leipzig. Dabei bin ich mir bewusst, dass dies meine nachfolgend abgegebenen Erklärungen hinsichtlich meiner Persönlichkeitsrechte nicht einschränkt.

Ich stimme zu, dass meine Bioproben unter der Verantwortung des LIFE-Zentrums in der Biobank der Medizinischen Fakultät der Universität Leipzig gelagert werden und diese Proben 20 Jahre nach der letzten Untersuchung anonymisiert werden.

Ich stimme zu, dass meine Bioproben und Untersuchungsergebnisse zur Erforschung von lebensstil- und umweltassoziierten Krankheiten, sowie zur Entwicklung neuer Diagnostika und Therapien dienen.

Ich bin damit einverstanden, dass mir - falls von mir gewünscht - nur solche Untersuchungsergebnisse mitgeteilt werden, die im Rahmen der Vor-Ort-Untersuchung bestimmt wurden, aber dass ich keine Informationen über später durchgeführte Untersuchungen oder Auswertungen erhalte.

Ich bin mir bewusst und damit einverstanden, dass ich für die Überlassung meiner Bioproben kein Entgelt erhalte.

ja nein

5. Anforderung von Daten von Ärzten

Ich stimme zu, dass befugte Studienmitarbeiter unter Wahrung des Datenschutzes studienrelevante diagnostische und therapeutische Informationen und Befunde bei meinen behandelnden Ärzten einholen dürfen. Diesbezüglich entbinde ich die mich behandelnden Ärzte gegenüber dem LIFE Studienzentrum von der Schweigepflicht hinsichtlich studienrelevanter Erkrankungen.

ja nein

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6. Anforderung von Daten von Ärzten, Melderegister und Gesundheitsämtern im Todesfall

Ich stimme zu, dass befugte Studienmitarbeiter unter Wahrung des Datenschutzes im Falle meines Todes Informationen zu dessen Ursachen und Umständen von Ärzten, Angehörigen und Melderegistern sowie Gesundheitsämtern einholen dürfen. Die Ärzte und anderen Personen/Einrichtungen entbinde ich hiermit gegenüber dem LIFE Studienzentrums insofern von ihren Verschwiegenheitspflichten. Diese Daten können auch von Mortalitätsregistern angefordert werden.

ja nein

7. Anforderung von Gesundheitsdaten bei der gesetzlichen oder privaten Krankenversicherung

Hiermit ermächtige ich meine Krankenversicherung unter Wahrung des Datenschutzes Daten über von mir in Anspruch genommene ärztliche Leistungen in der ambulanten Versorgung und stationären Aufenthalten sowie über Diagnosen, über Zeiten der Arbeitsunfähigkeit, über verordnete Heil- und Hilfsmittel, verordnete Arzneimittel und Angaben zum Bereich Pflege an des LIFE Studienzentrums zu übermitteln.

Das LIFE Studienzentrums fordert die Gesundheitsdaten mit Ihrer Krankenversicherungsnummer sowie weiteren personenidentifizierenden Daten (Name, Geburtsdatum) an. Die Krankenversicherung stellt Ihre Gesundheitsdaten zusammen, verwirft die personenidentifizierenden Daten und übermittelt nur die pseudonymisierten Gesundheitsdaten ans LIFE Studienzentrums. Diese Ermächtigung gilt für den Zeitraum meiner Studienteilnahme.

Ich willige ein, dass der Name meiner gesetzlichen oder privaten Krankenversicherung und meine Krankenversicherungsnummer erhoben, gespeichert und genutzt werden. Diese Angaben werden ausschließlich dafür verwendet, die oben aufgeführten Gesundheitsdaten anzufordern.

ja nein

8. Epidemiologische und klinische Krebsregister

Hiermit ermächtige ich die zuständigen Krebsregister auf Anforderung durch das LIFE Studienzentrums Daten zu allen registrierten Tumorerkrankungen mit detaillierter Diagnose, Tumorstadium, Lokalisation, Therapiemethoden, -verlauf und -abschluss an das LIFE Studienzentrums zu übermitteln

Das LIFE Studienzentrums fordert die Gesundheitsdaten mit personenidentifizierenden Daten (Name, Geburtsdatum, ggf. Adresse) an. Die Krebsregister stellen Ihre Daten zusammen, verwerfen die personenidentifizierenden Daten und übermitteln nur die pseudonymisierten Daten ans LIFE Studienzentrums. Diese Ermächtigung gilt für den Zeitraum meiner Studienteilnahme.

ja nein

9. Einwilligung in eine zukünftige Kontaktaufnahme

Ich bin damit einverstanden, dass ich bis zu 20 Jahre nach der letzten Kontaktaufnahme vom LIFE-Zentrum kontaktiert werden kann, um gegebenenfalls an einer schriftlichen Befragung oder Nachfolgeuntersuchung teilzunehmen (für Nachfolgeuntersuchungen im Studienzentrums ist eine separate Einwilligungserklärung abzugeben). Ich stimme einer gegebenenfalls notwendigen Anfrage bei der Einwohnermeldebehörde zur Einholung der aktuellen Anschrift (bei eventuellem Umzug) zu.

ja nein

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10. Widerrufsrecht

Bioproben:

Ich weiß, dass ich meine Zustimmung zur Lagerung und Verwendung meiner Bioproben jederzeit und ohne Angabe von Gründen gegenüber dem LIFE-Zentrum widerrufen kann, ohne dass mir daraus Nachteile erwachsen.

Personenbezogene Daten:

Ich bin damit einverstanden, dass im Falle meines Widerrufs meine bisher erhobenen Untersuchungsergebnisse in anonymisierter Form weiter genutzt werden dürfen.

Im Falle eines Widerrufs wenden Sie sich bitte an Ihr LIFE Studienzentrum:

LIFE Studienzentrum für Erwachsene

Philipp-Rosenthal-Str. 27

04103 Leipzig

Telefon: 0341 / 97-16716

Fax: 0341 / 97-16719

Email: info-adult@life.uni-leipzig.de

11. Datenschutzrechtliche Einwilligung

Ich bin über den Zweck der personenbezogenen Datenverarbeitung informiert worden. Ich stimme zu, dass alle in der Studie erhobenen Daten, die meine Person betreffen, unter Verantwortung des LIFE-Zentrums der Universität Leipzig in pseudonymisierter Form gespeichert werden. Pseudonymisiert bedeutet, dass meine Identifikationsmerkmale wie Name und Anschrift durch eine Codenummer ersetzt werden. Damit ist eine Zuordnung zu meiner Person nur über Mitarbeiter der Einladungsstelle möglich, für die jedoch der Zugang zu den wissenschaftlichen Daten versperrt ist. Umgekehrt haben Wissenschaftler, die sich mit der Auswertung meiner Daten befassen, keinen Zugriff auf meine Identifikationsmerkmale

Das LIFE-Zentrum der Universität Leipzig sichert mir zu, dass meine personenbezogenen Daten ausschließlich für den o.g. Zweck unter Beachtung der datenschutzrechtlichen Vorschriften verarbeitet werden. Alle MitarbeiterInnen sind zur Vertraulichkeit verpflichtet.

Ich bin darüber informiert worden, dass das LIFE-Zentrum außerhalb gesetzlicher Verpflichtungen und ohne meine persönliche Anfrage und gesonderte Zustimmung keine personenidentifizierenden Ergebnisse meiner Untersuchungen an Dritte übermitteln darf.

Mir ist bekannt, dass Daten und Bioproben an wissenschaftliche Kooperationspartner außerhalb des LIFE-Zentrums im In- und Ausland in einer für den Empfänger anonymisierten Weise (d. h. ohne Nennung von Namen oder Anschrift) weitergegeben werden können. Ich bin darüber informiert worden, dass die Weitergabe auch an ausländische Kooperationspartner erfolgen kann, die möglicherweise weniger strengen Datenschutzvorschriften als der europäischen Datenschutzgrundverordnung unterliegen.

Ich wurde darüber informiert, dass die datenschutzverantwortliche Person die Universität Leipzig ist, vertreten durch Prof. Dr. med. Markus Löffler, Institut für Medizinische Informatik, Statistik und Epidemiologie, Härtelstrasse 16-18, 04107 Leipzig. Der zuständige Datenschutzbeauftragte ist Herr Ronald Speer, Datenschutzbeauftragter der Medizinischen Fakultät, Universität Leipzig, Philipp-Rosenthal-Str. 27, 04103 Leipzig. Ich wurde darüber informiert, dass ich im Zusammenhang mit den

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datenschutzrechtlichen Aspekten der Studie bei folgender Behörde ein Recht auf Beschwerde habe: Der Sächsische Datenschutzbeauftragte, Bernhard-von-Lindenau-Platz 1, 01067 Dresden, Telefon: 0351/493-5401, Telefax: 0351/493-5490, E-Mail: saechsdsb@slt.sachsen.de.

Ich wurde über folgende Rechte hinsichtlich der Verarbeitung meiner personenbezogenen Daten informiert: Widerruf ohne Angabe von Gründen, Auskunft inklusive Überlassung einer kostenlosen Kopie, Korrektur unrichtiger Daten, Löschung, Einschränkung der Verarbeitung, Übertragung. Mir ist bekannt, dass meine personenbezogenen Daten spätestens 20 Jahre nach der letzten Untersuchung/Befragung anonymisiert werden.

Mir ist bekannt, dass zur Überwachung des Aufklärungsprozesses und zur Kontrolle, ob die Daten und Proben auch entsprechend meiner Einwilligung gespeichert und verwendet werden, autorisierte Mitarbeiter des Zentrums für klinische Studien (ZKS Leipzig) der Universität Leipzig Zugang zu meinen Probandenunterlagen und meinen Einwilligungserklärungen haben.

12. Versicherungsobliegenheiten

Mir ist bekannt, dass für die studienbedingten Maßnahmen keine Versicherung besteht. Mir ist bekannt, dass im Rahmen dieser Studie eine Probanden-Wegeunfallversicherung bei folgendem Versicherungsunternehmen besteht:

Gothaer Allgemeine Versicherung AG

Gothaer Allee 1

50969 Köln

Versicherungsnummer: aus Datenschutzgründen gelöscht

13. Schlussbemerkung

Ich bin mir bewusst, keinerlei Ansprüche auf Vergütung, Tantieme oder sonstige Beteiligung an finanziellen Vorteilen und Gewinnen zu haben, die möglicherweise auf der Basis meiner Bioproben oder sonstiger Untersuchungen erlangt werden.

14. Inhalt der mündlichen Aufklärung

Folgende Punkte wurden zusätzlich zur schriftlichen Probandeninformation im mündlichen Aufklärungsgespräch besprochen:

Leipzig, den _____

Name der Teilnehmerin/ des Teilnehmers: _____

Unterschrift der Teilnehmerin/ des Teilnehmers: _____

Leipzig, den _____

Name der/des aufklärenden

Studienmitarbeiterin/Studienmitarbeiters: _____

Unterschrift der/des aufklärenden

Studienmitarbeiterin/Studienmitarbeiters: _____

12.2.3 Questionnaire in Germany

HBM-Modul LIFE

Sehr geehrte Teilnehmerin, sehr geehrter Teilnehmer,

neben der Untersuchung Ihres Gesundheitszustands möchten wir auch Ihre Belastung mit bestimmten umweltrelevanten Chemikalien erfassen. Die Aufnahme dieser Substanzen erfolgt hauptsächlich über die Nahrung. Darüber hinaus können auch Lebensgewohnheiten und das Arbeitsumfeld zu einer vermehrten Aufnahme beitragen.

Die nachfolgenden Fragen zielen speziell auf die in der Studie untersuchten Substanzen. Bitte beantworten Sie die Fragen nach bestem Wissen. Vielen Dank!

Wohnumgebung und häusliche Exposition

1. Wann wurde Ihr Wohnhaus ungefähr gebaut?

Vor 1918	<input type="checkbox"/>	1982-1997	<input type="checkbox"/>
1918-1933	<input type="checkbox"/>	1998-2008	<input type="checkbox"/>
1934-1949	<input type="checkbox"/>	Nach 2008	<input type="checkbox"/>
1950-1965	<input type="checkbox"/>	Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>
1966-1981	<input type="checkbox"/>		

2. Haben oder hatten Sie kürzlich eines der folgenden Probleme bei sich zu Hause?

	Ja	Nein	Weiß nicht
Schimmel oder Mehltau an Wänden oder anderen Oberflächen	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wasserschäden (z.B. Rohrbruch, undichtes Dach oder Überschwemmungen)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Muffiger oder schimmeliger Geruch	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Abblättern von Farbe an Wänden oder Fensterbänken	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Schwarzstaub/Fogging-Effekt (schwarze Verfärbungen an der Wand oder Decke, oft oberhalb von Heizungen oder elektrischen Geräten)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

3. Aus welchen Materialien bestehen die Bodenbeläge bei Ihnen zu Hause?

MATERIALIEN	Ja	Nein	Weiß nicht
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1. glatte Böden			
1.1. Holzparkett	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
1.2. Holzbretter (Dielen)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
1.3. Laminat	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
MATERIALIEN	Ja	Nein	Weiß nicht
1.4. PVC-Fußbodenbelag	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
1.5. Linoleum	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
1.6. Fliesen (z.B. Stein, Marmor, Terrazzo)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
1.7. Andere faserfreie/glatte Materialien	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Welche?			
2. Teppiche/Teppichböden			
2.1. Kunstfaser (z.B. Kunststoff-Velour)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2.2. Naturfaser (z.B. Wolle, Tierhaarmischungen)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2.3. Mischfaser	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2.4. Andere textile Bodenbeläge	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Welche?			

4. Bitte vervollständigen Sie die folgenden Informationen zu Renovierungsarbeiten bei Ihnen zu Hause. Wurden bei Ihnen zu Hause...

	Ja	Nein	Weiß nicht
in den letzten 2 Jahren größere Renovierungen durchgeführt? (z.B. neue Wände, Böden, Fenster...)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
im letzten Jahr kleinere Renovierungen durchgeführt?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

5. Gibt es eine der folgenden Einrichtungen/Betriebe innerhalb eines Umkreises von 300 m um Ihr Wohnhaus?

Einrichtung/Betriebsstätte	Ja	Nein	Weiß nicht
Automobilindustrie	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Batterieproduktion	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Zementwerk	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Glaswerk	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Chemische Industrie	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Einrichtung/Betriebsstätte	Ja	Nein	Weiß nicht
Farben-/Pigmentfabrik	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Metallherstellung/Verarbeitung	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Herstellung von elektronischen Komponenten (z.B.Computer, Mobiltelefone)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Herstellung von Solarzellen	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pharmazeutische Industrie	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fungizidherstellung	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pestizidherstellung	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Kohlekraftwerk	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Bergbau, Tagebau	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Geothermales Kraftwerk	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Recycling-Anlage	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Mülldeponie	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Kläranlage	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Müllverbrennungsanlage	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Nahrungsmittel-/Getränkekonsum

1. Wie oft haben Sie die folgenden Nahrungsmittel in den letzten 4 Wochen zu sich genommen? Bitte in jeder Zeile nur ein Kreuz!

Nahrungsmittel	Mehrmals täglich	Täglich bzw. fast täglich	Mehrmals in der Woche	Etwa einmal in der Woche	Zwei- bis dreimal im Monat	Einmal im Monat oder seltener	Fast nie oder nie
<u>Fettreiche Fische</u> (z.B. Aal, Hering, Lachs, Rollmops, Sprotten, Thunfisch, Waller (Wels), Makrele)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<u>Fettarme Fische</u> (z.B. Barsch, Forelle, Hecht, Heilbutt weiß, Kabeljau, Karpfen, Sardine, Scholle, Seehecht, Seelachs, Seeteufel, Seezunge, Steinbutt, Stör, Zander)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<u>Unabhängig der beiden ersten Fragen, speziell bezüglich der Quecksilberexposition</u> Lachs und Thunfisch	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<u>Meeresfrüchte</u> (z.B. Garnelen, Krabben, Tintenfisch, Muscheln, Austern)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<u>Meeresalgen</u> (z.B. in Sushi, Miso-Suppe, Algennudeln)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<u>Fleisch</u> (Schwein, Rind, Lamm)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<u>Geflügel</u>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<u>Wildfleisch</u> (z.B. Reh, Hirsch, Wildschwein)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<u>Backwaren</u> (z.B. Brot, Brötchen)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<u>Zerealien</u> (z.B. Müsli, Cornflakes)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<u>Teigwaren</u> (z.B. Nudeln, Gnocch),	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

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<u>Reis</u>	<input type="checkbox"/>						
<u>Pilze/Pilzgerichte</u>	<input type="checkbox"/>						
<u>Karotten/Möhren</u>	<input type="checkbox"/>						

2. Wie viel Wasser nehmen Sie im Durchschnitt pro Tag zu sich?

Denken Sie auch an mit Wasser zubereitete Heißgetränke wie Kaffee und Tee sowie an Suppen)

Weniger als 1 Liter am Tag	1-2 Liter am Tag	2-3 Liter am Tag	3-5 Liter am Tag	Mehr als 5 Liter am Tag	Weiß nicht
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

3. Was ist die Hauptquelle Ihres Trinkwassers?

Leitungswasser, öffentliches Wassernetzwerk <input type="checkbox"/>	Leitungswasser, eigener Brunnen <input type="checkbox"/>
Wasser aus Plastikflaschen <input type="checkbox"/>	Wasser aus Glasflaschen <input type="checkbox"/>
Andere Quelle <input type="checkbox"/> Welche?.....	Weiß nicht <input type="checkbox"/>

4. Haben Sie in den letzten 4 Wochen Fast food zu sich genommen?

Ja Nein Weiß nicht

Falls ja: Wie war das Fast food verpackt und wie oft haben Sie es zu sich genommen?

Verpackung	(fast) nie	1 Mal pro Monat	2-3 Mal pro Monat	1 Mal pro Woche	2-3 Mal pro Woche	4-6 Mal pro Woche	täglich	Weiß nicht
Karton/Pappbox	<input type="checkbox"/>							
Papier	<input type="checkbox"/>							
Pappbecher	<input type="checkbox"/>							
Plastikbecher	<input type="checkbox"/>							
Plastik (z.B. Tüte, Behälter)	<input type="checkbox"/>							
Styropor-Behälter/Box	<input type="checkbox"/>							
Aluminium-Schale/Box	<input type="checkbox"/>							

5. Wie häufig haben Sie in den letzten 4 Wochen Gemeinschaftsverpflegungseinrichtungen (z.B. Kantine, Cafeteria, Essen auf Rädern) genutzt?

(fast) nie	1 Mal pro Monat	2-3 Mal pro Monat	1 Mal pro Woche	2-3 Mal pro Woche	4-6 Mal pro Woche	1 Mal pro Tag	Mehrmals pro Tag	Weiß nicht
<input type="checkbox"/>								

6. Trinken Sie außer Wasser auch andere Getränke (Fruchtsäfte, Eistee, Limonaden...)? Falls ja, aus welchen Getränkebehältern kommen diese (Mehrere Antworten können angekreuzt werden)?

<input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	falls ja, Getränke aus: <input type="checkbox"/> Glasflaschen <input type="checkbox"/> Plastikflaschen <input type="checkbox"/> Dosen <input type="checkbox"/> Andere Behältnisse. <input type="checkbox"/> Welche?..... <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht
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7. Benutzen Sie die folgenden Behältnisse um Essen im Kühlschrank oder an anderen Orten länger zu lagern? Falls ja, wie häufig nutzen sie diese Behältnisse?

Behältnis	(fast) nie	1 Mal pro Monat	2-3 Mal pro Monat	1 Mal pro Woche	2-3 Mal pro Woche	4-6 Mal pro Woche	täglich	Weiß nicht
Hartplastik-Container (fest, starr)	<input type="checkbox"/>							
Weichplastik-Container (leicht biegsam, wie z.B. Joghurtbecher)	<input type="checkbox"/>							
Backpapier	<input type="checkbox"/>							
Plastiktüten	<input type="checkbox"/>							
Aluminiumdosen/-boxen	<input type="checkbox"/>							
Keramik (z.B. Schüsseln)	<input type="checkbox"/>							
Glas	<input type="checkbox"/>							
Andere Welche?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>							
Weiß nicht <input type="checkbox"/>								

8. Benutzen Sie die folgenden Behältnisse um Essen in der Mikrowelle zuzubereiten oder aufzuwärmen? Falls ja, wie häufig nutzen sie diese Behältnisse in der Mikrowelle?

Behältnis	(fast) nie	1 Mal pro Monat	2-3 Mal pro Monat	1 Mal pro Woche	2-3 Mal pro Woche	4-6 Mal pro Woche	1 Mal pro Tag	Mehrmals pro Tag	Weiß nicht
Hartplastik-Container (fest, starr)	<input type="checkbox"/>								
Weichplastik-Container (leicht biegbar, wie z.B. Joghurtbecher)	<input type="checkbox"/>								
Styropor-Box/Dose	<input type="checkbox"/>								
Karton-/Pappboxen	<input type="checkbox"/>								
Keramik	<input type="checkbox"/>								
Glas	<input type="checkbox"/>								
Andere Welche?.....	<input type="checkbox"/>								
Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>								

Lifestyle

1. **Angaben zum Passivrauchen: Wie viele Personen - Sie ausgeschlossen - rauchen regelmäßig bei Ihnen zu Hause (drinnen)? Bitte geben Sie für jeden die durchschnittliche Anzahl an gerauchten Zigaretten pro Tag an.**

Haushaltsmitglied	Rauchverhalten
Nummer 1	Anzahl Zigaretten pro Tag __ __ <input type="checkbox"/> weiß nicht
Nummer 2	Anzahl Zigaretten pro Tag __ __ <input type="checkbox"/> weiß nicht
Nummer 3	Anzahl Zigaretten pro Tag __ __ <input type="checkbox"/> weiß nicht
Nummer 4	Anzahl Zigaretten pro Tag __ __ <input type="checkbox"/> weiß nicht

2. **Wurden in den letzten 4 Wochen mindestens einmal pro Woche die unten aufgeführten Reinigungsprodukte bei Ihnen zu Hause angewendet? Falls ja, bitte geben Sie an, ob es sich bei dem verwendeten Reinigungsmittel um ein konventionelles chemisches oder um ein umweltfreundliches Produkt handelt.**

Produkte	Ja	Nein	Weiß nicht	Falls ja, Produktart:
Reinigungsmittel für Küche, Bad, Boden, Fenster (z.B. Allzweckreiniger, Fenster/Glasreiniger)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> Chemisch /konventionell <input type="checkbox"/> Umweltfreundlich <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht
Bodenwachs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> Chemisch /konventionell <input type="checkbox"/> Umweltfreundlich <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht
Weichspüler	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> Chemisch /konventionell <input type="checkbox"/> Umweltfreundlich <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht

Holz-/Möbelpolitur	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> Chemisch /konventionell <input type="checkbox"/> Umweltfreundlich <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht
Produkte	Ja	Nein	Weiß nicht	Falls ja, Produktart:
Chemische Reinigungsmittel (z.B. zum Reinigen von Polstern, Kleidern, Teppichen)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> Chemisch /konventionell <input type="checkbox"/> Umweltfreundlich <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht
Lufterfrischer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> Chemisch /konventionell <input type="checkbox"/> Umweltfreundlich <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht
Lösungsmittel (z.B. Terpentin)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> Chemisch /konventionell <input type="checkbox"/> Umweltfreundlich <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht
Fleckentferner	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> Chemisch /konventionell <input type="checkbox"/> Umweltfreundlich <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht
Imprägniermittel (z.B. für Polster, Schuhe)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> Chemisch /konventionell <input type="checkbox"/> Umweltfreundlich <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht
Andere Reinigungsprodukte Welche?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> Chemisch /konventionell <input type="checkbox"/> Umweltfreundlich <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht

3. Wie alt ist das Auto, in dem Sie die meiste Zeit verbringen?

(Angabe bitte in Monaten, wenn Ihr Auto weniger als 2 Jahre alt ist)

___ ___ Jahre

oder ___ ___ Monate

Weiß nicht

4. Wie oft haben Sie in den letzten 4 Wochen die folgenden Kosmetik- und Hygieneprodukte verwendet?

	Nie	Gelegentlich	Mehrmals im Monat	Einmal pro Woche	Täglich	Weiß nicht
Haar(styling)produkte						
Haarspray, Haarlack, Haargel, Schaumfestiger	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Conditioner	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Färbemittel, Tönung	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Andere Produkte <input type="checkbox"/>						
Welche?.....						
Kosmetika						
Make-up (z.B. Puder, flüssig)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Lippenbalsam (z.B. Labello)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Lippenstift	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Augenmake-up (nicht wasserfest) (z.B..Lidschatten, Eyeliner)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Make-up-Entferner	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Nagellack	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Andere Produkte <input type="checkbox"/>						
Welche?.....						
Körperpflegeprodukte						
Parfüm / Eau de Cologne	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Körper- oder Handlotion (Creme, Milch,...)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Seife / Duschgel	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Anti-Alterungs-/Falten-Creme	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Sonnenschutz/Sonnencreme	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Deodorant	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Rasierschaum oder Aftershave Lotion	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Mundspülung	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Andere Produkte <input type="checkbox"/> Welche?.....						

5. Falls Sie Sonnencreme benutzen: Welche Art von Sonnencreme nutzen Sie normalerweise?

- Konventionelle Sonnencreme (nicht auf Mineralbasis)
- Sonnencreme auf Mineralbasis
- Ich weiß nicht, ob die benutzte Sonnencreme auf Mineralbasis ist

6. Falls Sie Sonnencreme benutzen: Wie wenden Sie diese normalerweise an? Als ...

- Creme
- Spray (Aerosol)
- Roll-On
- Weiß nicht

7. Welche Art von Körperpflegeprodukten verwenden Sie am häufigsten?

- Natürliche und umweltfreundliche
- Chemische
- Weiß nicht

8. Tragen Sie regelmäßig Plastik- oder Gummischeue wie z.B. Flip-Flops, Strandschuhe, Badeschuhe, Crocs® oder Clogs ohne Socken?

- Ja
- Nein
- Weiß nicht

9. Haben Sie die Angewohnheit, Gegenstände aus Kunststoff (z. B. Stifte, Brillen oder Spielzeug) in den Mund zu nehmen und darauf zu kauen?

- Ja
- Nein
- Weiß nicht

Falls ja, wie oft kommt das vor?

Täglich	Mehrmals in der Woche	Seltener	Weiß nicht
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Berufshistorie

1. Haben Sie in Ihren oben genannten vorherigen Arbeitsverhältnissen eine der folgenden Arbeitsaufgaben/-aktivitäten ausgeführt? Wenn ja, bitte geben Sie die gesamte Dauer an, während derer Sie die Arbeitsaufgabe/-Aktivität ausgeführt haben, ob Sie dabei persönliche Schutzausrüstung verwendet haben und ob kollektive/gemeinschaftliche Schutzmaßnahmen vorhanden waren.

Arbeitsaufgabe / -Aktivität	Dauer der Ausführung (in Jahren)								Persönliche Schutzausrüstung? Welche?	Kollektive Schutzmaßnahmen? Welche?
	<1	1-2	2-5	5-10	10-15	15-20	20-25	>25		
Verbrennung von fossilen Brennstoffen (z.B. Kohle, Öl) <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Bergbau und/oder Aufbereitung von Erzen <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Zinnober-Bergbau <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Gießerei und/oder Schmelzen von Arsenhaltigen Metallen <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Gießerei und/oder Schmelzen von anderen Metallen (z.B. Quecksilber, Kupfer, Metall-, Sulfiderze, Zink) <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Herstellung, Handhabung oder Verwendung von Anti-Reibungs-Zusätzen für Metalle <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		

Herstellung von Automobilteilen <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Herstellung von elektronischen Komponenten <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Arbeitsaufgabe / -Aktivität	Dauer der Ausführung (in Jahren)								Persönliche Schutzausrüstung? Welche?	Kollektive Schutzmaßnahmen? Welche?
	<1	1-2	2-5	5-10	10-15	15-20	20-25	>25		
Herstellung von Halbleitern <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Herstellung von Solar-Zellen <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Herstellung, Handhabung oder Verwendung von Batterien <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Galvanisieren <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Herstellung von Fluoreszenzlampen/ Leuchtstoffröhren <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Herstellung von Präzisioninstrumenten <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Zimmerei und Holzarbeiten (vor allem Arbeitsaktivitäten unter Verwendung von chromiertem Kupfer-Arsenat (CCA) oder CCA-behandeltem Holz)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		

<input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht										
Glasherstellung <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Zementherstellung <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Herstellung, Handhabung oder Verwendung von Farben <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Herstellung von Papier <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Arbeitsaufgabe / -Aktivität	Dauer der Ausführung (in Jahren)								Persönliche Schutzausrüstung? Welche?	Kollektive Schutzmaßnahmen? Welche?
	<1	1-2	2-5	5-10	10-15	15-20	20-25	>25		
Herstellung, Handhabung oder Verwendung von Chloralkali <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Handhabung von Klärschlamm <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Sammeln von festen Abfällen <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Entsorgung und/oder Verbrennung von festen Abfällen <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		

Altlastensanierung (Erneuerung kontaminierter Böden) <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>									
Recycling von Altbatterien <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>									
Recycling elektronischer Teile <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>									
Pharmazeutische Industrie <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>									
Herstellung, Handhabung oder Benutzung von arsenhaltigen Pestiziden <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>									
Herstellung, Handhabung oder Benutzung von Fungiziden <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>									
Herstellung, Handhabung oder Benutzung von Leder-Konservierungsmitteln <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>									
Taxidermie/Tierpräparation <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	<input type="checkbox"/>									

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Zahngesundheit

1. Haben Sie momentan oder hatten Sie jemals Amalgamfüllungen in Ihren Zähnen?

Ja Nein Weiß nicht

1.1 Falls ja, in wie vielen Zähnen haben sie momentan Amalgamfüllungen?

In ___ ___ Zähnen Weiß nicht

1.2 Falls ja, in wie vielen Zähnen hatten sie Amalgamfüllungen, die mittlerweile ersetzt wurden?

In ___ ___ Zähnen Weiß nicht

1.3 Wann wurde das letzte Mal eine Amalgamfüllung eingesetzt?

(Angabe in Tagen, Monaten oder Jahren)

Vor ___ ___ Tagen / vor ___ ___ Monaten / vor ___ ___ Jahren Weiß nicht

1.4 Wann wurde das letzte Mal eine Amalgamfüllung entfernt/ersetzt? (Angabe in Tagen, Monaten oder Jahren)

Vor ___ ___ Tagen / vor ___ ___ Monaten / vor ___ ___ Jahren Weiß nicht

Kürzliche Exposition

1. Wann haben Sie vor der Probenabgabe zuletzt die folgenden Nahrungsmittel zu sich genommen?

	Gar nicht	Vor weniger als 12 Stunden	Vor 12 bis 24 Stunden	Vor 24 bis 48 Stunden	Vor mehr als 48 Stunden	Weiß nicht
Fisch und Meeresfrüchte (z.B. Lachs, Thunfisch, andere Fischarten, Hummer, Garnelen, Shrimps, Tintenfisch, Krabben, Austern, Muscheln)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Getreideprodukte (z.B. Brot, Brötchen, Müsli, Cornflakes, Cracker, Körner, Nudeln, Reis)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fleisch (z.B. Schwein, Lamm, Rind)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Geflügel	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Innereien	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wildfleisch (z.B. Reh, Hirsch, Wildschwein)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Milchprodukte (z.B. Butter, Milch, Käse, Joghurt)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Eier	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fette (tierisch, z.B. Schmalz und pflanzlich, z.B. Oliven-, Raps-, Sonnenblumenöl)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Gemüse	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Früchte	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Erdnüsse	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Haselnussaufstrich (z.B. Nutella)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Eiscreme	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Gelee-Bonbons	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Geräuchertes Essen (z.B. Räucherschinken, Räucherlachs, Räucherkäse, Räucherwurst)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Gegrilltes Essen (über offener Flamme oder über Glut gegrillt)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Fast food (z.B. Döner, Pizza, Hamburger)	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Fertiggerichte in Plastikverpackung	<input type="checkbox"/>					

2. Haben Sie während der letzten 24 Stunden vor der Probenabgabe Getränke aus den folgenden Getränkebehältern zu sich genommen?

Es können mehrere Antworten angekreuzt werden. Denken Sie bitte an alle Getränke inklusive Wasser, Heiß-/Kaltgetränke und alkoholische Getränke.

<input type="checkbox"/> Glasflasche	<input type="checkbox"/> Plastikflasche	<input type="checkbox"/> Dose	<input type="checkbox"/> Plastiktasse
<input type="checkbox"/> Plastikbecher	<input type="checkbox"/> Styroporbecher	<input type="checkbox"/> Pappkarton	<input type="checkbox"/> Keine der oben genannten

3. Haben Sie während der letzten 24 Stunden vor der Probenabgabe Fast food zu sich genommen?

Fast food sind verarbeitete Lebensmittel, die einfach und schnell zubereitet werden, häufig in Imbissstuben und Cafés serviert werden und oft zum Mitnehmen verpackt werden

<input type="checkbox"/>	ja	► Weiter mit Frage 3.1.
<input type="checkbox"/>	nein	

3.1. Wie war dieses Fast food verpackt?

<i>Es können mehrere Antworten angekreuzt werden.</i>	
a) In Pappe/Karton	<input type="checkbox"/>
b) In Papier (Tüte, Schachtel/Box)	<input type="checkbox"/>
c) In Kunststoff/Plastik (Tüte, Schachtel/Dose, Tasse)	<input type="checkbox"/>
d) In Styroporschaum (Schachtel/Dose, Becher)	<input type="checkbox"/>
e) In Aluminiumbehälter (Schachtel, Dose)	<input type="checkbox"/>
f) In anderer Verpackung	<input type="checkbox"/> Welche?

4. Waren Sie während der letzten 24 Stunden vor der Probenabgabe Tabakrauch ausgesetzt?

<input type="checkbox"/> Ja, Ich habe selbst geraucht	Weiter mit Frage 4.1.
---	-----------------------

<input type="checkbox"/> Ja, Ich war als Passivraucher Tabakrauch ausgesetzt	Weiter mit Frage 4.2.
<input type="checkbox"/> Nein	

4.1. Wie viele Zigaretten haben Sie während der letzten 24 Stunden vor der Probenabgabe geraucht?

<input type="checkbox"/> 1-5
<input type="checkbox"/> 6-10
<input type="checkbox"/> Mehr als 10
<input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht

4.2. Wie lange waren Sie während der letzten 24 Stunden vor der Probenabgabe Tabakrauch als Passivraucher ausgesetzt?

<input type="checkbox"/> Weniger als 1 Stunde
<input type="checkbox"/> 1 bis 4 Stunden
<input type="checkbox"/> Mehr als 4 Stunden
<input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht

5. Haben Sie während der letzten 24 Stunden vor der Probenabgabe Schnupftabak verwendet?

<i>Dies bezieht sich auf eine Vielzahl rauchloser Tabakerzeugnisse, die über die Mund- oder Nasenschleimhaut aufgenommen werden</i>	
<input type="checkbox"/> Ja	Weiter mit Frage 5.1
<input type="checkbox"/> Nein	
<input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht	

5.1. Wie viele Schnupftabakladungen haben sie in den letzten 24 Stunden vor der Probenabgabe verwendet?

<input type="checkbox"/> 1-2
<input type="checkbox"/> 2-5
<input type="checkbox"/> Mehr als 5

6. Wann haben Sie innerhalb der letzten 48 Stunden vor der Probenabgabe zuletzt folgende Aktivitäten durchgeführt oder daran teilgenommen?

Bitte denken Sie bei der Beantwortung dieser Frage an alle Aktivitäten (z.B. Hausarbeit, Heimwerken, Hobbys), die zu einer berufsfremden Exposition gegenüber Umweltschadstoffen geführt haben könnten. Bitte geben Sie in der letzten Spalte an, ob Sie bei diesen Aktivitäten Schutzausrüstung (Atemmaske, Handschuhe) getragen haben.

	Gar nicht	Vor weniger als 12 Stunden	Vor 12 bis 24 Stunden	Vor 24 bis 48 Stunden	Vor mehr als 48 Stunden	Weiß nicht	Schutzausrüstung getragen
Reparaturen/ Wartungen/ Bauvorhaben am Haus/in der Wohnung (z.B. Holz- oder Glasverarbeitung, Verwendung von Zement, Oberflächenschutzmitteln oder Holzschutzmitteln)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> ja
Ledergerbung (d.h. Verwendung von Lederkonservierungsmitteln)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> ja
Gartenarbeit mit Verwendung von Düngemitteln (z.B. Kompost oder Klärschlamm, phosphathaltige Düngemittel)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> ja
Umgang mit Metallen (z.B. Schweißen, Verwendung von Metallen oder Legierungen)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> ja
Umgang mit Elektronik (z.B. Löten, elektrische Schaltkreise konstruieren)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> ja
Kontakt mit Kunststoffen (z.B. Plastikhandschuhe, wiederverwendbare Essens- oder Getränkebehälter, Herstellung oder Verarbeitung von Plastikprodukten)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> ja
Verwendung von Farbstoffen, Farben oder Tinten (z.B. Anwendung von Haar- oder Textilfärbemitteln, Handhaben von Tätowiertinte, Durchführen von Drucken, (Kunst-)Malerei)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> ja
Handhabung von Fluoreszenzlampen/ Leuchtstoffröhren	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> ja
Kontakt mit Rauch (z.B. Kaminfeuer, Lagerfeuer, Verbrennung von Gartenabfällen)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> ja

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Anwendung/Sprühen von Pflanzenschutzmitteln	<input type="checkbox"/> ja						
Anwendung/Sprühen von Insektenvernichtungsmitteln	<input type="checkbox"/> ja						

7. Haben Sie in den letzten 2 Monaten vor der Probenabgabe homöopathische Arzneimittel eingenommen?

<input type="checkbox"/> Nein	<input type="checkbox"/> Ja, vor weniger als 5 Stunden	<input type="checkbox"/> Ja, vor 5 bis 12 Stunden	<input type="checkbox"/> Ja, vor 12 bis 24 Stunden
<input type="checkbox"/> Ja, innerhalb der letzten 2-3 Tage	<input type="checkbox"/> Ja, vor 3 bis 30 Tagen	<input type="checkbox"/> Ja, vor 1 bis 2 Monaten	<input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht

8. Haben Sie in den letzten 2 Monaten vor der Probenabgabe hautaufhellende Cremes angewendet?

<input type="checkbox"/> Nein	<input type="checkbox"/> Ja, innerhalb der letzten 3 Tage	<input type="checkbox"/> Ja, vor 3 bis 30 Tagen	<input type="checkbox"/> Ja, vor 1 bis 2 Monaten	<input type="checkbox"/> Weiß nicht
-------------------------------	---	---	--	-------------------------------------

9. Haben Sie sich in den letzten 24 Stunden vor der Probenabgabe einer der folgenden medizinischen Untersuchungen/Behandlungen unterzogen?

<input type="checkbox"/> Blutspende
<input type="checkbox"/> Dialyse

10. Haben Sie in den letzten 24 Stunden vor der Probenabgabe Gegenstände aus Kunststoff (z. B. Stifte, Brillen oder Spielzeug) in den Mund genommen und/oder darauf gekaut?

<input type="checkbox"/> Ja
<input type="checkbox"/> Nein

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12.3 Appendix 3. Evaluation meeting, pp-presentations

12.3.1 Finnish feasibility study

KouBio-Kuopio – Study aims, conduct and challenges

Panu Rantakokko, Jani Koponen
3rd March 2021

Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare

PLAN: Aims of the KouBio-Kuopio Study

1. Collect information about health and chemical exposures of 5th and 6th grade students (10-13 years) from the selected primary schools of Kuopio area
2. Assess exposure to selected chemicals (phthalates and bisphenols from urine samples, and possible also PFAS from blood samples)
3. Assess if the construction years of the school buildings is reflected in the biomonitoring results

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PLAN: Target group and sample selection

- Schools selected based on their willingness to participate
- Aim to have 2-3 schools at least 10 years old and other 2-3 schools less than 10 years old
- Schools close to center of Kuopio (± 10 km)
- All students in 5th and 6th grade invited to participate
- Sample size from HBM4EU requirements: 300 children participating \rightarrow assuming 70% participation rate \rightarrow at least 430 students to be invited

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PLAN: Information and sample collection

- Basic information about students from the schools
- Health status of students collected with personal identifier linked to different data sources
- Lifestyle information and diet obtained through web based questionnaires that child fills-in with their parents
- During the regular health check-up at the school nurse/doctor, a spot urine sample will be collected.
- If allowed by the ethical approval and parents of the child, also venous blood sample collected by THL study personnel

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PLAN: Information and sample collection

Source of the information	Information/samples
Administrative registers	Sex, date of birth, social security number Medical history and follow-up information (AvoHILMO and HILMO) Medical prescriptions (KELA)
Questionnaire	Dietary habits Living environment Lifestyle Health Socio-demographic information
Health examination	Anthropometric measurements of height and weight Blood pressure (if feasible)
Biological samples	Spot urine (phthalates, bisphenols) Possibly blood sample (PFAS)

PLAN: Original plan of study timeline

	2018		2019												
	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
Preparation of the study plan															
Contacts to the school system															
Contacts to school health care system															
Contacts to individual schools															
Preparation of material for ethical approval															
Questionnaire and other material (electronic material, printing etc.)															
Recruitment and training of personnel															
Fieldwork															

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Challenges in the preparatory phase

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REALITY – Contacts with City of Kuopio

- Approval from city of Kuopio needed before submission of ethical approval to ethical board of Kuopio Univ. Hospital
- **30th Nov. 2018: FIRST CONTACT** to Kuopio school authorities
- **4th Dec. 2018:** Study brochure sent
- **14th Feb. 2019:** Reply from city after several contacts
- **27th Feb. 2019:** Research Permission Form submitted
- **26th March 2019: POSITIVE DECISION** after several contacts
- **Total time with city 4 months → FIRST MAJOR PROBLEM**

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REALITY - Application of ethical permission

- Ethical Board of the Kuopio University Hospital required 5 additional documents, GDPR-requirements very tricky
- **6th May 2019: FIRST SUBMISSION** for ethical approval
- **24th May 2019** : 18 point list of corrections
- **7th June 2019** : Corrections sent
- **28th June 2019** : 2 more corrections (GDPR and patient insurance)
- **8th July 2019** : Corrections sent
- **30th July 2019** : **POSITIVE DECISION**
- **Total time with ethical permission 3 months → SECOND MAJOR PROBLEM → SCHOOLS START IN 10-15 DAYS!!**

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REALITY - Changes to study plan during process

- Ethical board requested more detailed description of the process to get informed consent prior to sampling at health check-ups and more detailed justification for blood sampling
- Due to delays, not enough time to get the informed consent from parents before the school check-ups that start late august
 - Urine only sampling conducted **at home** was chosen
 - Blood samples and analysis of PFAS discarded
 - Need to substantially downgrade study plan!!
- **We were at least 4 months late with the first contact to city of Kuopio if we wished to have maintained the original plan – it would have been difficult even with sufficient time**

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Fieldwork

REALITY – School visits

- Contacts before the visits to the schools went well, but not always clear who was responsible for arranging the visit
- Teachers were generally not interested, reflected in pupils
- The visits themselves went well
- The group sizes in the schools were too large to allow more student-oriented presentation
- After presentation, more than half of the students tried to leave without a sampling package
- **Sampling should be done during health check-ups as originally planned, motivation of teachers and guardians important**

REALITY: participation

	PLAN	REALITY
Participated schools	5-7	7
Invited children	430	1200
Participated children	300	70
Participation rate	70 %	6 %

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9.4.1 German feasibility study

Additional Feasibility Studies for
Combining HBM and Health studies

German Feasibility Study –
Adding HBM to the LIFE Adult Study

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Leipziger Forschungszentrum für Zivilisationserkrankungen

Erwachsenenkohorten

Feasibility study in Germany

LIFE Adult - Adult Cohort

- 10,000 randomly selected participants from the Leipzig population (2011 to 2014).
- 1 Follow-up from 2017 - 2021
- Age between 40 and 79 years
- Participants went through an investigation program of at least 6 hours.
- People 60 years and older were examined on two further days with questions on cognition and depression (including MRI, EEG).
- Extensive measurements of genome, metabolome and transcriptome.

Feasibility study in Germany

LIFE Adult - Adult Cohort

© Fraunhofer IBMT

Loeffler et al., BMC Public Health, 2015

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IBMT

Feasibility study in Germany

LIFE Adult - Adult Cohort

Assessment

Anthropometry
Heart function
Vascular system
Glucose metabolism
Physical activity, fitness and sleep
Macula and glaucoma degeneration
Neuroimaging and neurocognition
Allergy
Interviews, questionnaires

Examples

3D-bodyscan, height, weight
Echocardiography, heart ultrasound
Carotid artery sonography, blood pressure
oGTT, fasting glucose, HbA1c
7-day actinometry
Optical coherence tomography
MRI, cognitive tests
Prick-test
Smoking habit, nutrition, lifestyle

Loeffler et al., BMC Public Health, 2015

Feasibility study in Germany

LIFE Adult - Adult Cohort

	ADULT-Cohort	CHILD-Cohort	HEART-Cohort
Population size	10.000	4.000	7.000
Population source	Population based	Population based	CVD-Patients
Biobanking (DNA, RNA, Serum, EDTA, Urine)	all	all	all
Laboratory profiling	80 parameters	80 parameters	80 parameters
Physical activity, partly with actometers	all	all	all
3d-Body shape	all	all	---
Eye Fundus/Retina OCT	9.300	subcohort	---
Cardiovascular Phenotypes	all (Carotis Plaques/IMT, ABI/PWV, ECHO)	all (IMT, endothelial function)	all (Coronary Angio, Carotis Plaques/IMT, ABI, ECHO)
Brain MRI (3T)	2.700	---	100
Abdominal MRI (3T)	1.200	---	---
Genotypes genome wide	7.500	3.000	5.800
WBC- gene expression profiling	3.500	1.000	4.500
Metabolomic profiling	10.000	2.000	7.000
Follow up	7-Yr Follow up ongoing	yearly Follow up ongoing	10-Yr Follow up in planning phase

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Feasibility study in Germany

LIFE Adult - Adult Cohort

SERUM	SERUM	SERUM
Electrolytes	Iron metabolism	Inflammation
Sodium	Transferrin	CRP (high sensitive)
Potassium	Ferritin	IL-6
Chloride	Vitamin	Autoimmunity / Allergy
Magnesium	Folic Acid	SK1
Liver / Pancreas	Vitamin B12	PK5
Alanine aminotransferase (ALAT)	Docu and Acid	IgG (total)
Aspartate aminotransferase (ASAT)	Alkaline phosphatase (ALP)	EDSA WHOLE BLOOD
Gamma-Glutamyl Transferase (GGT)	Calcium	Hematology
Bilirubin total	Phosphor	Diff. Blood count (n=5)
Bilirubin direct/ indirect calculated	Calcitonin	Erythrocytes
Albumin	Dioxecalcin	Theorocytes
Protein (total), (ALP)	B-Crosslaps	Lymphocytes
Urea	Procollagen type 1 (P1NP)	Reticulocytes
Creatinin	PTH	Erythrocyte indices (n=4)
Urea	25-OH-Vit.D3 (Calcidiol)	Hemoglobin
Cystatin C	Stroids and Sex Hormones	Hemoglobin A1c (G)
Uric acid	Cortisol	URINE
Heart	FSH	Kidney function
Creatin Kinase	Estrodel	Albumin
Troponin-T (high sensitive)	Testosterone	Creatinin
NT-proBNP	SHBG	IgG (total)
Lipid Metabolism	DMSS-S	Alpha-1-Microglobulin
Cholesterol	Thyroid Hormones	Dipstick
HDL cholesterol	TSH	MetabolomeProfil (n=8)
LDL cholesterol	T3	26 Amino acids
Apo B	T4	37 Acyl carnitines
Apo A1	Thyroglobulin antibodies	
Triglycerides	Thyroxine antibodies	
Lipoprotein (a)	TSH receptor antibodies	
Glucose metabolism		
Glucose		
C-peptide		
Insulin		

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Components

- Sample (size, frame, structure)
- Recruitment of participants
- Ethics and Data Protection (e.g. ethical approval, informed consent)
- Questionnaires
- Sampling (sample type, methods, processes, materials)
- Sample storage

Do these components of LIFE meet the requirements of HBM-surveys?

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Tasks of Fraunhofer IBMT / LIFE

Step 1: Requirements Analysis

Examination and evaluation of existing documents, methods and samples

- ethical and legal documents
- available questionnaires
- pre-analytical processes (eg sampling, sample preparation, storage)
- Sample types (matrix, volume, sample containers)
- Quality assurance and quality control

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Tasks of Fraunhofer IBMT / LIFE

Step 2: Development of an HBM module and integration strategy

Adaptation, revision and supplementation of:

- Information materials
- Ethical aspects (Ethics application) – incl. re-contact, release from confidentiality for physicians, permission for extensive data queries from e.g. health insurance companies
- Survey instruments
- Incentives
- Sampling processes
- Storage processes (sample vessels, volume, storage temperature)

DONE

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Tasks of Fraunhofer IBMT / LIFE

Step 3: Integration in LIFE Adult

- Development of SOPs for individual HBM components
- Training of LIFE Adult staff members
- Successful application of the HBM module for collecting HBM-relevant data and obtaining suitable human samples for pollutant monitoring.

DONE

Step 4: Assess and summarize the results

- Reporting

Internal call did not include funding for chemical analysis!

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Tasks of Fraunhofer IBMT / LIFE

Outcome

- Priorized substances (phthalates, arsenic & its compounds, mercury & its organic compounds)
- Implemented questionnaire with 21 sides (single, basic and matrix-specific)
- Trained staff members
- Implemented SOPs for sample collection including field blind samples
- Stored urine samples from 400 study participants (3 x 4 ml) + 20 field blind samples

Open

- quality assurance process and epidemiological data control for LIFE database

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9.4.2 UK feasibility study

HBM and the Health Survey for England

SWOT Analysis

Lorraine Stewart
Ovnair Sepai
Public Health England

science and policy for a healthy future

Introduction

Health Survey for England (HSfE)

- Annual Survey (Est. 1991)
- General Population
- Questionnaire
- Nurse Visit
- Collect blood, urine (saliva)
- Focused topics of interest

HBM in Public Health England (PHE)

- Do not have a National HBM programme
- Have been many calls for such a programme
- No national baseline exposure data
- No means to assess population exposure
- Have access to health data
- Have access to dietary data

Assessing the Addition of a HBM Module to HSfE

Tool to assess 'An Option'

The Objective – to link a HBM Module to HSfE

The Organisation – HSfE and PHE

The Environment – external pressures

SWOT ANALYSIS

	Helpful to achieving the objective	Harmful to achieving the objective
Internal origin (attributes of the organization)	S Strengths	W Weaknesses
External origin (attributes of the environment)	O Opportunities	T Threats

Strengths

- Unique Selling Point (UPS): Frameworks is already established
- Government Digital services- compliance already established
- Strong scientific input from UCL
- Core questions on demography etc are established
- Ethical approval – established
- Extensive quality control / assurance
- Trained staff – nurses, interviewers etc
- Access to stored (biobanked) samples
- Efficiency and cost saving

DO NOT NEED TO START FROM SCRATCH

Weaknesses

- Only in England
- Restricted in what we can add
- Restricted to HSfE's sampling frame
- Difficult to target – HBM
- Blood sampling in children prohibitively expensive
- Data only available after 2 years
- Reliant on HSfE – core funding/ allowing us to add HBM

Opportunities

- Chance to align with HBM4EU
- Fulfil PHE needs
- Link with numerous other programmes in PHE
 - Tracking
 - PHE Population Survey Board
 - Target studies – e.g. lead
- Link with other Government objectives
- Possible to address occupational exposures
- Linking other PHE data – e.g. environmental exposures / incidents

KEY PARTNERSHIP

Threats

- COVID – 19 (other priorities)
- Funding – long-term
- Need analytical capabilities
- Long-term storage of samples
- Data management
- Political

Outcomes – when we are successful

- Monitor and evaluate UK Chemical Strategy
- Creation of an evolving database of chemical exposure
- Evaluate chemical policy
- Enhance public health protection
- Input to:
 - 25 Year Environment Plan
 - National Adaption Plan

Thank You

Lorraine and Ovnair

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